

ENPOWER
POWER IN OUR HANDS

D5.1 – ‘First wave’ of ENPOWER data-driven services for energy- secure communities

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Energy Activated Citizens and Data-Driven Energy-Secure Communities for a Consumer-Centric Energy System

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Preface

ENPOWER will design, develop, and demonstrate SSH-driven methodologies, interactive and closed-loop tools, and data-driven services for energy-activated citizens and energy-secure cross-sector communities towards a citizen-centric energy system. We combine leading-edge ICTs with social/behavioural dimensions and with sharing economy and value stacking business models to deploy: 1) a Social Science Framework for energy citizens activation and innovative multidimensional incentives for citizens' participation in energy markets; 2) AI-based consumers clustering and segmentation algorithms; 3) interactive tools and facilitation services for energy community planning; 4) Energy Data Space adaptation to support community-level data-driven activation and interoperable automated privacy and sovereignty-preserving Demand Response (DR); 5) P2P DLT/Blockchain digital marketplace for tokenized energy and non-energy assets reciprocal compensation; 6) data-driven services and apps for energy efficiency and activation performance management; 7) ICT services and Digital Twins for community-level energy optimisation and aggregated flexibility management to trade off local self-consumption against grid service provisioning, while boosting a beyond-energy community social welfare; 8) Edge monitoring hubs for automated DR; 9) Business Sandbox for novel sharing economy and social innovation-based business models; 10) methodologies for evaluating different energy community setups, upscaling and replication. ENPOWER framework will be validated along 4 Front Runners energy communities' pilots and further replicated in 2 Early Adopters, covering different levels of maturity of communities, to demonstrate increased Renewable Energy Sources (RES) local self-consumption and consumers participation in the energy markets, while nurturing increased local security of supply. ENPOWER Leadership Programme and blueprints will support EU-wide replication and advise regulatory bodies on communities-friendly enabling frameworks.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable reports the initial findings of work performed under WP5 related to: (i) the enhancement of existing digital services; (ii) the design of new consumer data-driven energy services for energy-secure communities and (iii) providing models and digital tools to implement these services in the pilots under WP6. The main goal of this deliverable is to clearly define and describe each tool and service to be used by the pilots under WP6.

Firstly, the deliverable presents a literature review focused on user behaviour, change of behaviour and motivation for the users to participate in energy communities. A set of technical papers, reports, workshops, etc were explored and served as the basis for this study. In addition, a set of workshops were undertaken and feedback from the user perspective is reported to assist in the design of the energy services for energy communities.

Among the many tools and services that are provided within the WP5, flexibility assessment and planning tools, including two digital twins of flexibility assets are provided and described. A clear picture of the digital twins of electric water heaters and heat pumps is provided, enabling their preparation for integration (as modules) in other community planning and operating tools. Flexibility assessment tools, based on clustering algorithms and casualty models are described.

In addition, a set of self-consumption tools for optimisation at the individual and community levels are detailed. At the individual level, tools focused on enhancing energy efficiency and self-consumption strategies are provided. On the other hand, at the community level, tools focus on optimising the collective self-consumption considering different energy resources and sharing mechanisms within the community. These tools also allow decision-makers to assess different goals, such as maximising revenue, maximising community auto-sufficiency, or promoting equitable and fair energy sharing between the members of the community.

Besides the individual and community operation tools, market mechanisms to cover competitive DR products and P2P energy trading are proposed on top of the platform being developed within the WP4. In this particular, different market designs are detailed following different contexts in terms of sharing of energy, consideration of non-financial preferences and pilot application as well.

On top of these developments, especially on tools and systems addressing the aggregation of resources and DR services, a set of principles for automated privacy-preserving are presented to enable the deployment of a secure plug-and-play edge solution.

In short, this report sets the basis of the tools to handle the different challenges in the operation, negotiation and energy share of energy communities, to be further used in the ENPOWER demonstrators.

The Digital Twin service is founded on the optimisation of EWH functioning calendar, assuming that only a very reduced dataset is available. The service can read the EWH load diagram and some static information - such as the technical specifications - and provide the optimised functioning calendar, flexibility periods, and energy/cost savings. The tool is built on a fully documented mathematical foundation and includes several features such as data converters, optimisation modules and tools for visualising results.

Before the ENPOWER started, the tool was already in development, based on other project necessities (*Enershare*). Since then, the tool's main framework was updated with several new functionalities, mainly including Data Space integration, the inclusion of a graphical user

interface, and several other features. The current version of the service is currently in the crucial transition between TRL 7 and 8. The tool now provides direct interaction with dataspace, enhancing its integration and functionality within the operational environment. Clean real data testing has also been conducted, demonstrating the tool's reliability and performance in practical scenarios. Additionally, several adjustments and internal feature enhancements have been implemented, addressing previous limitations, and optimizing overall efficiency. The introduction of a dedicated GUI for stand-alone end-user interaction significantly improves user accessibility and experience. As soon as the dataspace integration is refined, more tests with real data are conducted, and some public issues/features are added, the tool will achieve TRL 9, marking its readiness for complete deployment.

The DT (Heat Pumps) service is based on a neural network that predicts the energy consumption of heat pumps. It relies on data observed over a one-year period provided by the Irish pilot project. The neural network is of the LSTM type and incorporates several variables, including Zone 1 temperature, outside temperature and produced energy. After verifying the consistency of the data, future steps will focus on optimizing energy consumption using a mathematical formulation, while also leveraging the existing neural network. Subsequently, a web application will be developed, allowing individual users to interact by inputting their own data.

The Consumers Clustering and Segmentation service is designed to analyze and categorize households based on their energy consumption patterns and sociodemographic characteristics. This service aims to identify distinct segments of energy consumers, enabling targeted interventions and policies to promote energy efficiency. Thus, the service can be split into two categories, one about the clustering based on energy consumption time series, and one about segmenting users based on their sociodemographic, economic and behavioural characteristics retrieved from questionnaire responses.

Before the initiation of the ENPOWER project, we had developed an advanced clustering methodology specifically designed for analyzing energy consumption data. This methodology utilized 7 different clustering algorithms and their assessment to enhance the accuracy and reliability of the clustering results. The initial status focused solely on energy consumption data, aiming to identify distinct usage patterns among households.

Since January, progress has focused on:

- **Questionnaire analysis:** It has been reported in D2.2 as a separate analysis that will be integrated into the tool.
- **Ensemble Clustering approach:** Integrate the results of the top-performing algorithms to achieve the optimal clustering outcomes through the ensemble clustering methodology as described below.

Future developments of the service will include:

- **Correlation of timeseries data with Socio-Demographic Features:** Incorporating socio-demographic features to timeseries data will help improve our solution, understand the impact of various factors on energy consumption and lead to more personalized energy-saving strategies.
- **Expanded Application of Explainable AI:** Future developments of the tool will include the integration of Explainable AI (xAI) methodologies. This enhancement will improve

model transparency and provide deeper insights into consumer behaviour, aiding in the development of targeted energy management strategies.

Both approaches are ready for pilot implementation in their current form. Nevertheless, the correlation between the two is not yet viable in this project as no questionnaire answer can be mapped into energy consumption data.

The Flexibility Assessment Tool for Energy Communities (FATEC) was developed to characterize the flexibility potential of individual consumers of residential units when exposed to demand response programs. These programs are usually characterized by providing price signals to consumers, from which a change in their electricity consumption is expected due to a price change. A thorough characterization of elasticity, as provided by FATEC, enables improved behaviour modelling and further optimisation of pricing strategies. FATEC is built on a data-driven approach and supported by a causal analysis of electricity consumption behaviour. FATEC was available as a stand-alone tool. The objective is to also be able to address external requests for flexibility estimates from third parties. Analysis of relevant individual consumer data from specific members of the ENPOWER project consortium such as Coopérnico will help improve the current causal model. The next steps for FATEC are to analyse the specificities of the energy community setting and evaluate the impact and possible changes that must be made on the assumptions that are at the core of the causality model in use, and to extend the individual flexibility estimates to aggregated ones.

The Self-Consumption Optimization Tool, part of the ENPOWER project, is designed to enhance collective RES self-consumption and optimize asset operations for the participating pilots. It is a combination of the Load Shifting and Self-consumption optimization technological enablers of ENPOWER. The tool will be targeted at the Greek pilot, located on the island of Chalki. The tool empowers users to select devices and specify usage hours, offering tailored recommendations to shift or shed loads, thereby enhancing collective energy efficiency. It integrates advanced forecasting techniques, user load habits, and heuristic optimization to maximize the self-consumption of renewable energy and reduce dependency on external sources.

Before ENPOWER, the tool did not exist in its current form, though key components were already developed. Load forecasting models, for example, were developed during the BD4NRG project using data from Tilos, a similar island. Additionally, PV production forecasting is integrated with the help of GEARS' and load disaggregation algorithms are provided by COMS.

Since January, progress has focused on:

- **Data Integration:** Initial work with PV production data and load patterns from Tilos, with plans to shift to real-time data from Chalki.
- **Algorithm Development:** Creating optimization algorithms that incorporate user behaviour and forecast data to recommend efficient energy use.
- **Application Interface:** Development of a user-friendly interface that displays forecasts and optimization tips, with ongoing work to turn mockups into a functional web app.

Next, the focus will be on refining data integration, enhancing algorithms, and completing the web application. This includes updating models with Chalki's real-time data, improving PV production forecasts, and transitioning from mockups to a fully functional application.

The tool is currently under development following the detailed mockups that have been documented in D5.1. While not yet fully operational, the foundation is in place. With Chalki's infrastructure being close to completion we are ready to transition to real data scenarios.

The V2G-enabled flexibility management platform optimises EV charging by leveraging real-time electricity demand data from smart meters, weather forecasts, historical consumption patterns, and solar energy production data. The tool is designed to provide users with hourly recommendations on the best times to charge their EVs. Additionally, the platform can shift EV charging to periods when RES exceed overall demand. This allows the service to advise users on when to charge or discharge (if V2G is available), helping to maximise their benefits.

For V2G mode, a credit system is offered, allowing users to charge their vehicles at public charging stations for free or to redeem credits for discounts on their electricity bills. As part of this project, the API connection to the Greek TSO data hub was implemented, and the mobile app front end was developed.

OSTEC simulates and optimises energy utilisation in ECn, aiming to reduce energy dependency on retailers and deliver financial savings to its members. It incorporates flexible resources like batteries and was intended to integrate additional assets such as EVs and EWHs. These additions enhance system flexibility and enable the achievement of optimal energy management results.

The tool operates in two distinct modes, both designed to minimise costs:

1. IC Mode: This mode runs in two stages, ensuring that results for each member in the second stage are not worse than in the first.
2. SP Mode: In this mode, a collective optimization is performed directly, with the assumption that a fair compensation mechanism will be established later for final settlement.

Various pricing mechanisms, such as the MMR and the SDR, can be applied to the IC mode to assess financial compensations for internal transactions.

Key developments included the integration of EVs and EWHs, which contribute to the optimal performance of collective self-consumption structures. EVs, particularly through V2G systems, are expected to become crucial players in energy systems, enhancing ECn operations. EVs can work as an additional battery for members, especially when smart charging algorithms are employed. EWHs offer flexibility by determining optimal operating periods, ensuring user comfort while minimizing costs or total consumption.

Future developments will focus on new business models with shared assets, addressing storage system degradation, integrating new thermal resources, and developing an API for tool access. Flexibility bidding curves will also be integrated to profit from flexibility provisions and support grid management.

Currently, the OSTEC tool is available offline and can be tested in various pilot projects, as long as the necessary data is available. Future work and API development will enable partners to access and utilise the tool for their project pilots, enhancing its usability and impact.

WIS4Household is an AI-based tool that serves as a virtual energy advisor for the residential user. The main goal of this tool is to improve the energy efficiency of the end user and increase energy literacy by pinpointing relevant information regarding their consumption. By ingesting electricity smart meter data and other non-mandatory metadata provided by the end user, the WIS4Households platform can provide a wide range of features such as non-intrusive load

monitoring (NILM) that disaggregates the consumption of the main appliances, tailored energy efficiency measures that can go from behavioural up to appliance substitution and other information such as tariff optimisation, contracted power optimisation and solar PV optimisation.

Before ENPOWER started, the WIS4Households was in a late stage of development and now it is fully functional, especially by including “on-demand” features that can be prompted at any time by the end-user such as tariff, contracted power and solar PV optimisations.

In future steps, this tool will be deployed in the Portuguese pilots and later will be coupled with another tool, WIS4Communities, which can manage a renewable energy community. Hence, we will be able to provide a platform that manages energy communities (all energy flows and benefits for participants) and will also provide energy efficiency to the end users, thus enhancing the potential impact for efficiency.

At this moment, we need to create the data infrastructure dedicated to ENPOWER and then WIS4Households is ready to be deployed in the pilots. The WIS4Communities is still under development but by April 2025 it will be deployed in the pilots.

The Power Seller Nudging App is a solution for optimizing energy production while engaging behavioural change in the members of the energy community. It provides personalized tips and tracks user responses, it enhances user involvement and community energy efficiency. The tool acts as a key source of information, offering valuable insights into energy production and consumption.

At the initial stage, the power seller nudging application operates as a basic prototype with limited features. It is capable of displaying individual consumption and production data and forecasting individual energy usage and generation. Additionally, weather forecasts are integrated into the energy forecasts.

Within the ENPOWER project, the following developments were performed:

- New frontend designs were started;
- Methods to increase user engagement and responsiveness to nudging mechanisms are conceptualized and visualized;
- An automatic energy data transfer was conceptualized;
- (Materials and methods to support Power Sellers in their active engagement are constantly being developed and tested in a co-creation process)

The development and application of a blockchain-based hybrid coalition-based flexibility aggregation tool aims to enhance flexibility aggregation within energy communities by integrating both intra- and inter-community mechanisms providing Virtual Power Plant (VPP) functionality. Before ENPOWER, there was no such integrated solution, leading to inefficiencies and limited market participation for energy communities.

The technology enabler initially consists of two parts. The first part is a collection of blockchain tools for community flexibility aggregation and Virtual Power Plant (VPP) operations. The second part is a blockchain-based solution for traceable privacy and confidentiality protection. This solution manages rules, policies and control interfaces for automated demand response operation.

In the first stage of the ENPOWER project, an initial conceptual design for the blockchain-based flexibility marketplace was proposed. The conceptual design includes both the main actors in the

energy community and the functionality groups that cover the main groups of interactions inside the energy community related to flexibility aggregation and flexibility management.

In the following stages, the flexibility marketplace design will be further refined, implemented and integrated into the blockchain solution developed in T4.4. The next steps in the development process will include the finalisation of the marketplace design, applying P2P energy market designs and algorithms (TE-17) in the marketplace definitions, and implementing the marketplace on blockchain technology developed in T4.4. Future efforts will also refine the tool by adding advanced data analytics and predictive modelling to forecast flexibility potentials and optimize resource allocation. Expansion across various pilot sites in Europe will test scalability and adaptability in different regulatory and market contexts.

The OurPower P2P Marketplace is a service that matches electricity generated from renewable energy sources by its members with customers. The platform provides a comprehensive suite of services, including accounting, settlements, and contracting, in adherence to applicable legislation. It supports P2P electricity trading utilizing standard market procedures, allowing for economic valuation and statistical load profiling without the need for real-time smart meter data access. In fact, the OurPower marketplace allows Power Sellers to share their energy with Power Buyers. Sellers state how much electricity they offer on the marketplace and set the price for their produced energy. Buyers can choose their energy producers and receive a full electricity supply of renewable energy.

Within ENPOWER, project, the following developments were performed:

- A power plant overview including filter options was integrated into the website;
- An interactive map presenting the location of participating power plant was integrated into the website;
- The Family & Friends feature that allows Power Sellers to set custom tariffs for selected individual was developed;
- A simulation tool for energy communities was developed.

P2P energy markets designs and algorithms of subtask 5.4.1 covers competitive DR products and P2P energy trading. The market design will integrate citizens' requirements from WP2/T5.1, consumer preferences and smart contracts with P2P information forecasting and sharing, and the local DSO as a potential buyer of DR products. TE-17 market designs for Local Flexibility Markets (LFM) integration build upon the post-delivery local energy market (PD-LEM) design and pricing tools also included in OSTEC. To integrate LFMs into the PD-LEM design, adaptations of the LEM no-delivery commitment algorithm are necessary to consider the commitment to the accepted flexibility peers' bids with the non-committed PD LEM bids.

Within ENPOWER, project, the following developments were performed:

- **Conceptual design for LEM-LFM integration**
- **LFM bidding algorithm** that builds flexibility bids from aggregating the community resources and sends a bidding curve to the LFM relating quantities of available flexibility to price.
- **ECn self-consumption operation** considering CSC allocation rules, which leads to important adaptations of the optimization algorithm.

Universal Security Gateway (USG) from task T5.5 is an edge software platform for secure and privacy-preserving energy consumption management and energy community management. The USG will be extended by the services and technology enablers developed in the ENPOWER project

such as the API Gateway (defined in T4.1) and integration of tokenised marketplace from task T4.4 with community-based flexibility aggregation mechanisms from task T5.4.

USG platform at the beginning of the ENPOWER project supported smart meter data collection, load forecasting, giving recommendations to adapt consumption profiles, aggregating consumption and production and provided mechanisms for exposing flexibility to the DSO. The core system was designed around a compact data model that supported all interactions and activities expected in the small energy community.

In the first development period, USG platform was extended by packing components into individual Docker images using Docker files and orchestrating them into a deployable solution using Docker Compose files. The work done in T4.1 contributed to the overall USG architecture to protect users and their personal and non-personal data. API Gateway provides security, privacy protection and access management capabilities to the otherwise unsecured application API. This gives control to the user to set who can access his/her data and for what purposes. The permission to access data can be revoked at any time, for any user and for any reason.

In the following months, the functionality to integrate the flexible assets (battery storage, EC chargers, etc.) will be implemented. Local flexibility potential will be estimated and shared with the energy community manager that can be later converted into a flexibility offer. The API Gateway functionality will be more thoroughly integrated into the USG platform, where the energy community management interface will be extended to provide more fine-grained control over the identities inside the energy community, their assets and control over the data access. A flexibility marketplace will be developed inside tasks T4.4 and T5.4 and will be integrated into the USG platform to provide interfaces and mechanisms to share or trade the local and aggregated flexibility.

OpenDERMS, developed by the Electric Power Research Institute (EPRI) as part of the SPIDER Testbed initiative, is a sophisticated Distributed Energy Resources (DER) management system designed to aggregate, monitor, and control DER devices at both individual and group levels. Built as a web application using the Django framework, OpenDERMS facilitates real-time monitoring and control of devices through standard communication protocols like MQTT.

The system communicates with DERs using Protocol Driver Agents (PDAs), which serve as intermediaries between OpenDERMS and the devices, translating JSON-formatted control commands into device-specific protocols. This flexible communication architecture allows users to send, schedule, and manage commands for fleets of DERs while collecting status updates for post-analysis. OpenDERMS further enhances control through a Python-scripted sandbox feature, enabling customized DER management algorithms for optimal grid service delivery.

Future developments of OpenDERMS are aligned with its integration into the ENPOWER project's Irish pilot, where updated control algorithms will optimize the operation of controllable devices to enhance self-consumption within local energy communities. These advancements will be instrumental in validating key use cases for DER and demand response management in real-world scenarios.

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List of acronyms

AC	Allocation Coefficients
API	Application Programming Interface
ASC	Academic Search Complete
CF	Clustering Feature
CH	Calinski-Harabasz Score
CoreDEX	Compliant Regulatory Data Exchange
CSC	Collective Self-Consumption
DB	Davies-Bouldin Score
DC	Data Controller
DER	Distributed Energy Sources
DI	Dunn Index
DP	Data Processor
DR	Demand Response
DS	Data Subject
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DT	Digital Twin
ECn	Energy Community
ETi	Economical/Technological
EV	Electric Vehicle
EWH	Electric Water Heaters
FATEC	Flexibility Assessment Tool for Energy Communities
GMM	Gaussian Mixture Models
GLA	Greater London Authority
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IC	Individual Cost
ISP	Interval Settlement Period
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MMR	Mid-market Rate

MILP	Mixed-integer Linear Programming
ML	Machine Learning
MLR	Multiple Linear Regression
NILM	Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring
LEI	Long-Term Expected Impacts
LFM	Local Flexibility Markets
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
OpenDERMS	Open Distributed Energy Resources Management System
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
PDA	Protocol Driver Agent
PD LEM	Post-Delivery Local Energy Markets
PEP	Privacy Enforcement Point
PPE	Privacy Protection Enforcement
PRIMULA	Privacy, Reputation and Mutual Auditability
PV	Photovoltaic
REC	Renewable Energy Community
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SC	Smart Contracts
SCi	Societal
SDR	Supply and Demand Ratio
SI	Silhouette Score
SLR	Simple Linear Regression
SOC	State of Charge
SOM	Self-Organizing Maps
SP	Shadow Price
SPC	Secure and Persistent Communication
SSH	Social Science Humanities
USG	Universal Security Gateway
V2G	Vehicle-to-Grid
VPP	Virtual Power Plant
WP	Work Package
xAI	Explainable AI

1 Introduction

1.1 Objective and motivation

The continuous proliferation of energy communities is transforming how consumers perceive the energy transition and interact with the different systems, as energy communities empower consumers to be more active in energy-related issues at the local level. In this scope, digital and data-driven energy services being developed in ENPOWER under WP5 are crucial to empower community members. These solutions give community members greater control over their energy use and the ability to participate in local energy actions and markets.

The main objectives of WP5 are to: (i) enhance existing digital services; (ii) design new consumer data-driven energy services for energy secure communities and (iii) provide models and digital tools to implement these services in the demonstrators (WP6).

To this end, the WP5 is composed of 5 tasks, from the identification of services to the improvement and development of existing and new tools. These tools can provide decision support either to individual community members or community managers.

More precisely, Task 5.1 focuses on mapping, defining and co-designing data-driven services based on the literature review (including academic literature, government reports and other reports from energy community projects) and feedback from potential community members and stakeholders during workshops.

Task 5.2 provides a set of tools for the assessment of flexibility in energy communities, including the digital twin of specific flexible resources that can enhance energy community management.

Task 5.3 provides tools that allow the optimisation of self-consumption at individual and community levels, accounting for different objectives. At this stage, several services will be provided considering the different needs of the energy communities, which can include the use of digital twins developed in Task 5.2.

Task 5.4 addresses the flexibility mechanisms, aggregation and scheduling from intra- and inter-community perspectives. It covers the provision of tools that allow the trade of energy and flexibility in local and regional markets through P2P mechanisms.

Finally, to ensure the privacy-preserving of community members in trading energy and flexibility, Task 5.5 provides a set of principles to enable deploy secure plug-and-play solutions, in an automated way. Figure 1 highlights the main tasks of WP5.

Figure 1: Overview of WP5 tasks.

A set of technology enablers (Table 1) are the base of development for the deployment of innovative digital and data-driven energy services in the energy communities composing the demonstrators of ENPOWER. These technology enablers are spread throughout the WP5 tasks. The digital twins of flexible resources (TE-6) to be integrated into community operating tools, as well as tools for flexibility assessment and planning (TE-7, TE-8) are addressed in T5.2. Individual self-consumption optimisation tools for improving energy efficiency (TE10, TE-13, TE14) and community self-consumption optimisation (TE-11, TE-12, TE-14) tools are addressed in T5.3. Some of the tools, e.g., TE-12, can optimise the use of each member for the well-being of the community without diminishing the individual performance of each member of the community. For intra- and inter-community flexibility scheduling, trading and aggregation, TE-15, TE-16 and TE-17 are used within T5.4.

Table 1: List of Technical Enablers under WP5.

TE #	TE Description	Partner	Task
TE-6	Digital Twins for consumer activation	INESC TEC, DST	T5.2
TE-7	Consumers clustering and segmentation tools	NTUA, UNIBAS	T5.2
TE-8	FATEC - Flexibility Assessment tool for EnCs	INESC TEC	T5.2
TE-9	Self-consumption optimisation tool	NTUA, GEARS	T5.3
TE-10	Closed-loop optimal load control and intelligent monitoring of electric appliances for residential users	NTUA, COMS	T5.3
TE-11	V2G-based flexibility management platform for providing incentives to communities of Electric Vehicles (EVs) drivers	PARITY	T5.3

TE-12	OSTEC-Optimised Scheduling Tool for EnCs	INESC TEC	T5.3
TE-13	AI-Powered Virtual Energy Manager (WIS4Households)	WATT-IS	T5.3
TE-14	Nudging Apps for near real time closed loop consumers activation	OurPower, BLUEPRINT	T5.3
TE-15	Blockchain-based hybrid coalition-based flexibility aggregation tool	DST, COMS	T5.3
TE-16	P2P digital tools and platforms for consumer activation and social engagement	OurPower, BLUEPRINT	T5.4
TE-17	P2P energy markets designs and algorithms	INESC TEC	T5.4
TE-18	Privacy preserving tools for automated interoperable DR	EPRI, DCSix, MaREI, COMS	T5.4

1.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) description

In the context of WP5, it is crucial to monitor and evaluate performance through a set of KPIs. These KPIs serve as measurable benchmarks to provide insights regarding the effectiveness, efficiency and impact of the several tools and innovations developed under this project. This measurement can be done by looking at several areas such as user engagement, tools, development, cost reduction, operation improvement and dissemination activities. To ensure accuracy and reliability, all tools and services developed and implemented within the WP5 will be utilised as means of verification for these KPIs. Table 2 presents the list of KPIs for WP5, where Y_i used in the third column to refer to the objective value of the corresponding KPI at the end of the i^{th} year of the project and ET_i , SC_i , and LEI are Economical/Technological, Societal and Long-Term Expected Impacts, as explained in the next subsections.

Table 2: List of KPIs under the context of WP5.

N°	KPI	Target
KPI_{1-ET1}	N° of technologies adapted and expanded for delivering interactive tools	1, Y_1 , 2 Y_2 , 3 Y_3
KPI_{1-ET2}	N° of closed-loop tools' users	30 Y_1 , 100 Y_2 , 200 Y_3 , 1000 Y_{5+}
KPI_{5-SC1}	Journal publications on customers and assets flexibility modelling and assessment	0 Y_1 , 1 Y_2 , 3 Y_3
KPI_{5-SC2}	Number of new services co-designed	0 Y_1 , 10 Y_2 , 0 Y_3
KPI_{LEI1-1}	N° of services created with RES generation	0 Y_1 , 2 Y_2 , 5 Y_3 , 7-10 Y_{5+}
KPI_{LEI1-2}	% reduction in RES curtailment	0% Y_1 , 3-5% Y_2 , 10-12% Y_3 , 30-35% Y_{5+}
KPI_{LEI2-2}	% of cost reduction in data-driven services	10% Y_{3+} , 20% Y_{5+} , 40% Y_{7+}

KPI_{LEI2-3}	% of the increase in individual and community flexibility in the market enabled by data-driven services	15% Y ₃₊ , 30% Y ₅₊ , 60% Y ₇₊
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Note that all these KPIs may not be exclusively from WP5 tools and services, yet the work developed under WP5 will contribute to the achievement of the targets of these KPIs under ENPOWER project timeline.

1.2.1 KPI_{1-ET1} - Number of technologies adapted and expanded for delivering interactive tools

This KPI measures the quantity and extent of technologies that have been modified and enhanced to develop and deliver interactive tools to improve user engagement in the energy sector. This KPI measures the number of tools with a front-end facilitating better energy management and providing valuable insights through advanced interfaces and functionalities. This KPI helps assess the technical advancement and the project’s ability to create practical, user-centric solutions that address energy-related challenges.

Target:

- Year 1 – 1;
- Year 2 – 2;
- Year 3 – 3.

1.2.2 KPI_{1-ET2} - Number of closed-loop tools’ users

This KPI tracks the total number of users actively engaging with the project's closed-loop tools. This KPI includes all users interacting with the tools developed within the scope of the WP5, such as residential customers, commercial entities, and grid operators. It provides insight into the tools' operability and user base growth, reflecting their usability, effectiveness, and the value perceived by the end-users. Monitoring this KPI helps assess user penetration and satisfaction, and the overall impact of the tools on improving energy efficiency and management.

Target:

- Year 1 – 30;
- Year 2 – 100;
- Year 3 – 200;
- Year 5+ - 1000.

1.2.3 KPI_{5-SC1} - Journal publications on customers and assets flexibility modelling and assessment

This KPI tracks the number of peer-reviewed journal publications produced by the project partners within the WP5 context, focused on modelling and assessment of flexibility both in energy usage and assets. The publications should explore methodologies, frameworks, and case studies that demonstrate innovative approaches to enhancing the flexibility of energy systems.

The KPI can be quantified by the number of publications, the impact factor of the journals, and citations received, providing a measure of the project's influence and recognition in the field.

Target:

- Year 1 – 0;
- Year 2 – 1;
- Year 3 – 3.

1.2.4 KPI_{5-SC2} - Number of new services co-designed

This KPI measures the number of new services the partners have collaboratively designed. This KPI highlights the project's commitment to innovation, ensuring the resulting services are practical and relevant. The number of energy-related services available for end-users is an important indicator to address real-world problems and enhance user experience.

Target:

- Year 1 – 0;
- Year 2 – 10;
- Year 3 – 0.

1.2.5 KPI_{LEI1-1} - Number of services created with RES generation

This KPI measures the total number of new services developed that incorporate RES generation. These services are designed to leverage renewable energy, such as solar, but also some flexible resources like batteries, EVs and Electric Water Heaters (EWH). This KPI tracks initiatives where renewable energy is a core component, including energy management systems and customer-centric services promoting the use of clean energy.

Target:

- Year 1 – 0;
- Year 2 – 2;
- Year 3 – 5.
- Year 5+ - 7 to 10.

1.2.6 KPI_{LEI1-2} - % reduction in RES curtailment

This KPI measures the percentage decrease in the curtailment of RES generation over a specified period. Curtailment occurs when the available renewable energy cannot be used or stored due to grid constraints or mismatched supply and demand. This KPI tracks the endeavour to optimize the integration and usage of renewable energy through improved grid management, enhanced storage solutions and demand response. A reduction in RES curtailment indicates greater efficiency in using renewable energy, reduced wastage, and a more resilient and flexible energy system.

Mathematical Formula:

$$KPI_{LEI1-2} = \frac{E_{RES,curtailed_before} - E_{RES,curtailed_scenario}}{E_{RES,curtailed_before}}$$

where:

$E_{RES,curtailed_bef}$ - RES curtailment before the considered scenario.

$E_{RES,curtailed_scenario}$ - RES curtailment in the considered scenario.

Target:

- Year 1 – 0%;
- Year 2 – 3 to 5%;
- Year 3 – 10 to 12%.
- Year 5+ - 30 to 35%.

1.2.7 KPI_{LEI2-2} - % of cost reduction in data-driven services

This KPI measures the percentage decrease in costs achieved through the implementation of data-driven tools within the energy sector. These tools use advanced data analytics to optimize energy production, distribution, and consumption. The KPI tracks how effectively these tools reduce operational expenses and lower costs related to energy management, maintenance, and infrastructure.

Mathematical Formula:

$$KPI_{LEI2-2} = \frac{Cost_{before} - Cost_{scenario}}{Cost_{before}}$$

where:

$Cost_{before}$ - Cost before the considered scenario.

$Cost_{scenario}$ - Cost in the considered scenario.

Target:

- Year 3+ – 10%;
- Year 5+ – 20%;
- Year 7+ – 40%.

1.2.8 KPI_{LEI2-3} - % of increase in individual and community flexibility in the market enabled by data-driven services

This KPI measures the percentage increase in the flexibility of both individual consumers and communities in the energy market as a result of implementing data-driven services. Flexibility refers to the ability to adjust energy consumption patterns in response to market signals, such as price changes or demand peaks, thereby enhancing grid stability and efficiency. Data-driven services employ predictive modelling and automated controls to optimise the management and use of energy assets such as batteries, EVs and EWH. By enabling better management of these

assets, users can dynamically shift their energy usage, store excess energy, and provide demand response capabilities. This KPI tracks improvements in the responsiveness of energy consumers, highlighting how effectively these services are fostering greater participation and engagement in demand response programs, and hence in energy and flexibility markets.

Mathematical Formula:

$$KPI_{LEI2-3} = \frac{Flexibility_{before} - Flexibility_{scenario}}{Flexibility_{before}}$$

where:

- Flexibility_{before}* - Flexibility before the considered scenario.
- Flexibility_{scenario}* - Flexibility in the considered scenario.

Target:

- Year 3+ – 15%;
- Year 5+ – 30%;
- Year 7+ – 60%.

1.3 Structure of the document

This document is organised to comprehensively summarise the work conducted in WP5 from M5 up to M13 related to the design and development of data-driven services for energy communities, accounting for the different levels and interactions between all participants in the energy communities.

The report first presents (Chapter 2) an overview of the literature focused on data-driven services for energy communities, accounting for the social engagement and interaction of users. A valuable set of works, reports and workshops are explored to set up the basis for the design of energy and non-energy services suitable for energy communities.

Chapter 3 describes the flexibility assessment tools that can be used to assess, model and quantify the flexibility of an energy community, considering different energy resources. Two Digital Twins (DTs) (Electrical Water Heater and Heat Pump) are developed in a modular way, which allows the integration of these DTs into the planning and operating tools of energy communities.

Chapter 4 describes the self-consumption optimisation tools for two different levels of the communities. It provides tools for optimising each member of the community individually and tools for optimizing the self-consumption of the energy community as a whole. Part of the described tools includes both levels with mechanisms to ensure that the optimisation at the community level always creates additional value for all the members.

Chapter 5 addresses the participation of energy communities in energy and flexibility markets, based on competitive Demand Response (DR) products and Peer-to-Peer (P2P) energy trading mechanisms. Different market designs are addressed, accounting for different financial and non-

financial preferences. The aggregation at intra- and inter-community levels are addressed, including mechanisms for trading flexibility in different markets.

Chapter 6 presents two platforms that will be used to prepare the integration of the tools developed in T5.2 to T5.4. The Universal Security Gateway (USG) and the Open Distributed Energy Resources Management System (OpenDERMS) are described and initial steps for its combination and extension are proposed. For instance, the community-based flexibility aggregation mechanism developed in T5.4 will extend these platforms.

2 Data-driven consumer-centric services for energy communities

2.1 Literature review

In this chapter, we outline a scoping literature review that aims to outline, define, and identify practices associated with data-driven services for energy-secure communities. This represents the first segment of a trilogy of related research outputs dedicated to capturing and advocating for best practices and research recommendations concerning energy community data sharing. We base this initial work on three over-arching objectives, namely to:

- To explore and document the concept of energy data sharing with communities from a multi-disciplinary perspective;
- To offer learnings based on three thematic areas: the energy grid, buildings, and technologies;
- To identify key opportunities associated with data-sharing for promoting energy transitions and behaviour change at a community level.

Overall, the study design entails a multifaceted approach, incorporating qualitative data acquisition through a literature review, a series of Thought Leader and Civil Society workshops, and a Delphi Panel survey to delve into both existing and emerging insights regarding data sharing. Our primary aim is for this initial review to serve as a springboard for well-organized and well-informed discussions with community members, aligning with the specific objectives of WP5. These objectives centre around co-designing data-driven services for energy-secure communities and exploring non-economic incentives for data sharing. Furthermore, we present initial recommendations that stemmed from our inaugural WP5 Thought Leader Workshop, themed 'Energy communities and data sharing' and jointly organised on 5 June 2024 by ENPOWER partners ENASCO and MaREI/UCC in collaboration with Károli Gáspár University in Hungary.

The insights derived from our multifaceted methodology in this chapter and subsequent chapters will significantly contribute to WP5's principal objective—enhancing existing digital services and designing new consumer data-driven energy services for energy-secure communities. The process will offer access to emerging models and digital tools for implementing data-sharing services within the ENPOWER real-life Front-Runner and Early Adopter pilot communities across Europe (namely in Ireland, Portugal, Spain, Greece, Hungary and Austria). Given the large-scale geographical span of the pilot sites, the mixed method approach will also develop learnings to support the replicability of solutions across the various socio-economic and cultural contexts.

2.1.1 Context

The widespread deployment of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and the rise of calls to activate energy-empowered citizens and data-driven energy-secure communities pose significant challenges to the operation of the energy system and electricity market. Pathways to enable the electricity market to shift from a centralised, supplier-centric structure to a more decentralised,

consumer-centric model are central to this shift. However, ENPOWER has identified challenges and barriers preventing the full deployment of a consumer-centric European energy system along three dimensions that require further research and action. They include:

- A 'social dimension' to meet the challenge of developing culturally appropriate, meaningful and accurate information across the supply chain that addresses energy literacy issues and provides effective tools and methodologies to help improve energy efficiencies, to co-develop innovative incentives (incorporating both financial and non-financial dimensions), to counter energy poverty, and to contribute to a more sustainable and greener quality of life;
- A 'technological dimension' to address the current lack of digital tools and frameworks for creating, planning, and expanding energy communities across different industries. To develop innovative tools to assess the readiness of local communities and to promote interoperable tools for data sharing across energy sectors. Furthermore, to meet the socio-technical challenge of enabling better real-time interaction between consumers and utilities;
- A 'organisational/business dimension' to meet the challenge of a lack of sharing economy and social innovation-based business models. To explore shared ownership models for community-based renewable energy assets that capture and share benefits with community members and balance private stakeholders' interests with social benefits. To co-develop new market roles prioritising consumers.

To meet these challenges, ENPOWER's multi-stakeholder and multi-disciplinary consortium shares the core ambition to devise, develop, and showcase Social Science Humanities (SSH)-driven methodologies, interactive, closed-loop tools, and services for energy-empowered citizens and data-informed, energy-secure communities to move towards a consumer-centric energy system. The identification of practice in our literature review, therefore, pays close attention to the socio-technical dimensions around data-sharing innovations, highlighting and documenting opportunities to deepen SSH-led innovation in this space.

2.1.2 Methodology

Mixed-method design

We develop a mixed-method research design seeking to offer a multi-level perspective of data sharing that draws from a programme of research based on desk research, workshop insights and a Delphi Panel Expert Survey. For this initial deliverable, our communication focuses on preliminary insights that will expand through the course of the research programme. This report, therefore, considers a selection of academic papers and reports captured and synthesised through a scoping literature review process where a selection of preliminary themes is showcased. Furthermore, we will provide a summary of our first thought leader workshop, which was held with energy experts in Hungary.

Scoping Literature Review

Literature reviews play a crucial role in academia in advancing knowledge. They are utilised to assess rapidly evolving research areas, identify the adoption of new practices, gather evidence for specific research questions, and offer fresh perspectives on existing knowledge [1]. While literature reviews are often considered foundational and preparatory work for deeper empirical research, we argue that they should also be seen as a research method leading to new knowledge and insights [2]. Our ambition to enhance SSH-led innovation in this space is groundbreaking in this research space and, as such, is an opportunity for a new critical reading of existing literature. We followed several steps to conduct the scoping review, including a literature search, screening and analysis based on the method outlined by [3]. This process involved creating search terms and specific criteria for including or excluding materials during the screening process. We used Scopus, Academic Search Complete (ASC/EBSCO host), and Google Scholar databases to search for available literature. We included literature published between 2022 and 2024 and limited the search to articles written in English. Search terms used included 'Energy Data Sharing' and 'Energy Communities'. This process led to the retrieval of 226 articles, and subsequent thematic analysis of titles and abstracts was conducted to identify SSH-led or SSH-informed research publications.

Thought Leader Workshops

Workshops are increasingly leveraged in research environments to engage groups in problem-solving, innovative thinking and the acquisition of new knowledge [4]. A wide range of format for conducting workshops has emerged ranging from highly creative group exchanges to more formal interactions focused on specific tasks and objectives. The Thought Leader workshop format we use in ENPOWER is conceived as a multi-disciplinary brainstorming space whereby experts from different fields join to share their research findings and discuss synergies with other thought-leaders through a series of roundtable presentations and discussions. Our inaugural WP5 Thought Leader Workshop was carried under the theme 'Energy communities and data sharing'. It was jointly organised and hosted on 5 June 2024 by ENPOWER team partners, namely ENASCO and MaREI/UCC in collaboration with Károli Gáspár University in Hungary. Various disciplinary views were offered including market-based insights, legal and legislative perspectives, technological know-how and learnings from grassroots deliberations.

2.2 Exploring the concept of data sharing from a multi-disciplinary perspective

Energy data sharing is a dynamic and evolving concept which is increasingly applied to accelerate the provision of sustainable energy systems tied to ideas such as 'energy decentralisation, 'renewable energy communities' 'smart-systems' and 'distributed energy resources' [5]. It does so by refining technological solutions, understanding consumer data sharing preferences and strengthening privacy and security protections. Big data is often hailed as a driver in the delivery of sustainability in the energy system and new approaches are emerging that seek to leverage the use of diverse data types and data assets across the energy domain in a more open manner [6]. Across Europe, we have also seen substantial growth in government-led policies seeking to promote and support the establishment of energy communities and encourage a grassroots investment base for renewable energy. The operation of such shared assets at a micro-scale requires adequate planning and management strategies which rely heavily on effective processes of data circulation based on open, transparent and meaningful sharing arrangements across

sectors [7]; standards such as the FAIR Guiding Principles for Data Management and Stewardship provide an initial framework for ensuring access to good quality data¹; it draws on guidelines for development, circulation and life-cycle management of scientific data.

The literature shows that stakeholders and researchers apply the concept of data sharing based on different perspectives.

These range from adopting specific legal and regulatory frameworks [8], [9], [10], [11], applying ideas in the context of governance and the promotion of innovative local collaborative frameworks [12], [13], [14], developing new data sharing business models [15], [16], [17], [18], and leveraging data sharing interactions to change energy behaviours [19], [20].

As such, these dimensions often present specific understandings and outlooks over who controls or owns data, how data should be shared and circulated, and why sharing energy data is increasingly relevant.

2.2.1 Interdisciplinary insights and hybridization strategies

Interdisciplinary insights drawing from SSH learning could provide a bridge to connect and align recommendations stemming from these various sources of disciplinary know-how. For instance, innovations in this space include the advancement of niche hybridization strategies as proposed by [21] which combine elements of cooperative and commercial systems and socio-technical insights to establish a new niche model that is adaptable and responds to multiple social, technological and institutional needs and requirements. Looking at the case of *Community Power* in Ireland, a community owned supply company that operates under this hybrid logic, the study shows how this approach allowed an energy community to compete with the incumbent energy system and adapt to an unfavourable institutional context (ibid). Another innovative hybrid framework for energy communities as ‘socio-legal institutions’ is proposed by [22] framed around the acknowledged need to provide regulatory and social flexibility given the diversity of contexts encountered across different European countries. This trend toward hybrid forms of energy community models was also previously identified in the Dutch context [23]. Framed as a ‘happy middle-ground’, [23] see the trend towards hybrid cooperative models as a pragmatic mix of local participation, community engagement and business logic which they argue could provide continuity and longevity to many emerging energy community alliances.

2.2.2 Social innovation is a new concept to support energy system change

Social innovation in the context of energy communities is a relatively new concept which can broadly be understood as the development of new collaboration, relationships and ideas that enhance social dividends and societal capacity to act [24]. There are various types of social

¹ The concept of FAIR was introduced in 2014 during the Lorentz workshop. Subsequently, the FAIR principles were published in *Scientific Data* in 2016. The enhancement of data Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR) provides the framework for facilitating scientific data reuse. See website for more details <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

innovations which include new organisational forms, financing aspects, new value creation and incentives, new policies and regulations (ibid). Looking at the general societal benefits of emerging innovations, [25] offer insights from a systematic literature review seeking to map the social impacts of energy communities in Europe. The study identified four recurring impact categories. Namely: energy justice; energy democracy, community empowerment and social capital. Equality of access, knowledge development, social cohesion and networking are some closely tied to energy data-sharing practices. [26] explore social innovation processes in Sweden and Denmark and they identify novel methods of information sharing and dissemination such as study-circles, town hall meetings and trialability as relevant innovative precursors to the phase-out of old technologies and the establishment of new systems. From a business model perspective, [16] relates numerous co-creation value opportunities, which include the development of new connection points between consumers and energy cooperatives, the development of legal and technical cooperative supports, and developments in energy literacy and research. Numerous co-creation value opportunities include the development of new connection points between consumers and energy cooperatives, the development of legal and technical cooperative supports, and developments in energy literacy and research.

2.2.3 Sites and technologies of data sharing

Energy data sharing and the digitalisation of the energy system can be found in sites such as the 'energy grid' undergoing a process of decentralised energy generation involving a heterogeneous range of stakeholders, such as municipalities, prosumers, and aggregators. On a smaller scale, sites such as 'buildings' are also the focus of change, with smart building controls, storage systems, and sharing alternatives that enable 'smart' living solutions for city dwellers [27]. Applications and convergence of new technologies for data sharing, such as blockchain and artificial intelligence, have received growing attention. As a nascent area of research, it will continue to raise important questions over delivering valuable services that complement rather than compromise place-based practices and economies.

2.3 Summary of first Thought-Leader Workshop

The "Energy Communities and Data Sharing" workshop (Thought Leaders Workshop), held on June 5, 2024, in Budapest, brought together a diverse group of participants both in-person and online. The workshop focused on the critical aspects of data sharing within energy communities, addressing various challenges and opportunities.

A highlight of the workshop was an interactive Q&A session, where participants had the chance to ask questions and share their perspectives. This was followed by an informal brainstorming session to further discuss issues raised during the presentations. During this segment, several key challenges were identified:

- **Regulatory Barriers:** Constant changes in distribution regulations make it difficult to establish partnership models that comply with legal requirements.
- **Technical and Operational Hurdles:** Different entities within the community often operate on separate transformer circuits, complicating data integration.

- **Motivation and Engagement:** Engaging the public and businesses is challenging due to a lack of immediate financial incentives and the complexity of initiatives.
- **Financial and Technical Constraints:** Significant upfront investments in technology and infrastructure are required for these projects.
- **Operational Models:** Choosing the right structure - be it cooperatives, non-profit LLCs, or shared ownership structures - is crucial, with each model having its own benefits and drawbacks.
- **Role of Municipalities and Industrial Actors:** A top-down approach can sometimes overshadow the role of individual participants.

The collaborative segment of the "Energy Communities and Data Sharing" workshop proved essential for generating practical ideas and fostering a collective understanding of the barriers and motivations related to data sharing within energy communities. Participants highlighted the need for enhanced data-sharing practices, supported by a favourable regulatory environment and engaged stakeholders, as crucial for the success and sustainability of energy communities.

Overall, the workshop addressed a broad spectrum of topics concerning data sharing among energy communities, including technical, legal, economic, and practical aspects. This comprehensive approach facilitated a dynamic exchange of information and ideas. By bringing together a diverse group of participants, the event laid the groundwork for future partnerships and advancements in this vital area. It also emphasized the significant role of data in ensuring the success and long-term viability of energy communities.

3 Cross-commodity digital twin for flexibility assessment and planning

3.1 Overview

The proper assessment of flexibility in energy communities is key to having a system that adapts to variations in energy supply and demand, smoothly. To this end, the flexibility of each available resource must be modelled to be integrated into the operation and management tools of energy communities. On one hand, controllable resources should be modelled, so that they can be integrated directly into the management tools to profit from their flexibility. On the other hand, many members (consumers) of the energy communities may have different degrees of responsiveness to external signals requesting flexibility, so the assessment of the response of such consumers to such signals (such as price signals or other incentives) is essential for the community manager to understand what the potential flexibility is available from ordinary members and how they can contribute to the flexibility of community. In this scope, T5.2 aims to:

- Design a set of digital twins (TE-6), namely thermal models (e.g., heat pump and electric water heater), based on data-driven models to leverage real-world assets in the management of buildings and consequently energy communities. The digital twins will provide information for enhanced flexibility management and aggregation at the energy community level. That is, the modelling of flexibility for these assets will be then integrated into the operation and management tools of energy communities within T5.3;
- Provide clustering algorithms (TE-7) of residential consumers/prosumers to categorize residential users based on their energy consumption patterns and sociodemographic characteristics. The categorisation and classification of the users by the clustering algorithm include combining energy and non-energy data, such as energy consumption, gender, socioeconomic factors, etc.
- Provide a flexibility assessment tool (TE-8) for energy communities that allows ranking consumers and their individual and collective responsiveness or elasticity to dynamic economic and non-economic incentives. The Flexibility Assessment Tool for Energy Communities (FATEC) tool allows the community manager to characterize the flexibility potential of individual consumers (members of the community) to demand response programs to evaluate the type of consumers that will be more susceptible to responding to DR signals. FATEC will then be extended to assess the collective flexibility potential of the energy community considering all the individual behaviours.

As depicted in Figure 2, all these tools will be a great support for community managers to manage all the flexibility potential of the community members and to understand their intrinsic behaviour and assess their potential and available flexibility to enhance the planning, operation and management of the energy community.

Figure 2: Cross-commodity flexibility overview.

3.2 Digital twins for consumer activations

3.2.1 Electric water heater

3.2.1.1 Flexibility modelling of thermoelectric water heaters – general characterization

This service is founded on the optimisation of EWH functioning calendar, assuming that only a very reduced dataset is available. The service can read the EWH load diagram and some static information - such as the technical specifications - and provide the optimised functioning calendar, flexibility periods, and energy/cost savings. The tool is built on a fully documented mathematical foundation and includes several features such as data converters, optimisation modules and tools for visualising results. All documentation, description, technical reviews, mathematical foundations, and others are directly sourced from this tool's original development project (i.e., *Enershare* [28]).

The service is built over a Python framework library, including a coded pipeline of functions, counting with several stages, namely:

1. **Data acquisition:** reads input data in several formats' possibilities, namely:
 - a. Sources data directly from the data provider via Data Space comprising only timestamps and electrical consumption data with minute resolution.
 - b. EWH load diagram time-series dataset in JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format comprising only timestamps and electrical consumption data (in watts) with minute resolution.
 - c. EWH daily usage example with periods and durations of hot-water usage.
2. **Data conversion:** converts provided input in the missing counterpart, namely:
 - a. If provided with the EWH load diagram (1.a), runs the load-to-usage converter.
 - b. If provided with EWH daily usage example (1.b), runs the usage-to-load converter.
3. **Missing data:** fills missing data with default values or energy distribution.
4. **Data resampling:** resamples data to 15-min or 1-hour resolution (optional).
5. **Linearisation:** extracts the Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) parameters for linearisation of non-linear constraints.
6. **Optimisation:** creates and runs the optimisation module.

7. **Results:** plot and save results

A simplified version of the overall service architecture and processing steps is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: EWH service architecture.

3.2.1.1.1 Current status (until M13)

The service is close to the final release version and is currently in the crucial transition between TRL 7 and 8. The tool now in its beta version, has an interactive Graphical User Interface (GUI) for end-user interaction and incorporates the possibility of directly interacting with a dataspace, enhancing its integration and functionality within the operational environment. Clean real data testing has also been conducted, demonstrating the tool's reliability and performance in practical scenarios. Additionally, several adjustments and internal feature enhancements have been implemented, addressing previous limitations, and optimising overall efficiency. The introduction of a dedicated GUI for stand-alone end-user interaction significantly improves user accessibility and experience. As soon as the service is completely validated in an operational environment, the tool will achieve TRL 9, marking its readiness for complete deployment.

3.2.1.1.1.1 Mathematical foundation

The service includes an optimisation model that is built on a fully documented mathematical foundation. The modelling approach is anchored in fundamental principles, ensuring transparency and clarity in the application of mathematical concepts for robust optimisation. The service's documentation includes a detailed exposition of the tool's methodology and underlying mathematical principles, but the main concepts of the optimisation's mathematical fundamentals are:

- **Temperature Assurance:** guarantee that the water temperature within the EWH never falls below the user-defined comfort threshold during and after hot water usage intervals.
- **Energy Estimates:** calculate the minimum accumulated energy required for comfort and the total equivalent energy accumulated in the EWH after each hot water usage, considering fluid mixing dynamics.
- **Comfort Guarantee:** ensure that the final energy accumulated after use is equal to or greater than the minimum equivalent comfort energy value.
- **Penalty Mechanism:** incorporate a penalty variable to handle challenges in guaranteeing constant hot water availability and penalizing excessive temperature reductions.
- **Energy Considerations:** account for energy losses by usage, gains by heating, and losses by convection through the EWH's surface area.
- **Cost Minimization:** minimises the total operating cost by optimizing the proportion of EWH heating usage and the respective pricing.

For a more detailed description of the mathematical foundation, including the optimisation structuring including restrictions, objective function, linearization procedures, etc., see the service [documentation available directly in the service's GitHub repository](#).

3.2.1.1.1.2 Features overview

Apart from the base optimisation foundation, the service includes a set of essential features that were implemented on top of the original and basilar alpha version.

3.2.1.1.2.1 Built-in load to Boolean usage converter

The main objective of this service is to extract periods of flexibility and simulate energy savings associated with a given EWH load diagram. In this sense, this service must be able to provide this information using only as inputs the device's charging diagram, some technical information about the device in question, and the user-defined comfort temperature for using hot water. During the process of creating the tool, it was assumed that a Boolean hot water usage calendar might be available. However, to make the tool more robust, a converter is now included so that the service can receive the raw diagrams coming from a given load measurement sensor/tool.

The converter (illustrated in Figure 4) that was developed requires as inputs the load diagram in question, and three additional parameters: EWH operating power; the maximum permissible temperature of stored water (defaulted at 80°C); user-defined comfort temperature when using hot water (defaulted at 40°C). With this set of information, the converter can detect the periods in which the EWH came into operation, and estimate periods of hot water usage, associated with this *ON/OFF* activation of the EWH. For this purpose, it is assumed that the EWH comes into operation whenever the temperature of the stored water drops below a certain threshold. When the activation period is long enough, it is assumed that hot water has been used, the duration of which is estimated based on the activation duration. In this way, together with a simplified version of the formula for mixing hot water from the EWH with cold water from the network it is estimated which energy equivalent is possibly used, together with the reheating time (to restore the energy losses), total the total activation period.

$$\text{Heating Period}_{Total} = \text{Heating Period}_{Usage=1} + \text{Heating Period}_{Usage=0}$$

$$\text{Heating Period}_{Usage=1} = \frac{\text{Heating Period}_{Total}}{\left(1 + \frac{EWH^{maxTemp} \cdot Flow^{EWH} \cdot c}{3600 \cdot W^{in}}\right)}$$

where,

c – water specific heat capacity ($4.184 \text{ J} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)

$$Flow^{EWH} = \frac{Flow^{total} \cdot (Temp.^{Comf.} - Temp.^{Inlet})}{EWH^{maxTemp} - Temp.^{Inlet}}$$

It is important to note that, as mentioned, even if hot water is not used, it is normal for the EWH to come into operation when the temperature, through convection losses, drops beyond the established limit. To try to overcome the signalling of these false positives, the converter determines the average duration between automatic connection intervals, and it is only marked as a period in use, if the usage interval is less than 90% of the average *OFF* periods, or if the estimated period of usage is greater than 2 minutes.

$$\overline{OffPeriod} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n OffPeriod_i}{n}$$

$$\begin{cases} \text{If } OffPeriod_i < 0.9 \cdot \overline{OffPeriod} \text{ , } OnPeriod_j^{Usage} = 1 \\ \text{If } OnPeriod_j^{Length} > 2min. \text{ , } OnPeriod_j^{Usage} = 1 \\ \text{Else , } OnPeriod_j^{Usage} = 0 \end{cases}$$

Finally, the converter exports a Boolean map of hot water usage, which is the main requirement of the previously developed tool.

Figure 4: EWH load to usage converter visualisation example.

Even though, with the provision of a Boolean usage diagram from the user, where the certainty of the Boolean usage was higher, with the inclusion of this tool, any type of additional user-sided work becomes unnecessary, making it possible to use only the parameters and the diagrams from the measurement system.

3.2.1.1.1.2.2 Data resampling

The service has been significantly upgraded to include a flexible resampling feature. Originally, the module handled only load diagram data with up-to-the-minute resolution, which provided detailed insights and is still mandatory for running the service. However, for the optimisation module stage, namely with other services integration, this higher resolution could implicate higher computational effort or could be compromising for broader analysis, longer periods, and larger-scale integrated solutions. With the new resampling feature, the service can now convert the input data to a 15-minute or 1-hour resolution. This enhancement offers several advantages, such as:

- **Data management:** Simplifies the handling of large datasets, making it easier to store and process information in-between entities and connectors;
- **Performance efficiency:** significantly reduces computational effort, which is particularly valuable for large-scale simulations (e.g., larger time horizons);
- **Compatibility:** enhances compatibility with various analytical tools and facilitates integration with third-party services that could require coarser data resolutions.

To apply this change, it was also necessary to update certain portions of the service, namely the integration of input data with the optimisation module. Here, new updates to the variables were introduced, such as the formulation for calculating the resolution of the provided dataset, and the Δt variable. Furthermore, the problem constraints have also been updated, so that there is a dynamic integration with different data resolutions.

Regarding the resampling methodology itself, the process is done automatically, using the *resample()* function from the *pandas* library. Since it is always a matter of decreasing resolution, in the case of the load variable, the aggregation is done via the sum of fifteen or sixty observations, for a new resolution of 15 minutes, or 1 hour, respectively. In the case of the $\hat{\delta}_t^{use}$ variable, the aggregation is done based on the time-to-time ratio. Once again, the resolution of 1 minute is assumed as the base, to calculate the value for aggregation of 15 minutes or 1 hour, a quotient is made between the sum of the various portions of the original base (1 minute), and 15 or 60, respectively.

Assuming \hat{t} as the new time interval, 15 minutes or 1 hour:

$$OriginalLoad_{\hat{t}}^{15min} = \sum_t^{t+14} OriginalLoad_t^{1min}$$

$$OriginalLoad_{\hat{t}}^{1h} = \sum_t^{t+59} OriginalLoad_t^{1min}$$

$$\delta_{\hat{t}}^{use | 15min} = \frac{\sum_t^{t+14} \delta_t^{use | 1min}}{15}$$

$$\delta_{\hat{t}}^{use | 1h} = \frac{\sum_t^{t+59} \delta_t^{use | 1min}}{60}$$

In short, this functionality not only broadens the scope of potential applications, namely due to the interest in integrating this service with other energy-based solutions (e.g. energy communities), but from a standalone viewpoint, also extends the possibility of reducing computational effort in longer time horizon simulations.

3.2.1.1.1.2.3 Linearization revamp

The linearization process has been updated from Simple Linear Regression (SLR) to MLR. Originally, linearization had temperature as the only variable, but this updated version also considers the $\hat{\delta}_t^{use}$ variable. This change only has an impact if the $\hat{\delta}_t^{use}$ values are less than 1, as is most likely the case in cases where resampling is done. For example, for a subsequent 5-minute hot water usage, the $\hat{\delta}_t^{use}$ value for a 15-minute resampling will be equal to $\frac{5}{15}$. In this sense, the linearization process must also be adapted to these new values, to consider different $\hat{\delta}_t^{use}$ values that may occur. In this context, for a new resolution of 15 minutes, there are 15 possible usage values (i.e., $\frac{1}{15}, \dots, \frac{15}{15}$). For the case of hourly resolution, there are 60 possibilities (i.e., $\frac{1}{60}, \dots, \frac{60}{60}$). This change makes it possible to integrate this new functionality and respond with greater precision to different hot water usage scenarios.

The new formulation, with greater detail, can be seen in the project documentation. Even so, the simplified formulation of the linearization process, right after extracting the linear coefficients, is presented below:

If $\hat{\delta}_t^{use} > 0$:

If $temp_t^{EWH} < \widehat{temp}^{set}$:

$$W_t^{mix} = m_{\delta_t^{use}}^{belowSet} \cdot \hat{\delta}_t^{use} + m_{temp_t^{EWH}}^{belowSet} \cdot temp_t^{EWH} + b^{belowSet}$$

If $temp_t^{EWH} \geq \widehat{temp}^{set}$:

$$W_t^{mix} = m_{\delta_{use}}^{aboveSet} \cdot \hat{\delta}_t^{use} + m_{temp^{EWH}}^{aboveSet} \cdot temp_t^{EWH} + b^{aboveSet}$$

3.2.1.1.1.2.4 Hot water usage input alternative

One of the useful features that have been added to the service is to promote the use of the service by consumers who do not have an EWH consumption measurement diagram available. In this context, the possibility for the end-user to provide an exemplary 24-hour synthetic schedule of the periods and duration of hot water use applies. In this way, the service becomes useful for consumers who want to have a high-level idea of the savings they can obtain after 24 hours. It is important to note that, even with the results being reliable, as we are trying to simulate the period of the first 24 hours, the first uses are somehow biased and subject to the initial temperature of the EWH's internal water and could not represent a long-term estimate.

Here, the coded input that should reach the service must include two variables per instance of water usage:

- *start*: a timestamp that represents the beginning of the estimated hot water usage;
- *duration*: an integer that represents the estimated duration of the hot water usage.

In this way, for a synthetic scenario with four estimated hot water usages, the actual coded input would look like the following example:

```
[
{"start": "07/12/2022 08:00", "duration": 10},
{"start": "07/12/2022 08:15", "duration": 10},
{"start": "07/12/2022 12:00", "duration": 5},
{"start": "07/12/2022 20:00", "duration": 5}
]
```

With this input, the service refers to both start and duration parameters and builds a one-minute resolution Boolean usage diagram, like the one that is returned from the load-to-usage converter.

Once again, the service requires both load and usage diagrams to run successfully. The former is necessary to serve as a reference for calculating the original energy and cost values, and the latter is necessary since it serves as input for the optimisation module. In this way, since – in the scenario – the user only provides the usage diagram, it is necessary to develop a converter that can extract an estimated load diagram, based on this presented usage schedule.

3.2.1.1.1.2.5 Built-in usage to load converter

As mentioned before, in case the consumer is unable to provide an actual EWH load diagram, this service now provides the possibility of receiving a simple estimate of the various user's hot water usage for 24 hours. Still, for this information to be useful, it is necessary to extract a diagram of EWH consumption from this input.

For this purpose, a converter is developed that can extract the EWH consumption diagram. For this to be possible, in addition to the various specifications of the EWH (e.g., power, capacity, etc.), it is also necessary to know the value of the normal operating temperature of the EWH. Typically, to a classic EWH is assigned a temperature value at which it must operate. As soon as, through losses due to convection or the usage of hot water, there is a reduction in the internal

temperature that exceeds the one, added range, lower than the previously defined value, the EWH goes into heating mode. For example, if the stipulated value is 60°C, and assuming an interval of 3°C if, for example, after 4 hours, the temperature is lower than 57°C, the EWH will enter water heating mode. In this sense, there is a new parameter that must be provided - *ewh_std_temp* - which refers to the normal operating temperature of the EWH (defaulted as 60°C). Furthermore, in addition to the need to contend with temperature losses by convection, the converter must also consider programmed water uses (supplied by the user).

To calculate the necessary energy to compensate for this loss of temperature, and to once again reach an internal temperature of 60°C, the mathematical formulation of fluid mixing is used (check the mathematical foundation documentation). With this information, and through this mechanism, it is possible to estimate the amount of time necessary for the EWH to be on, to make the temperature rise again to the established value. Finally, by carrying out this operation for the entire period, an estimated original load diagram is obtained.

For the same example as the one provided in the section 3.2.1.1.1.2.4, the extracted load diagram should look like the one presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: EWH usage to load converter output example.

As can be seen in Figure 5, in addition to the need for heating after hot water usage, there are periods where convection losses were high enough to trigger the device's operation.

3.2.1.1.1.2.6 Reconstructing “Delta-In” parameter

After introducing the possibility of resampling optimisation data (see section 3.2.1.1.1.2.2), it was necessary to readjust the parameter that indicates whether the EWH is working.

Indeed, in the previous version, this decision variable was Boolean (assuming 0 or 1 values) and indicated that, in the period under analysis (in the previous case, always of 1 minute), the EWH was ON or OFF during the entire interval (with $\delta_t^{in} = 1$ or $\delta_t^{in} = 0$, respectively).

With data resampling, assigning a value of $\delta_t^{in} = 1$ would imply that the EWH would be ON for at least the entire 15 min or 1-hour interval (depending on the resampling choice). These circumstances are not entirely viable, as it may not be necessary to exhaust the entire period for shorter water usage. For example, even if only 7 minutes of heating were required, with the δ_t^{in} variable being Boolean, a minimum of 15 minutes (or 1h) of heating would always be enforced.

Given this, a change was applied to the δ_t^{in} formulation, now allowing it to take any values between 0 and 1, thus enabling heating for shorter periods than that limited by the new data resolution. This change not only allows a more realistic and seamless integration of the resampled data but also makes it possible to obtain improved results in the original scenario (with 1-minute resolution), as it allows the device to be connected for shorter periods than 1 minute. It is important to understand that these differences, in the original scenario, may not represent significant differences, since a 1-minute resolution is already very high.

3.2.1.1.2.7 Dataset resolution and error verification

In addition to the service's need to receive data with 1-min resolution, without missing data, and after analysing the quality of the raw data that comes from EWH meters, we detected the need to make some fixes to the data. In this sense, a layer of analysis and processing of input data is added. Here, several tasks are performed:

- The received load diagram is merged into an empty template with all datetime observations, with resolution to the minute, for the entire period under analysis.
- Missing data is corrected with zero measurement.
- Since some data sources provide diagrams with values in energy (kWh), and since the service requires data in instantaneous power, there is a need to convert kWh to W. For this purpose, if the data arrives in energy (kWh), undergo the following modification:

$$EWH Load_W = EWH Load_{kWh} \cdot 60 \cdot 1000$$

- Since energy meters, in cases of measurement failures, add the total energy to the next successful measurement, there is a need to correct/divide this measurement with the previous instances. In view of this, the diagram goes through a mechanized correction process that detects which periods are in failure and establishes the division of the aggregated energy by the previously detected missing periods.

3.2.1.1.2.8 Graphical User Interface

To assist the interaction of any end-user with this service, even for standalone handling (if it is not associated with a dataspace source), a GUI was developed that allows direct user interaction with the service. After installing the library, the user can then choose to run the service via IDE/terminal or through a fully functional GUI. In this last option, the end-user can fill in all the EWH parameters, and choose one of three data input methods: data space, uploading a file with the EWH load diagram, or filling in a set of estimated uses of hot water. After running the service, the user will be presented with some essential results, and plots of the water temperature and the optimized and original consumption of the device.

This dashboard allows end-users to configure and optimize their EWH, for energy and cost savings, while ensuring comfort. The GUI streamlines the process by allowing users to input the EWH technical specifications, select data access methods, and visualize results through plots. The final version, linked to the dataspace allows accessing stored historical data via the dataspace connector, uploading load diagrams, or just filling in the estimated hot water usage calendar (24-hours). It was developed using *Streamlit*, and the implementation ensures a seamless and

intuitive user experience, enabling input configuration - EWH specifications in fields or dropdown menus -, and result visualization and download. The dashboard starts with a brief description of the service and a short summary of the tool's applications (Figure 6).

Figure 6: EWH GUI introductory section.

The end-users can begin by specifying several parameters of their EWH, including:

- EWH Capacity (l), defaulted as 100l;
- EWH Power (W), defaulted as 1800W;
- EWH Maximum Allowed Temperature (°C), defaulted as 80°C;
- EWH standard non-optimized functioning water temperature (°C), defaulted as 60°C;
- Hot-Water Usage Comfort Temperature (°C), defaulted as 40°C;
- Selection between Simple or Dual Daily Tariff, defaulted as Simple;
- Pricing per kWh (€), defaulted as 0.12€, Simple Tariff only;
- Price per kWh during the day period (€), defaulted as 0.15, Dual Tariff only;
- Price per kWh during the night period (€), defaulted as 0.08, Dual Tariff only;
- Daily Tariff (€), defaulted as 0.36€.

EWH Specifications

EWH Capacity (liters)

100 - +

EWH Power

Auto-Detect

Specify the EWH Power (watt)

EWH maximum allowed temperature (°C)

80 - +

EWH standard non-optimized functioning water temperature (°C)

60 - +

Hot-Water Usage Comfort Temperature (°C)

40 - +

Simple or Dual Daily Tariff

Simple v

Price per kWh (€)

0.12 - +

Daily Tariff (€)

0.36 - +

Figure 7: EWH GUI input section.

Once these parameters are provided (see Figure 7), the GUI offers multiple ways to input data (see Figure 8):

- **Dataspace Connector:** Users will be able to log in with their unique access token to access historical data directly from the dataspace. After logging in, they can select the time interval/date range for analysis in the optimisation module (1-7 days);
- **JSON File Upload:** For standalone operation, users can upload a JSON file containing their actual load diagram. This option is ideal for users who prefer to operate independently of the dataspace or have specific load data ready for analysis;
- **Estimated Usage Calendar:** Users can manually input estimated hot water usage patterns over a 24-hour period. This method provides flexibility for users who do not have access to load diagrams, but still wish to have an elementary optimisation of their EWH settings.

EWH Usage

Select the source for EWH usage data:

- EWH load diagram time-series dataset from Data Space or uploaded JSON/CSV, comprising only timestamps and electrical consumption data (in watts) with minute resolution. This alternative provides results with higher precision. Maximum of 30 days.
- EWH daily usage example with periods and durations of hot-water usage. This alternative provides results with lower precision. Maximum of 24h.

What kind of input do you want to provide?

Data Space
Source EWH Load Diagram data with 1-min resolution from the Data Space

Upload JSON/CSV
Upload a JSON or CSV with the EWH Load Diagram Time-Series with 1-min resolution

Hot-Water Usage Example
I don't have a Load Diagram file. Fill in a daily basis typical calendar

What's your Data Space source?

CEVE/Sentinel
CEVE - Cooperativa Eléctrica do Vale d'Este

SEL
Smart Energy Lab

User ID

Replace with user ID, e.g.: 12340abcd

Select the period to optimize (max. 30 Days)

19/06/2024 - 25/06/2024

Figure 8: EWH GUI dataset source section.

When selecting one of the options, the dashboard updates itself respectively so that the end-user can fill in or select the necessary information: for the Data Space options, the user just selects the range of dates for the period to be simulated (see Figure 10); for the Upload JSON option, the user must upload a 1-min resolution JSON containing the EWH load diagram (see Figure 11); and for the Hot-Water Usage Example option, the user fills in several usage periods and durations (see Figure 12).

Figure 9: EWH GUI Data Space sourcing option.

Figure 10: EWH GUI JSON sourcing option.

Figure 11: EWH GUI usage example sourcing option.

The interface processes the input data and computes the most efficient operational strategy, balancing energy consumption and cost-effectiveness, as detailed in the mathematical foundation documentation.

The results section contains basic and intuitive information on the optimisation's output (see Figure 12), including:

- Original/Optimized EWH Load (kWh);
- Original/Optimized Pricing (€);
- Simulated Period (days);
- Total Available Flexibility (hours);
- Plot of EWH water temperature after optimisation (°C);
- Plots of EWH’s original/optimized energy diagrams (W).

Figure 12: EWH GUI results section.

Overall, the *Streamlit* GUI ensures that users can easily interact with the optimisation module, making informed decisions to enhance their energy management and achieve energy and cost savings.

3.2.1.1.2 Input data description

This service requires the user to provide the EWH load diagram and some static data (EWH specifications and other parameters). The static data should be provided via the GUI and include the parameters shown in Table 3.

Table 3: EWH input parameters specifications.

Parameter	Unit	Default
EWH Capacity	l	100
EWH Power	w	1800
EWH Maximum Allowed Temperature	°C	80
EWH standard non-optimized functioning water temperature	°C	60
Hot-Water Usage Comfort Temperature	°C	40
Selection between Simple or Dual Daily Tariff	-	Simple
Pricing per kWh (simple tariff only)	€	0.12
Price per kWh during the day period (dual daily tariff only)	€	0.15
Price per kWh during the night period (dual daily tariff only)	€	0.08
Daily Tariff	€	0.36

For the EWH load diagram, the user can provide data via data space (configuring the respective endpoints, as necessary), or by uploading a JSON/CSV with the load diagram and respective timestamps. For example, the JSON input should contain data in the following format:

```
[
  {
    "timestamp": "25-06-2024 00:00",
    "load": 0
  },
  {
    "timestamp": "25-06-2022 00:01",
    "load": 1500
  },
  ...
  {
    "timestamp": "25-06-2022 23:59",
    "load": 0
  },
]
```

For both dataspace and JSON/CSV input alternatives, the data must be provided with a 1-min resolution. For more details, see Table 4.

Table 4: EWH input data specifications.

Variable	Description	Unit	Resolution
timestamp	datetime timestamp for the observation	datetime	1-min
load	EWH instant power	w	

As described in section 3.2.1.1.1.2.4, the user has the option to run the service even if no EWH consumption is available. In this scenario, the user can provide a 24-hour hot water estimated usage, supplying the following data:

- *start*: a timestamp that represents the beginning of the estimated hot water usage;
- *duration*: an integer that represents the estimated duration of the hot water usage.

For example, for a synthetic scenario with four estimated hot water usages, the actual coded input would look like the following example:

```
[
{"start": "25/06/2022 08:00", "duration": 10},
{"start": "25/06/2022 08:15", "duration": 10},
{"start": "25/06/2022 12:00", "duration": 5},
{"start": "25/06/2022 20:00", "duration": 5}
]
```

3.2.1.1.3 Output data description

Since the service is run via a GUI, the user can interactively see the key results. The platform shows the following information:

- Original Load (kWh);
- Optimized Load (kWh);
- Original Pricing (€);
- Optimized Pricing (€);
- Simulated Period (days);
- Total Flexibility (hours).

In this GUI, the user is also able to interact with a plot that shows three different graphs:

- EWH Water Temperature & Usage;
- EWH Optimized Energy Consumption;
- EWH Original Energy Consumption.

An illustrated example of these main outputs can be found in Figure 12. However, for more advanced usage, the user is given the possibility of downloading a JSON containing the full results. This file contains the results shown in Table 5.

Table 5: EWH service output specifications.

Variable	Description	Unit
simulation_period	Simulated/Optimized Period including start and end datetimes	datetime
original_energy	Total accumulated energy for the real measurement profile	kWh
optimized_energy	Total accumulated energy for the optimized measurement profile	kWh
original_price	Total cost for the real measurement profile	€

optimized_price	Total cost for the optimized measurement profile	€
avg_daily_energy	Average daily energy Consumption for the optimized scenario	kWh
total_flexibility	Flexibility availability for the optimized period	minutes
perc_flexibility	Percentage of the total simulated period that can provide flexibility	%
avg_daily_flexibility	Average flexibility availability for the optimized scenario	minutes
savings_cost	Pricing savings between real and optimized scenarios	€
savings_energy	Energy savings between real and optimized scenarios	kWh
original_usage_profile	Estimated hot-water usage profile based on EWH's real load diagram	bool
optimized_calendar	Optimized EWH functioning calendarization	bool

An illustrative example of the content of this file is shown below:

```
{
  "user": "sample_user",
  "simulation_period": {
    "start": "2022-07-12 00:00:00+00:00",
    "end": "2022-12-13 23:59:00+00:00",
    "days_in_simulation": 7.0
  },
  "original_energy": {
    "value": 24.3384,
    "unit": "kWh"
  },
  "optimized_energy": {
    "value": 20.196,
    "unit": "kWh"
  },
  "original_price": {
    "value": 5.43,
    "unit": "Euro"
  },
  "optimized_price": {
    "value": 4.94,
    "unit": "Euro"
  },
  "avg_daily_energy": {
    "value": 2.8851,
    "unit": "kWh"
  },
  "total_flexibility": {
```

```

    "value": 9332.0,
    "unit": "minutes"
  },
  "perc_flexibility": {
    "value": 92.58,
    "unit": "Percent"
  },
  "avg_daily_flexibility": {
    "value": 1333.0,
    "unit": "minutes"
  },
  "savings_cost": {
    "value": 0.5,
    "unit": "Euro"
  },
  "savings_energy": {
    "value": 4.1424,
    "unit": "kWh"
  },
  "original_usage_profile": [
    {"timestamp": "2022-07-12 00:00:00+00:00", "hot_water_usage": 0},
    {"timestamp": "2022-07-12 00:01:00+00:00", "hot_water_usage": 0}
    /* ... more entries ... */
  ],
  "optimized_calendar": [
    {"timestamp": "2022-07-12 00:00:00+00:00", "ewh_on": 0.0},
    {"timestamp": "2022-07-12 00:01:00+00:00", "ewh_on": 0.0}
    /* ... more entries ... */
  ]
}

```

In addition to these outputs, the service contains another output that represents the energy savings when comparing both original and optimized EWH load diagrams. For this specific service, it is calculated as follows:

$$Energy\ Savings = \left| \frac{EWH\ Original\ Load - EWH\ Optimized\ Load}{EWH\ Original\ Load} \right|$$

Since the main goal of this service is to optimize the calendarization of a given EWH, this output is enough to comprehensively verify the tool’s efficiency.

3.2.1.2 Illustrative Example

For this service’s assessment, several real datasets were introduced, that provided real scenario results and conclusions.

3.2.1.2.1 Case characterization

This service was tested with real data from 5 different end-user EWH’s with periods ranging from 7 to 335 days. For each appliance, the service used the required data (EWH load diagram) with a 1-min resolution. For each appliance, there was no known information apart from the provided EWH load diagram.

3.2.1.2.2 Results

While some individual results are shown in Figure 12, this section identifies a wider range of testing and promotes the analysis of a more robust KPI (energy savings) with larger periods and with 5 different user datasets. The results presented in Table 6 support the functionality of the service with testing results' KPI ranging from 14% to 34%. The average scenario, counting with larger analysis periods, shows an average saving of roughly 21%.

Table 6: EWH results summary (savings - %)

User	Simulation Period (days)	Original Load (W)	Optimized Load (W)	KPI (Energy Savings)
User-1	7	26	22.45	14%
User-2	7	33	22.63	31%
User-3	7	36.39	24.16	34%
User-4	7	17.52	12.64	28%
User-5	7	33.87	22.90	32%
User-5	30	142.67	106.57	25%
User-5	335	1179.26	944.19	20%
Total	400	1468.71	1155.54	21%

3.2.1.3 Further developments

This service is currently in its beta version, and it is expected to transition to the final version in the next deliverable. This accounts for all beta feature validation in operational testing and other minor developments.

3.2.2 Heat Pump

3.2.2.1 General Characterization

This section describes the development of a neural network designed to compare predicted values with actual energy consumption data for heat pumps over a year. The neural network model aims to enhance the accuracy of energy consumption forecasts by learning from historical

data and adjusting its predictions based on real-world observations. By evaluating the model's performance through this comparison, one can assess its effectiveness in forecasting energy usage and identify potential areas for improvement.

3.2.2.1.1 Current status (until M13)

At the current stage, an LSTM neural network has been developed using the data provided by the Irish pilot, which pertains to "MITSUBISHI" heat pumps. Below is a description of the structure that has been implemented:

1 Data Preprocessing:

- **Correlation Matrix:** indoor temperature zone 1 and zone 2 are correlated with each other. So, the second one is dropped from the dataset;
- **Standardization of Numerical Columns:** This step involves adjusting the values in numerical columns to have a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. Standardization is crucial because it ensures that each feature contributes equally to the model's performance and helps in speeding up the convergence of the neural network;
- **Labelling of Categorical Columns:** Categorical data is converted into numerical format using techniques like label encoding. This is essential as neural networks require numerical input, and proper encoding ensures that the model correctly interprets the categorical variables.

2 Creation of Data Sequences:

- The data was organized into sequences distributed per minute. This sequence creation is vital for time-series analysis, allowing the model to learn patterns and dependencies over time. By structuring the data in this way, the neural network can better capture temporal dynamics and improve predictive performance.

3 Dataset Division:

- The dataset is split with the first 9 months allocated for training and the last 3 months for testing. This chronological split ensures that the model is trained on historical data and evaluated on the most recent data, simulating a real-world scenario where future predictions are based on past trends.

4 Neural Network Structure:

- **LSTM Layer:** An LSTM layer is included to handle the sequential nature of the data. LSTMs are a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) that are well-suited for time-series forecasting and sequence prediction tasks because they can learn long-term dependencies and patterns in the data. The LSTM layer helps in capturing the temporal dynamics by maintaining a memory cell that updates and forgets information over time;
- **Single Dense Layer:** Following the LSTM layer, a dense (fully connected) layer is used to map the learned features from the LSTM to the output space. This layer helps in synthesizing the information captured by the LSTM and making final predictions.
- **Optimizer (Adam):** The Adam optimizer is chosen for its efficiency and ability to handle sparse gradients. It combines the advantages of two other extensions of stochastic gradient descent: Adaptive Gradient Algorithm (AdaGrad) and Root Mean Square Propagation (RMSProp);
- **Loss Function (Mean Squared Error):** Mean Squared Error (MSE) is used as the loss function to measure the average squared difference between predicted and actual values.

MSE is particularly useful for regression tasks, providing a clear indication of how well the model's predictions align with the actual data.

5 Training Configuration:

- **Training Epochs:** The number of training epochs is set to 10. This parameter determines how many times the entire training dataset is passed through the neural network. During this exploratory phase, a lower number of epochs helps in quickly iterating and validating the model's performance.

3.2.2.1.2 Input data description

Here is the detailed description of the dataset columns:

- **TimeStamp:** This column contains the dates and times with a frequency of one minute for an entire year. Each row represents a specific moment, starting from 01/02/2021 to 01/02/2022, recording the exact hour and minute;
- **RoomTemperatureZone1:** This column records the indoor temperature of Zone 1. The values are expressed in degrees Celsius and are recorded every minute, providing a detailed trend of the temperature in Zone 1 throughout the year;
- **RoomTemperatureZone2:** Like the previous column, this one contains the indoor temperatures of Zone 2, also in degrees Celsius. The temperature is recorded every minute, allowing for monitoring and comparing temperature variations between the two indoor zones;
- **OutsideTemperature:** This column records the outdoor temperature every minute, expressed in degrees Celsius. These data are crucial for understanding the external climatic variations and their impact on indoor temperatures and energy consumption;
- **FlowTemperature:** This column records the temperature of the fluid (e.g., water) used for heating or cooling, measured in degrees Celsius. The fluid temperature is monitored every minute, indicating how the heating or cooling system operates under different environmental conditions;
- **EnergyConsumed:** This column records the energy consumed every minute, expressed in kilowatt-hours (kWh). The collected data allow for analysing energy consumption in relation to indoor and outdoor temperatures, as well as fluid temperature variations;
- **EnergyProduced:** Similar to the energy consumption column, this one records the energy produced every minute, also in kilowatt-hours (kWh). This information is useful for evaluating energy efficiency and the balance between energy consumed and produced;
- **OperatingMode:** This column indicates the operating mode of the system every minute. It can contain values representing different modes such as Stop, Heating, HotWater, FreezeStat, and LegionellaPrevention. This information is crucial for understanding how and when the system changes its operation in response to environmental conditions and energy needs.

Together, these columns provide a comprehensive and detailed view of the thermal dynamics and energy consumption in a building or system for an entire year.

Figure 13 represents the energy consumption of the heat pump, showing a nearly constant trend throughout the year except for October, where there was a noticeable peak, as the consumption is significantly lower compared to the other months.

Figure 13: Heat pump consumed Energy by month.

3.2.2.1.3 Output data description

The predicted values are very close to the actual values. This implies that the model is performing well. In Chapter 3.2.2.2.2, "Results", there is a graphical representation supporting this claim.

3.2.2.2 Illustrative Example

3.2.2.2.1 Results

For the results, a Mean Squared Error (MSE) of 3.31 was obtained. This is very good considering the range of variability of the target variable (**EnergyConsumed**), which is about 85. Consequently, the predicted data closely matches the observed values from the test set, as can be seen in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Predicted vs real energy consumption values for the heat pump.

3.2.2.3 Further developments

Given the coherence of the data, it is planned to use a mathematical model. In this case, the goal would be to minimize the energy produced or energy consumed.

The first phase will involve adapting the model to the data. Additionally, it might be considered to derive the energy cost for each minute of heat pump activation. This depends on the availability of the data.

All this does not imply that the neural network cannot be used, but it could be complemented with optimization to also provide a prediction of future consumption based on the current consumption provided by the user.

Finally, a web application will be created with which individual users can interact by entering their data and obtaining an optimization or a prediction of their specific heat pump. It is being considered whether to regulate everything on a per-minute basis or to average the variables and set the processing for 15-minute intervals of data.

3.3 Consumers clustering and segmentation tools

3.3.1 General Characterization

The Consumers Clustering and Segmentation service is designed to analyse and categorize households based on their energy consumption patterns and sociodemographic characteristics. This service aims to identify distinct segments of energy consumers, enabling targeted interventions and policies to promote energy efficiency.

The operations can be split into two main phases:

1. **Data Collection:** Gathering energy consumption data through smart meters and collecting sociodemographic data via questionnaires.
2. **Data Analysis:** Applying clustering algorithms to each data set separately and once integrated, performing dual clustering to derive comprehensive consumer segments.

Figure 15 that provides an overview of the Consumers Clustering and Segmentation services:

Figure 15: Flowchart of the consumer clustering and segmentation service.

3.3.1.1 Initial status

Before the initiation of the ENPOWER project, we had developed an advanced clustering methodology specifically designed for analysing energy consumption data. This methodology utilized 7 different clustering algorithms and their assessment to enhance the accuracy and reliability of the clustering results. The initial status focused solely on energy consumption data, aiming to identify distinct usage patterns among households.

Clustering methodology overview:

The initial step involves preparing the dataset, which consists of detailed energy consumption data collected from various households. To address the challenge posed by the diverse scales of the dataset's features, we apply Z-score normalization. This approach adjusts each feature to have a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one, as shown in the equation above:

$$z = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma}$$

where z represents the standardized value, x is the original value, μ is the mean, and σ is the standard deviation of the feature. This normalization facilitates the comparability of features with varying magnitudes and units, which is essential for the subsequent analysis.

A comprehensive suite of features was developed to encapsulate the intricacies of energy consumption patterns within households. These features are designed to reveal insights into

consumption behaviours, temporal dynamics, and variability essential for demand response management. The selected features include:

- Median Consumption;
- Average Peak Consumption;
- Peak Frequency in Each Time Slot;
- Consumption Standard Deviation;
- Average Consumption by Time of Day;
- Average Seasonal Consumption;
- Average Peak-Hours and Off-Peak-Hours Usage;
- Average Weekday and Weekend Usage;
- Seasonal Usage Trend;
- Autocorrelation Features (1 and 7 days);
- Consumption Growth;
- Variability in Peak-Usage Times.

Following dataset preparation, we apply seven traditional unsupervised clustering algorithms to the data: K-Means++, Fuzzy K-Means, Hierarchical Clustering, Birch, Self-Organizing Maps (SOMs), Spectral Clustering, and GMMs (Gaussian Mixture Models). A brief overview of the clustering algorithms employed can be found below:

K-Means++: K-Means++ enhances the traditional K-Means algorithm by improving the initial selection process of cluster centers. This method significantly reduces the likelihood of convergence to suboptimal solutions by spreading initial centroids more evenly across the data space. In our analysis, we used the scikit-learn library to implement K-Means++.

Fuzzy K-Means: Using the scikit-fuzzy library, we implemented the Fuzzy K-Means clustering algorithm. This method allows for nuanced segmentation by assigning varying degrees of membership to each data point across clusters, rather than restricting them to a single cluster. Our approach iteratively adjusted memberships and cluster centroids for a range of clusters.

Hierarchical Clustering: We applied Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering to explore the hierarchical structure of our energy consumption dataset. This method starts with each data point as its own cluster and iteratively merges clusters to reveal the data's natural stratification. Our implementation used the Euclidean distance to measure dissimilarity between data points and the Ward method as the linkage criterion. The Ward method minimises the increase in total within-cluster variance, leading to a more meaningful hierarchical organization of energy consumption patterns.

SOMs: SOMs were implemented for clustering using the MiniSom Python library. We used SOMs to identify distinct consumption patterns by organizing high-dimensional data into clusters within a two-dimensional grid. The algorithm initialized a grid of neurons with random weights and iteratively adapted these weights based on the dataset, ensuring similar data points moved closer in the grid space. This competitive adaptation process allowed us to achieve a topology-preserving mapping of the dataset. We explored various grid sizes and learning parameters to identify coherent clusters.

BIRCH: We applied the BIRCH algorithm to efficiently handle our extensive household energy consumption dataset. Using the scikit-learn library's Birch class, we carefully adjusted the algorithm's parameters, such as the maximum cluster radius in the leaf nodes and the branching factor, which determines node capacity in the CF Tree. This configuration allowed us to

incrementally process the data, building a Clustering Feature (CF) Tree that concisely represents the dataset's structure.

GMMs: We used GMMs to cluster household energy consumption data, implementing this method with the GaussianMixture class from the scikit-learn library. GMMs offer a probabilistic framework, assuming the data is generated from a mixture of several Gaussian distributions, each representing a cluster. This approach allows each cluster to have its own covariance matrix, accommodating ellipsoidal shapes of varying sizes in the data space. We configured GMMs to explore a range of potential clusters, using the Expectation-Maximization algorithm to iteratively estimate the parameters of the Gaussian distributions. The model was initialized with a certain number of components, representing the number of clusters, and fitted to the data. Data points were then assigned to clusters based on the highest likelihood of belonging to each Gaussian component.

Spectral Clustering: We used Spectral Clustering to identify complex structures within the household energy consumption dataset, particularly those that might not be linearly separable. This method, effective in revealing clusters through graph theory and linear algebra principles, was implemented using the scikit-learn library. We adjusted the number of clusters and fine-tuned other parameters to best match the dataset's characteristics. Specifically, we explored different configurations for constructing the affinity matrix and selecting the optimal number of neighbours for each data point, which are critical steps in the spectral clustering process. The final step involved applying a clustering algorithm, such as K-Means, to the transformed data, allowing us to assign each data point to a specific cluster.

Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs): We used GMMs to cluster household energy consumption data, implementing this method with the GaussianMixture class from the scikit-learn library. GMMs offer a probabilistic framework, assuming the data is generated from a mixture of several Gaussian distributions, each representing a cluster. This approach allows each cluster to have its own covariance matrix, accommodating ellipsoidal shapes of varying sizes in the data space. We configured GMMs to explore a range of potential clusters, using the Expectation-Maximization algorithm to iteratively estimate the parameters of the Gaussian distributions. The model was initialized with a certain number of components, representing the number of clusters, and fitted to the data. Data points were then assigned to clusters based on the highest likelihood of belonging to each Gaussian component. Once the clustering is performed using the seven algorithms, we evaluate their performance using specific clustering metrics such as silhouette score, Davies-Bouldin index, and other relevant criteria. The clustering assessment metrics are described in detail below:

- **Silhouette Score (SI):** This metric measures how similar an object is to its own cluster compared to other clusters. It is calculated for each sample by taking the difference between the average distance to all other points in the same cluster ($a(i)$) and the minimum average distance to points in the nearest different cluster ($b(i)$), and then dividing by the larger of the two values. The silhouette score ranges from -1 to 1, with higher values indicating that the object is well-matched to its own cluster and poorly matched to other clusters;
- **Davies-Bouldin Score (DB):** This score evaluates the average similarity between each cluster and its most similar other cluster. Similarity is defined as the ratio of the sum of within-cluster distances to the between-cluster distance. A lower Davies-Bouldin score indicates better clustering quality, signifying lower within-cluster distances and higher between-cluster distances;

- **Calinski-Harabasz Score (CH):** Also known as the Variance Ratio Criterion, the CH score is the ratio of the sum of between-cluster dispersion to within-cluster dispersion. It is calculated by dividing the between-cluster sum of squares by the within-cluster sum of squares, adjusted by the number of clusters and total number of samples. Higher Calinski-Harabasz scores indicate more distinct and compact clusters;
- **Dunn Index (DI):** The Dunn Index is designed to find clusters that are both compact and well-separated. It does this by maximizing the distance between different clusters while minimizing the distance within each cluster. The index is calculated by finding the minimum ratio of the distance between clusters to the maximum intra-cluster distance. Higher Dunn Index values suggest better clustering quality.

These metrics together provide a thorough evaluation of clustering results, allowing us to compare the performance of different clustering algorithms in our study.

3.3.1.2 Current status (until M13)

The questionnaire analysis has been reported in D2.2 as a separate analysis that will be integrated into the tool.

As far as it concerns the machine learning approach, the current status involves employing an ensemble methodology to integrate the results of the top-performing algorithms, as shown in Figure 16. The clustering algorithm results have been utilized to achieve optimal clustering outcomes through the ensemble clustering methodology as described below.

Figure 16: Current status of the clustering methodology.

We use an association matrix, which captures the agreement between the clusters identified by the top three algorithms. The association matrix is then normalized, and a distance matrix is computed from it. This distance matrix is converted to a condensed form suitable for hierarchical clustering. Finally, hierarchical clustering with the 'average' linkage method is applied to the condensed distance matrix to obtain the final cluster labels/results. Our ensemble clustering methodology, as described above can be witnessed in Figure 17.

Algorithm 1 Ensemble Clustering Approach

Require: Data points, D

Ensure: Cluster labels, $cluster_labels$

- 1: Decide on the number of clusters, $num_clusters$
- 2: Initialize $n \leftarrow$ number of data points in D
- 3: Initialize similarity matrix $similarity_matrix$ as a zero matrix of size $n \times n$
- 4: **for** each clustering algorithm ($K - means + +$, $Hierarchical$, $Birch$) **do**
- 5: Obtain $labels$ for D based on $num_clusters$ from the clustering algorithm
- 6: **for** $i = 1$ to n **do**
- 7: **for** $j = 1$ to n **do**
- 8: **if** $labels[i] == labels[j]$ **then**
- 9: $similarity_matrix[i][j] \leftarrow similarity_matrix[i][j] + 1$
- 10: **end if**
- 11: **end for**
- 12: **end for**
- 13: **end for**
- 14: Normalize $similarity_matrix$ by dividing each element by the number of clustering algorithms
- 15: Compute $distance_matrix \leftarrow 1 - similarity_matrix$
- 16: Convert $distance_matrix$ to condensed form $condensed_distance_matrix$
- 17: Perform hierarchical clustering on $condensed_distance_matrix$ using 'average' linkage method
- 18: Obtain final cluster labels $cluster_labels$
- 19: **return** $cluster_labels$

Figure 17: Algorithm of the Ensemble Clustering Approach.

3.3.1.3 Input data description

The input data can again be split into two different categories. The one mainly concerns the electrical loads of the households that the Machine Learning clustering approach is going to be applied to and the answers from the questionnaires. In Table 7, the input data for the machine learning approach can be seen. For the questionnaire analysis, the input data depends on the answers.

Table 7: Input data for the machine learning approach.

Attribute	Description	Unit/Format
House_id	Identifier of each household	int
timestamp	Timestamp of measurement.	ISO 8601
consumed_energy	Electrical energy consumed	kWh

3.3.1.4 Output data description

The final output of this service is going to be the clusters that have been created from the involvement of both approaches that have been described above. Most likely, a .csv file is going to contain the clusters appointed, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Output data of the clustering tool.

Attribute	Description	Unit/Format
House_id	Identifier of each household	int
Cluster	Group/Cluster of households appointed	int

3.3.2 Illustrative Example

3.3.2.1 Case characterization

Our study is grounded in a detailed case analysis using publicly available data from the London Data Store, an initiative by the Greater London Authority (GLA) to promote data transparency. The "Smart-meter Energy Use Data in London Households" dataset is central to our analysis, offering half-hourly energy consumption readings from smart meters across London households.

This dataset provides a comprehensive view of energy usage across 5,567 households in Greater London, spanning from November 2011 to February 2014, comprising over 167 million data points. The format of the dataset was as described in the section 3.3.1.3, and the same analysis can be performed with adequate data from the project's pilot sites.

3.3.2.2 Results

The evaluation of clustering algorithms using various metrics reveals a nuanced landscape of algorithmic performance. The Ensemble method generally ranked among the better performers in silhouette scores, indicating a decent level of cluster cohesion and separation. However, it experienced a steep drop for configurations with more than seven clusters, suggesting a decline in clustering quality as the number of clusters increased. The Davies-Bouldin score often showed the Ensemble method favourably, with its lower scores indicating better partitioning, though it did not uniformly outshine all methods. Regarding the Calinski-Harabasz score, the Ensemble method emerged as one of the top performers, consistently yielding high scores indicative of better cluster separation. Despite its strong showing, it did not surpass the performance of the individual component clustering method K-Means++. This outcome highlights the individual strength of K-Means++ in producing clusters with minimal intra-cluster variance and maximal inter-cluster separation within our dataset. For the Dunn Index, the Ensemble method demonstrated a significant performance spike at a six-cluster solution. Conversely, some methods, such as Fuzzy K-Means and Spectral Clustering, often fell behind across these metrics, struggling to consistently define well-separated clusters, suggesting a general underperformance compared to other techniques.

While silhouette analysis and other metrics are important, they may not directly translate to the optimal number of clusters for DR programs due to the specific needs of utility providers. Given the focus of utility providers on real-world usability, we opted for a solution with clear benefits for program implementation. Rather than striving to identify the universally 'best' number of clusters, we have chosen to examine a six-cluster solution in depth. This choice is strategically motivated by its practical utility for energy providers. For this six-cluster solution, the Ensemble method emerged as the top performer according to two out of four key evaluation metrics. Consequently, the following analysis will focus on the results obtained from the Ensemble clustering approach with six clusters.

The analysis of the non-normalized load profiles in Figure 18, reveals a clear division of households into high, medium, and low consumption categories. Although the data's scale makes it challenging to discern more specific energy usage patterns, such as peak consumption times or day-to-day variations within these broad groups, this classification into distinct consumption levels is a crucial insight. It helps us understand the varied energy demands across the customer base and informs the development of targeted interventions. For instance, high-consumption households might benefit from energy efficiency programs, while medium-consumption households could be targeted with time-of-use pricing plans to incentivize off-peak consumption.

Figure 18: Non-normalized load profiles of all households for each cluster.

3.3.3 Further developments

Future developments of the tool within the domain of energy consumer segmentation will incorporate the correlation with the socio-demographic features that will be available from the answers of the questionnaires handed to pilot users and the use of Explainable AI techniques for enhancing transparency and result meaning. An analytical description can be found below:

- **Correlation with Socio-Demographic Features:** Incorporating socio-demographic data to understand the impact of various factors on energy consumption could lead to more personalized energy-saving strategies.

- Expanded Application of Explainable AI:** Future developments of the tool will include the integration of Explainable AI (xAI) methodologies. This enhancement will improve model transparency and provide deeper insights into consumer behaviour, aiding in the development of targeted energy management strategies.

Adding to the previous, we aim to incorporate our solution to the Digital Twin that is being developed for ENPOWER. Nevertheless, mapping questionnaire answers to real consumption data might be a quite complex task, due to GDPR regulations and non-IID nature of the data. Thus, the limitation of what has been promised lies in whether the pilot energy consumption data can be correlated with answers and segmentation results, coming from the questionnaire responses and results.

3.4 FATEC – Flexibility assessment tool for energy communities

3.4.1 General Characterization

The FATEC [29], [30] was developed to characterize the flexibility potential of individual consumers of residential units, when exposed to DR programs. DR programs are usually characterized by providing price signals to consumers, from which a change in their electricity consumption is expected due to a price change, which relates to their price elasticity of demand. A thorough characterization of elasticity, as provided by FATEC, enables improved behaviour modelling and further optimisation of pricing strategies. FATEC is built on a data-driven approach and supported by a causal analysis of electricity consumption behaviour.

A simplified flow chart of the current version of FATEC is available in Figure 19. Input data is fed into a data cleaning tool, which assures that the user provides the necessary data (including the required treatment, outcome, and associated covariates), and in the correct format. A data pre-processing tool is applied to the input data for aggregation based on the inferred measurement frequency. The core of the FATEC tool, the causality model, is executed. The processed data is fed into the causality model, which estimates the price elasticity of demand of individual consumers, and the potential for flexibility for each of the price signals. Finally, the outputs of the causality model are retrieved by the user. Inputs and outputs, as well as the detailed characterization of each module, are further detailed in the next subsections.

Figure 19: FATEC architecture.

3.4.1.1 Initial status

Before the start of the ENPOWER project, FATEC was available as a stand-alone tool (i.e., a set of scripts which can be used to run the tool with a certain input file and provides a local output file). The tool was fully implemented in Python programming language.

A data cleaning and pre-processing module was created to identify the correct covariates and possible missing variables within the input data structure and to remove possible outliers.

The causality model was based on Robin's G-method, more specifically with the application of the parametric g-formula. For causality assessment purposes, the price signal is the *treatment*, and the electricity consumption of the households is the *outcome*. The model used to minimise the mean-squared error and control for established confounders (variables that simultaneously affect the treatment and the outcome) was a Kernel regression model. This framework enables us to find the dependency between the price (X) and consumption (Y), while controlling for the confounders (Z), as shown in the following Equation:

$$E[Y|X_j] = \sum_{h=1}^{24} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N E[Y|X_j, (Z_{hi}, Z_{2i}, Z_{3i})]$$

Therefore, the model returns Y estimates ($E[y]$) at each price $X = x$ value for every Z. In this tool, the considered confounders are calendar (such as hour of the day, day of the week, and day of the year) and meteorological variables (such as ambient temperature, and precipitation). The model was implemented using the Python library *Causality* [31]. For more information on FATEC's initial version, interested readers are directed to [29], [30], which characterize and provide a more in-depth analysis of the methodology.

3.4.1.2 Current status (until M13)

The new contributions to FATEC during this first wave of the ENPOWER project are:

- A new Flask Application Programming Interface (API) module, still ongoing (with some parts being tested and others still under development), to execute the core of the FATEC tool in the backend. The objective is to have a stand-alone tool but able to address external requests for flexibility estimates from third parties, returning the results as soon as the calculation of the outputs is finished. Thus, with this improvement, in the future, it should no longer be necessary to create a local instance of the tool;
- Analysis of relevant individual consumer data from specific members of the ENPOWER project consortium, namely Coopérnico, which includes their household electricity consumption and the prices they were exposed to for one year. An illustrative example of this analysis is provided below. These preliminary analyses will help to improve the assumption made when developing the causal model, and to consider the most relevant covariate for this specific problem;
- It is expected that more partners provide similar datasets to accelerate the development of the causal model for FATEC. It is also important to note that these preliminary analyses are only developed to check if a relationship between price and demand exists in general and to have a sense of the order of magnitude of that relationship. However, a more complex causal model is needed to estimate the price elasticity of demand of consumers, and how their elasticity varies with the hour of the day.

3.4.1.3 Input data description

The tool inputs are described in Table 9, and must be provided in a JSON file. Inputs relate, not only to general information (“*General_Info*”) on the demand response program but also to how the mapping should be made between the provided historical data (“*Historical_data*”) and the outcome and treatment variables for the causal model. Furthermore, the JSON file includes historical data of the confounders, price (*treatment*), and consumption (*outcome*), for each timestamp considered.

Table 9: Characterization of FATEC input data.

Input	Type	Attributes	Description
General_Info	int	intervalSchedule.starttime	Start time of the period of analysis, in UNIX.
General_Info	int	intervalSchedule.endtime	End time of the period of analysis, in UNIX.
General_Info	int	noofconfounders.value	Number of confounder variables considered.
General_Info	string	interventionsignal.value	Name of the key that contains the signal or treatment provided to consumers (e.g., “price”).
General_Info	string	interventionType.value	Type of intervention provided to consumers (options: “discrete”)
General_Info	string	price.valueUnit	Units of the price provided to consumers (e.g., “€/kWh”)
General_Info	string	responsevariable	Name of the key that contains the response variable or outcome from consumers (e.g., “use”)
General_Info	int	timestep.value	Resolution of the (e.g., 1)
General_Info	string	timestep.unit	Unit of the timestep considered in the above attribute (e.g., “h”)
General_Info	int	numberofusers	Total number of consumers that were under the DR program and are present in the provided input data.
Historical_data	int	userID	Identification of each consumer present in the input data.
Historical_data		user_profile	Key that considers the time series of confounders, treatment, and outcome variables.
Historical_data	float	use	Time series of the outcome or response variable between the

			start and end date for each consumer, in kWh.
Historical_data	float	price	Time series of the treatment variable between the start and end date for each consumer, in €/kWh.
Historical_data	float	externaltemperature	Time series of a confounder (in this case, the external ambient temperature) between the start and end date for each consumer, in °C.
Historical_data	int	localhour	Time series of the timestamps considered between the start and end date for each consumer, in UNIX.

3.4.1.4 Output data description

FATEC outputs are described in Table 10 and are provided in a JSON file along with four figures that postprocess and present graphically some of these outputs. Some examples of the JSON structure and figures are also detailed in Table 10.

Table 10: Characterization of FATEC outputs.

Output #	Type	Attributes	Description
1	JSON file	-	JSON structure with all the outputs of the model, including the average consumption, and the expected consumption variation for each individual consumer, for a certain price signal, for each hour of the day.
2	Figure	-	Figure with the average consumption for each price signal, for each hour of the day.
3	Figure	-	Figure with the expected consumption variation for each price signal, for each hour of the day.

4	Figure	-	<p>Figure with the estimated probability of response to each price signal, for each hour of the day.</p>
5	Figure	-	<p>Figure with a heatmap of multiple consumers and respective ranking in terms of demand response potential. Only returned when there is more than one consumer in the input data.</p>

3.4.2 Illustrative Example

3.4.2.1 Case characterization

Data provided by Coopérnico, member of the ENPOWER consortium, was used to develop a preliminary analysis. Data included household electricity consumption for one consumer, and the prices he was exposed to, which varied in time since its tariff was indexed to the MIBEL spot market price. The period of analysis was roughly one year.

Although for now, this dataset includes only one consumer, a preliminary analysis was done to estimate the relationship between price and demand for this consumer. In addition to the data provided by Coopérnico, INESC TEC gathered external additional data such as meteorological data (more specifically precipitation and temperature data) from publicly available APIs [32].

For this purpose, a simple linear regression model was conceptualized. A factor analysis (a statistical method aimed at reducing a large number of variables into a smaller set of factors) was also performed, and it was validated if the assumptions of the linear model still held, namely if the model shows a constant variance, if errors are normally distributed, if there is no collinearity, and if there is linearity on the link scale. Finally, the relationship between price and demand was analysed briefly.

3.4.2.2 Results

A factor analysis of all the available variables, which are essentially calendar (weekday, weekend, year, hour, day, month, season) and meteorological (precipitation, temperature), allowed us to detect collinearities among variables (as seen in Figure 20). For example, it allowed us to understand that variables *month* and *season* are interchangeable.

Figure 20: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of Coopérnico consumer example.

After that, fitting a simple linear model with the remaining variables showed that, for this specific consumer, variables *month* and *holiday* were not statistically significant and, therefore, should not be included in the model.

The main assumptions of a simple linear model were checked, and the inherent autocorrelation present in the data was taken care of by including a new variable which considers the consumption from the previous hour. When including the final set of variables related to the year, weekday, and consumption lag, a stepwise regression model was able to explain 92% of the data.

As a conclusion from the regression model fitted, only a weak relationship between price and consumption was found, and therefore more data are needed to validate the approach, as seen in the next Equation.

$$Consumption_x = -0.42 + .000012 * marketprice_x + .0021 * year_x + .00014 * weekday_x + 0.95 * Consumption_{x-1}$$

Note that more details on the consumers themselves, such as the type of equipment they own, or sociodemographic information, would enable a more precise characterisation.

3.4.3 Further developments

The current version of the tool considers only the energy consumption of individual residential consumers.

Although FATEC can consider multiple consumers, and rank them according to their flexibility potential, it is not fully adapted to a setting such as energy communities, where the multiple residential consumers and their assets are operated according to the strategy of the community itself. Therefore, the next step for FATEC is to analyse the specificities of the energy community setting and evaluate the impact and possible changes that must be made on the assumptions that are at the core of the causality model currently in use.

As a second step, the causality model itself will be improved, by extending the individual flexibility estimates to aggregated ones. Moreover, the feasibility of considering different types of prosumer assets (e.g., thermal or mobility loads) and extending the tool to non-economic incentives will be checked. There is also a possible contribution from ongoing developments from a parallel project (InterConnect), where a causal model is being developed for the electric mobility setting.

All developments carried out will be thoroughly validated through the establishment of different case studies and analysis of respective outcomes. It is expected that the developments already comply with the input/output data requirements for an efficient integration with the pilot projects.

As can be checked, the developments here proposed are aligned with the original proposal of the project, mainly in terms of checking different levels of aggregated flexibility estimates within the energy community (individual or community-level flexibility).

Finally, let's remark that the availability of observational data from experiments or pilot projects is crucial for the development of causal models. As a mitigation strategy, if no consumer data is available from the project partners and their pilot projects in the next months, we plan to find a methodology to generate synthetic data of electricity consumption for multiple consumers for a certain period. This synthetic data could be used to build different scenarios of sets of consumers and to validate, to the extent possible, the assumptions made by the causal model.

3.5 Summary

This section focuses on developing tools to enhance flexibility in energy systems, a critical need given the increasing intermittency of renewable energy sources and the rising variable energy consumption patterns throughout the day.

To address this, digital twins were developed for EWHs to optimise their operation, particularly when limited data is available. These digital twins aim to determine the optimal operation times for EWHs, leading to energy and cost savings. A standalone GUI was also developed, enabling users to directly interact with the service. Key outputs include water temperature data, as well as comparisons between optimised and original energy consumption. This model will be integrated into the SITEC and OSTEC tools, which are being enhanced by INESC TEC as part of this project. For heat pumps, the plan is to integrate them with a consumption prediction model. The final application will feature a predictive model where users can input their data to receive optimised consumption forecasts and cost predictions for their heat pumps.

Clustering and segmentation tools were developed to categorise and analyse households based on their energy consumption patterns and sociodemographic characteristics. These tools can promote policies and interventions aimed at improving energy usage. The development process involved two primary phases: data collection and data analysis. Future work will focus on correlating consumption patterns with sociodemographic data and incorporating explainable AI (xAI) into the methodology.

The FATEC tool was developed to assess the flexibility potential of individual consumers when exposed to DR programs. The main objective is to analyse how changes in electricity pricing might influence consumption behaviour, allowing for the optimisation of pricing strategies. Key developments included the creation of an API and data analysis in collaboration with Coopérnico, which will support further tool enhancement. The outputs will provide insights into average consumption and expected variations based on different price signals.

In conclusion, the development of these tools—ranging from digital twins and predictive models to clustering, segmentation, and flexibility assessment—represents significant progress in optimizing energy systems for greater flexibility and efficiency. By integrating advanced analytics and user-friendly interfaces, these tools not only enhance energy management but also empower consumers to make informed decisions, ultimately contributing to more sustainable and cost-effective energy consumption patterns. The ongoing and future work will further refine these tools, ensuring they continue to meet the evolving challenges of energy systems.

4 Self-consumption optimisation adaptable to different consumers activation modes

4.1 Overview

Task 5.3 focuses on developing a unified data-driven framework aimed at optimizing the self-consumption of RES and enhancing operational efficiency across diverse energy community configurations. This task integrates advanced technologies and methodologies to cater to both individual consumers and collective communities, ensuring adaptability to various energy management scenarios. This task is divided into two main categories, each using advanced technologies and methods to serve both individual consumers and collective communities. These categories are designed to handle different energy management situations effectively, promoting innovation and sustainability in the following ways as shown in Figure 21.

In the individual level optimisation category, the focus is on enhancing energy efficiency and self-consumption strategies for individual consumers and users. It utilizes tools connected to three different technological enablers TE-10, TE-13 and TE-14. It incorporates solutions such as managing seasonal energy demands, integrating AI-powered energy efficiency tips and enabling real-time information exchange through nudging services. These approaches are personalized to align energy usage with consumer preferences and encourage participation in demand response initiatives.

On the other hand, the community level-based category emphasizes on optimizing collective self-consumption and developing fair benefit-sharing models among energy communities. Four different technological enablers are related to this category, namely TE-9, TE-11, TE-12 and TE-14. It integrates tools to facilitate real-time data exchange, implement collective smart EV charging with Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) capabilities, optimise the scheduling of flexible assets and enhance community engagement. All the tools are meant to address issues for different pilots of the project. These initiatives aim to maximise revenue, facilitate peer-to-peer trading, and meet comfort requirements within community energy strategies, promoting sustainability and equitable energy distribution.

Figure 21: Task 5.3 main categories.

4.2 Self-consumption optimisation tool

4.2.1 General Characterization

The Self-Consumption Optimisation Tool, being developed for the ENPOWER project, aims to unify a data-driven framework to forecast and optimize collective RES self-consumption and asset operation, specifically tailored for the Greek pilot. This innovative tool will provide users with the capability to choose from various devices and specify the hours during which they typically use these devices. Based on this input, the tool will offer suggestions to shift or shed their loads to enhance collective energy consumption efficiency. A visual representation of the workflow can be seen in Figure 22.

The core functionalities of the tool are outlined as follows:

- **Forecasting PV Plant Production:** The tool will generate a 3-day forecast of photovoltaic (PV) plant production, focusing mainly on the next-days forecast. This forecast will leverage advanced data analytics and weather prediction models to provide accurate and reliable production estimates.
- **Energy community/Island Load Forecasting:** Using state-of-the-art methods, the tool will predict the energy load for the entire island or energy community. These forecasts will consider historical consumption data, weather conditions, and other relevant factors to ensure precise load predictions.
- **Incorporating User Load Habits:** The tool will integrate individual user load habits, including device usage patterns and preferred times of operation. By understanding these habits, the tool can provide personalized recommendations for load shifting or shedding.
- **Heuristic Optimisation:** With the knowledge of both production and consumption patterns, as well as user-specific load habits, the tool will employ a heuristic optimisation function. This function will aim to balance and optimize energy consumption based on the available production, thereby maximising the self-consumption of renewable energy and minimising reliance on external energy sources.

Figure 22: Workflow of the self-consumption optimization tool.

The Self-Consumption Optimisation Tool will offer a user-friendly interface with a visual overview, making it easy for users to understand and interact with. Users will be able to see forecasts, receive optimisation suggestions, and monitor their energy consumption patterns.

By optimising energy consumption based on production forecasts, the tool will contribute to a more efficient and sustainable energy ecosystem. It will enable users to make informed decisions about their energy usage, reduce energy waste, and enhance the overall efficiency of the energy community. This tool represents a significant step towards achieving greater energy independence and sustainability for the Greek pilot and beyond.

4.2.1.1 Initial status

The Self-Consumption optimisation tool, as a complete entity, did not exist prior to the initiation of the ENPOWER project. This tool is set to be developed specifically for the ENPOWER initiative. However, several components that will form the core functionalities of this tool were already in existence.

Energy community/island load forecasting:

During the BD4NRG European project, extensive data was collected from the entire island of Tilos. This data, similar in volume and type to what will be incorporated into the load forecasting tool, allowed for the development of relevant models. Given that Chalki and Tilos have comparable energy consumption patterns – both measured using devices that monitor the entire island – these models are directly applicable. Moving forward, we aim to enhance the accuracy of these models by integrating new data from Chalki, utilizing state-of-the-art machine learning and forecasting techniques.

Forecasting PV plant production:

GEARS being a licensed aggregator by the Regulatory Authority for Energy in Greece, has experience in trading in the Hellenic Power Exchange wholesale electricity markets and thus evaluating the production forecasts given by two renewable energy forecasters. RES Plants of various capacities scattered around different locations in Greece. Specializing in solar PV plants GEARS can accordingly provide an optimum dynamic generation prediction based on the forecasters' data.

4.2.1.2 Current status (until M13)

At this stage of development, the tool includes two basic functionalities. Advanced forecasting models for the island's energy consumption have been created and tested on data from Tilos, producing good results. Furthermore, the PV plant production forecasting which has been demonstrated on data from a plant located in the Greek pilot.

Additionally, detailed mockups of the tool's interface have been prepared. These mockups help visualize the engineering team's ideas and provide a template for the design team. They are showcased in detail in Section 4.2.2.

Forecasting PV Plant Production:

As mentioned, two forecasters provide their production forecasts to GEARS for the renewable PV plant installed on Chalki island. After that GEARS evaluates the two-forecasts using a set of algorithms and KPIs specifically tailored for making dynamic forecast decisions that will yield the most accurate production-results. Currently, the production forecast data have been archived since 1st of April 2024 and evaluated from the 7th of June 2024.

4.2.1.3 Input data description

The input data for the self-consumption optimisation tool is the following:

- PV plant production data, as detailed in Table 11;
- The island's total electrical consumption as measured by the metering infrastructure;
- Smart data from the participating actors of the project (households, hotels, businesses, utility plants);
- Self-reported data from the island's residents that will be used for the self-consumption optimisation features.

Table 11: PV production input data.

Attribute	Description	Unit/Format
timestamp	Timestamp of measurement	ISO 8601
produced_energy	Electrical energy produced	kWh
solar_radiation	Solar radiation levels	W/m ²
technical_characteristics	Technical characteristics of the panels	string

The user load habits are going to be incorporated into the tool and using the developed algorithms and heuristics, a consumption optimisation model is going to be proposed.

At this stage, the smart metering infrastructure of the participating actors is being installed and is not yet fully operational. The same is true for the island’s total measured consumption.

The currently available input data consists of the PV plant production (as detailed Table 11) and a consumption dataset from the island of Tilos (input data detailed in Table 12 and illustrated in Figure 23) that shares similar load patterns to Chalki as explained in section 4.2.1.1. Once the metering infrastructure is set, we will shift to the energy data of Chalki. Also, besides the metered data, the island residents will be given the opportunity to self-report their loads and get personalized suggestions for ideal load management.

Table 12: Energy consumption input data.

Attribute	Description	Unit/Format
timestamp	Timestamp of measurement	ISO 8601
consumed_energy	Electrical energy consumed	kWh

Figure 23: Historical total energy consumption data sample of the Tilos island.

Forecasting PV Plant Production:

The input data that are mandatory to have an accurate forecast of the PV plant’s power and energy production consist of:

- The installed capacity of the renewable energy plant and the type of the plant (PV plant, wind turbine etc.);
- Technical characteristics of the renewable energy plant; mounting or tracking structure, number and capacity of inverters, PV module technology, etc.;
- Geographical coordinates, longitude and latitude;
- Whether the plant is fully, partially or not operational (PV plant availability).

- Solar radiation assessment.
- Historical production data to increase the accuracy of the forecast.

4.2.1.4 Output data description

The output data of the tool will be the result of the corresponding analysis based on the inputs provided. These results will be displayed in a user-friendly manner to optimize the user experience. Currently, the output data (specified in Table 13) are planned, with additional features likely to be added during development:

Table 13: Output data of the self-consumption optimisation tool.

Output Data	Description
PV Production Forecasts	The tool will display a 3-day ahead forecast of the island’s PV park production, providing users with detailed information on expected solar energy generation.
Optimal Consumption Time	Informed by the production and consumption forecasts, the tool will inform users of the ideal times during the day for electricity consumption, helping them utilise energy more efficiently.
Load Scheduling Suggestions	Based on the production and consumption data, as well as user-selected activities, the tool will suggest an optimal arrangement of loads throughout the day to maximize energy efficiency.
Incentive Information	To encourage users to follow the tool’s suggestions, it will showcase the benefits achieved by adhering to these recommendations. This includes information on energy efficiency improvements, money saved, and potential reductions in carbon emissions.

Forecasting PV Plant Production:

Output data of the forecast mechanism include the calculated power and energy production of the renewable plant, as for our case, the latest values of radiation and the PV plant actual production are captured and can be depicted.

Notable is the fact that weather conditions forecast dynamically change during the day, the more accurate the weather forecast is, the more accurate forecast on the production from the renewable plant we will get. Due to this factor, the accuracy in the PV plant production is higher for the next day (if not for the next hours), rather than the next three days. The forecast prediction that is going to be used in our analysis will be the day ahead forecast to capture as much realistic conditions as possible. It is crucial for any energy community that the analysis will provide its result ahead of time to offer the community members sufficient time to respond to the community's energy needs.

4.2.2 Illustrative Example

For the needs of the illustrative example, (we) implemented state-of-the-art Machine Learning (ML) models for energy production and consumption. The consumption models were temporarily tested on the data from Tilos. This forecast along with the PV production data will serve as the basis for the self-consumption optimisation functionalities that will be developed in the later stages of the project.

Below one can see some mockups of the mentioned functionalities. Starting with Figure 24, the insert activities page is displayed. On this page, the user selects the electricity consuming activities that he plans to do on the following day from a user-friendly list of common flexible loads.

Figure 24: Dashboard of the self-consumption optimisation tool - insert activities.

After this selection, the user proceeds to the self-consumption optimisation page.

- Insert activities
- Self-consumption
- CLOC
- My profile

Self-consumption optimization

Suggested Activity Management

	Laundry	11:00 - 12:00
	Charging EV	14:00 - 17:00
	AC Usage	12:00 - 18:00

By following our model's suggestions you achieve:

 CO2 reduction
Reduce 4.6kg of CO2 this day

 Energy optimization
Up to 40% less energy consumed

 Cost savings
Save up to 13€ this day

Figure 25: Dashboard of the self-consumption optimisation tool – self-consumption optimisation.

On this page (Figure 25), the application displays the 3-day PV production forecast (Figure 26) and suggests to the user the ideal time to perform the activities selected in the previous step based on the PV production (Figure 27). In addition, it displays the potential earnings of the user that follows the suggestions.

Figure 26: Chalki’s PV hourly forecasted generation.

Figure 27: Hours during the day with medium and high energy generation (kWh).

4.2.2.1 Case characterization

We used the Tilos dataset to train state-of-the-art models for electricity consumption forecasting. As already mentioned, the characteristics of the two islands are very similar and we believe that their load profiles are going to match. In any case, these data serve as a placeholder until we have the full picture regarding Chalki consumption data.

For the training of the models, we tested combinations of Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Boosting Trees. Having predicted the consumption and production data we will have most of the required data to conduct develop our heuristics and conduct the self-consumption optimisation.

4.2.2.2 Results

The results of the total Island consumption forecasts can be seen in Figure 28. In total, 3 models were tested, namely, the LSTM, the XGBoost and the LightBMG model. Figure 28 to Figure 30 display the test set forecast for our data, for each model respectively.

Figure 28: LSTM total island consumption forecasting.

Figure 29: XGBoost total island consumption forecasting.

Figure 30: LightGBM total island consumption forecasting.

The figures are accompanied by the metrics calculations. The performance metrics were chosen to be Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE), as it is the industry standard for forecasting performance evaluation. Figure 31 displays the relative RMSE and MAE between the three chosen models.

Figure 31: Evaluation scores and comparison for the LSTM, XGBoost and LightGBM forecasting models.

It is evident that the LSTM Model achieves superior performance in both metrics and therefore there is a high chance that it will be selected as our primary implementation method moving forward.

4.2.3 Further developments

The next steps in the development of the tool revolve around three key areas: data integration, algorithms, and application development.

For data integration, the experiments and models should be rerun with the data from Chalki infrastructure (consumption) given the recent installation of the smart meters that provide live data information. Moreover, based on the production forecasters and the real production historical data a dynamic hourly forecast generation profile will be created taking into account the production seasonality and the regional solar irradiation availability. This analysis will be used in the algorithms which will eventually combine the load with the generation profiles as described below.

For algorithms, the development will focus on creating an algorithm combined with a heuristic. This algorithm aims to calculate the optimal self-consumption optimisation by considering the current electrical loads and the PV production forecast. The goal is to tailor the algorithm to achieve maximum energy efficiency.

For the application, the transition of mockups into a fully functional web application will be undertaken. The structure of the application will be similar to the one currently displayed but with significant improvements in both form and functionality. The enhancements will focus on improving user experience, adding new features, and ensuring the application is robust and scalable.

4.3 Closed-loop optimal load control and intelligent monitoring of electric appliances for residential users

4.3.1 General Characterization

The Closed-loop optimal load control and intelligent monitoring of electrical appliances for residential users will be integrated into the Self-Consumption Optimisation Tool (Section 4.2), being developed for the ENPOWER project. It aims to unify a data-driven framework to forecast and optimize collective RES self-consumption and asset operation, specifically tailored for the Greek island of Chalki. This innovative tool will provide users with the capability to choose from various devices and specify the hours during which they typically use these devices. Based on this input, the tool will offer suggestions to shift or shed their cooling loads to enhance collective energy consumption efficiency. A visual representation of the workflow can be seen in Figure 32.

The basic functionalities of the integrated tool are described below:

Smart Meter Data Integration: The tool will take real-time load data from smart meters, allowing for a detailed and accurate understanding of energy consumption patterns across the island. The smart meters will not only be placed in residential household setups but also in entertainment areas placed on the island.

Cooling Load Disaggregation: The tool will disaggregate the cooling loads from the overall energy consumption data. This will help in identifying the specific contribution of cooling systems to the total energy demand.

Comfort-Based Models Calculation: The tool will calculate comfort-based models that consider indoor temperature and humidity. These models will ensure that any recommendations for load shifting or shedding do not compromise the comfort of the users.

Heuristic Optimisation: This function will aim to shift the disaggregated cooling loads in a way that maintains user comfort based on indoor temperature and humidity, whilst minimizing reliance on external energy sources and self-consumption.

Adding these functionalities to the Self-Consumption Optimisation Tool for Chalki will significantly enhance the efficiency and sustainability of energy usage on the island, paving the way for a more resilient and self-sufficient energy community. The tool will be more general and be applied not only on a community-level optimisation schema but also on an individual one.

Figure 32: Workflow of the closed-loop optimal load control and intelligent monitoring tool of electrical appliances for residential users.

4.3.1.1 Initial status

The Self-Consumption optimisation tool, as a complete entity which incorporates the closed-loop optimal load control and intelligent monitoring of electrical appliances for residential users, did not exist before the start of the ENPOWER project. This tool is being developed specifically for the ENPOWER initiative. However, several components that will constitute the core functionalities of this tool were already in place.

Comfort-Based Models Calculation:

During the BD4NRG European project [33], Comfort-based models together with the corresponding algorithms were created. Moving forward, we aim to enhance the accuracy of these models by integrating new data from Chalki that is tailored for cooling, utilizing state-of-the-art machine learning and forecasting techniques and comfort-based models.

Cooling Load Disaggregation:

In some previous projects, such as H2020 SAAM², H2020 BRIGHT³, H2020 BD4OPEM⁴, and Slovenian national project Uporabljalj Pametno which cannot be referenced, several approaches to load disaggregation were implemented. The most successful approach for load disaggregation was the implementation of a model developed inside project Uporabljalj Pametno (no reference available) that was capable of disaggregating PV production from the smart meter data based on historical smart meter data and weather data (outdoor temperature and solar irradiation). At the start of the ENPOWER project, the cooling load disaggregation algorithm did not exist and will be fully developed inside the ENPOWER project. It will enable estimating the daily energy consumption of cooling equipment inside individual living units equipped with smart meters therefore educating the consumer on his approximate energy consumption used for the cooling loads.

4.3.1.2 Current status (until M13)

Currently, the actual data from the Greek pilot are not yet integrated into the solution and thus the comfort-based models, the cooling load disaggregation and the heuristic optimisation functions are not yet in their final form. The development of the tool that is going to host those algorithms in a user-friendly environment has begun while waiting for the actual data to arrive. An estimation of the data volume and intensity has taken place in order to formulate the activities of the tool. Furthermore, it is worth noting that load disaggregation is never an easy task. It is always an approach that tries to recreate a piece of information that was lost during aggregation at the smart meter. It provides tools that can replace exact information provided by costly upgrades of infrastructure inside the apartment (e.g., installing numerous submeters) with energy consumption estimates of limited reliability or certainty. The quality of estimates always depends on the amount of supporting information available at a specific location, the quality of the appliance model, and the presence of specific consumption patterns that the modelled appliance creates during normal operation.

4.3.1.3 Input data description

At the current point in the project, the Greek pilot is not yet ready to provide smart meter data for development and evaluation purposes. In general, the required input for this tool can be further divided into three categories, namely, smart meter data, comfort-based data and weather data. Those will be analysed below separately for each functionality of the tool.

Comfort-based data:

As mentioned earlier there is no data currently for the Greek pilot. According to the solution that we are aiming to produce and based on the literature and our previous works, in Table 14 the required data and their formats are presented. The indoor and outdoor temperature and the relative humidity are all required as input to the comfort models, as they are the most important attributes to calculating the comfort levels of a user.

² <https://saam2020.eu/>

³ <https://www.brightproject.eu/>

⁴ <https://bd4opem.eu/>

Table 14: Comfort-based input data.

Attribute	Description	Unit/Format
timestamp	Timestamp of measurement.	ISO 8601
indoor_temperature	Indoor temperature	°C
relative_humidity	Relative humidity	%
outdoor_temperature	Outdoor temperature.	°C

Smart meter and weather data for cooling load disaggregation:

For development purposes data from the Portuguese pilot was provided by the CEVE which contains historical data from one energy community with several consumers and a district-grade PV plant. There are 28 households in the community.

Each household has a smart meter that measures imported and exported electrical energy at 15-minute intervals in kWh. The information is further expanded by introducing weather information from the open-source weather API which provides additional information for outdoor temperature and shortwave radiation both for forecasting purposes and historical weather data for the selected geolocation. Weather information is important for modelling the dynamics of PV production, heating, and cooling because the amount of solar irradiation and outdoor temperature influence the amount of electrical energy produced at PV and the amount of heating or cooling energy needed to maintain the desired indoor comfort level.

The input data format for all stages of cooling load disaggregation contains the attributes that are presented in Table 15.

Table 15: Cooling load disaggregation input data.

Attribute	Description	Unit/Format
timestamp	Timestamp of measurement.	ISO 8601
consumption	Electrical energy imported from the grid.	kWh
injection	Electrical energy exported to the grid.	kWh
outdoor_temperature	Outdoor temperature.	°C
shortwave_radiation	Solar irradiation.	W/m ²

At several stages of cooling load disaggregation, the service requires input data in the same format but with different time frames. For the initial stage of the cooling load disaggregation, the cooling load disaggregation service requires historical data with one year of historical data to be able to model the correlation between the outdoor temperature and daily electrical energy consumption.

The operational stage of cooling load disaggregation works as an estimator of electrical energy consumption spent by cooling loads during a current day. The model takes historical data for the last 7 days including the data of a current day. Forecasted data is added to the historical data to provide the missing data from the current time of the day until midnight of the current day. All data inputs contain the same set of attributes as defined in Table 15.

4.3.1.4 Output data description

The output of the service will include the recommended cooling load shifting schedule, aiming to minimise energy consumption while maintaining the same comfort levels. This schedule will ensure the current comfort levels are preserved in terms of relative humidity and indoor temperature. Initially, the cooling load disaggregation module will output the electrical consumption of the cooling loads as a single time series. This time series will serve as input for the heuristic optimisation functions developed for the service, as outlined below.

Cooling load disaggregation:

The cooling load disaggregation component provides a simple electrical energy consumption estimate caused by the cooling loads installed in a living unit (e.g., apartment) during a current day. The output data format of a cooling load disaggregation component is defined in Table 16. The first attribute, `datetime_start`, defines a starting point of a time frame inside which a cooling load disaggregation estimate is being made. It is formatted according to the ISO 8601 standard. The second attribute, `datetime_end`, defines the end point of a time frame inside which a cooling load disaggregation estimate is being made. A time frame for estimation is currently being selected as a time between the start of a current day and the end of a current day.

The last attribute, `energy_consumption`, contains an estimated energy consumption caused by the cooling loads from the `datetime_start` until `datetime_end`.

Table 16: Cooling load disaggregation output data format.

Attribute	Description	Unit/Format
<code>datetime_start</code>	Starting datetime of a time frame used for energy consumption estimate.	ISO 8601
<code>datetime_end</code>	End datetime of a time frame used for energy consumption estimate.	ISO 8601
<code>energy_consumption</code>	Estimated energy consumption by cooling loads.	kWh

4.3.2 Illustrative Example

The screenshot in Figure 33, displays an example of a potential Closed Loop Optimal Control page. The purpose of this page is to assist the user in saving energy and resources while maintaining the same comfort levels. Through applications of cooling load disaggregation and self-consumption optimisation, a recommendation is given to the user to alter his cooling loads in a way that keeps the same comfort whilst maintaining minimal cost and energy usage.

Closed Loop Optimal Control

Cooling Loads

Current Comfort Levels

Load Shifting

Activity	Suggested shifting
Laundry	11:00 - 12:00
Charging EV	14:00 - 17:00
AC Usage	12:00 - 18:00

By adapting your energy consumption schedule to the suggested option you can achieve equivalent CI with 11% less consumed energy and cost.

Figure 33: Closed-loop optimal control.

4.3.2.1 Case characterization

As mentioned above there are no data available currently from the Greek pilot. For development purposes, data from the Portuguese pilot provided by CEVE was used. This dataset contains historical information for an energy community consisting of 28 households and a district-grade PV plant. For each household, there is a smart meter installed and the relevant data retrieved are utilized to test the cooling load disaggregation function that is going to be utilized in the service. The coordinates of the houses were provided and used as reference points to correlate with the corresponding weather data. This geographical information enabled precise matching with localized weather conditions, including outdoor temperature and solar radiation, which are crucial for accurately modelling and predicting energy consumption patterns. By aligning the household coordinates with high-resolution weather datasets, we ensured that the environmental factors influencing each household's energy usage were accurately captured and are going to be necessary for the Greek pilot as well.

Cooling load disaggregation:

Due to the lack of cooling load data availability at this point of the project, the current case study includes the analysis of historical daily energy consumption data together with historical data for outdoor temperature and solar shortwave radiation which represents the portion of the electromagnetic spectrum emitted by the sun that reaches the Earth. It contains visible light, UV light, and near-infrared radiation. The amount of shortwave radiation is directly proportional to the amount of produced electrical energy at the PV plant. Figure 34 represents the workflow for the cooling load disaggregation.

Figure 34: Case study flow for cooling load disaggregation.

4.3.2.2 Results

The results for this specific tool are narrowed down to the testing of the disaggregation algorithms on the Portuguese pilot data, provided by CEVE, and their corresponding weather attributes which were retrieved through an open API.

Cooling load disaggregation:

The data from the Portuguese pilot contains data from 28 households and a common central PV plant. The data analysis has not identified any correlation between the increased outdoor temperature and daily household energy consumption. The analysis concludes and confirms that households in the Portuguese pilot do not have cooling assets installed, or they are not using them which currently does not support the development of cooling load disaggregation algorithms. An example of daily energy consumption and outdoor temperature visualisation is presented in Figure 35.

Figure 35: Daily energy consumption and outdoor temperature for household 4 in Portuguese pilot.

Despite having no correlation between the increased outdoor temperature and daily household energy consumption, a few households in the Portuguese pilot present increased energy consumption in the winter months when the outdoor temperature drops. This can potentially indicate increased domestic hot water usage or using any kind of electric heating asset for heating the household. The example of increased household energy consumption with decreasing outdoor temperature can be seen in data for household 7 in the Portuguese pilot which is presented in Figure 36.

Figure 36: Daily energy consumption and outdoor temperature for household 7 in Portuguese pilot.

4.3.3 Further developments

The work that will be undertaken until the next report of services involves real data integration from the Greek pilot. Since this service requires data during the summer, the goal is to work on data from the summer of 2024 since the sensors will have this kind of data. So, the developments that are going to follow can be split into three categories: the smart-meter data integration, the functional algorithms and the actual application development and integration with the Self-consumption optimisation tool. As mentioned, the smart-meter data is already under construction to have this Summer’s data.

In what concerns to algorithms, future work will include the adaptation and improvement of two existing algorithms considering the following criteria:

- **Comfort-Based Models Calculation:** Comfort-based models will be calculated considering indoor temperature and humidity to ensure that any load shifting or shedding recommendations do not compromise user comfort. These models will be a critical component of the heuristic optimisation process;
- **Cooling Load Disaggregation:** When the smart meter data from the Greek pilot containing cooling loads becomes available, the model will be extended by applying the following steps:

- Identification of baseline daily consumption (excluding cooling loads) based on analysis of historical smart meter data and weather data;
- Creating a model of cooling load energy consumption depending on outdoor temperature and shortwave radiation;
- Providing results for daily cooling load consumption based on smart meter data, outdoor temperature and shortwave radiation.

Regarding the application development, the following tasks will be considered:

- **Transition from Mockups to Functional Web Application:** The development will focus on transitioning the current mockups into a fully functional web application that will be integrated into the Self-consumption optimisation tool as described in chapter 4.2. The application’s structure will remain similar but will undergo significant improvements in form and functionality to enhance user experience;
- **User Experience Enhancements:** The application will be designed to be more robust and scalable, with new features added to improve usability. Users will be able to select various devices and specify their typical usage hours, with the tool providing suggestions for shifting or shedding cooling loads to enhance collective energy consumption efficiency;
- **Visual Workflow Representation:** A visual representation of the workflow, similar to the one depicted in Figure 33, will be integrated into the application to help users understand the optimisation process.

4.4 V2G-enabled flexibility management platform for providing incentives to communities of EV drivers

4.4.1 General Characterization

The V2G-enabled flexibility management platform is designed to optimize electric vehicle (EV) charging by leveraging real-time electricity demand data from smart meters, weather forecasts, historical consumption patterns, and solar energy production data. It provides users with hourly guidance on when to charge their EVs. The platform aims to shift flexible demand from EV charging during time intervals where renewable energy production exceeds total demand. During periods of low renewable energy availability, the service advises users to avoid charging. For users with vehicle-to-grid (V2G) compatible charging stations, the software offers the option to discharge their EVs to support the grid during peak demand, allowing them to earn energy credits in return. These credits can then be used to charge their vehicle in public charging stations for free or redeemed for reductions in their electricity bill. V2G-enabled flexibility management platform empowers users to make environmentally conscious decisions while contributing to grid stability and optimising their energy costs. The solution can be embedded within existing commercial EV charging applications to help charging point operators such as large utilities to provide smart charging incentives to their clients. The workflow of the V2G-enabled flexibility management platform is depicted in Figure 37. For ENPOWER, this service will be added within the EV Loader app and tested within Chalki Island.

Figure 37: Workflow of the V2G-enabled flexibility management platform.

4.4.1.1 Initial status

Parity Platform has developed and commercialised EV Loader a software platform that helps charging station owners (large charging point networks, hotels and other businesses) to monitor EV charging stations and collect payments remotely. EV Loader consists of:

- Web dashboard that enables charging station owners to monitor their assets, set costs per kWh charged and review real-time status and historical transactions;
- Mobile application for drivers that enables them to select a charging station and initiate a payment.

Before the start of the project, no service was developed to allow charging point operators to offer incentives to users to charge at specific time intervals.

4.4.1.2 Current status (until M13)

API connection to the data hub⁵ of the Greek transmission system operator for mainland Greece has been implemented, enabling EV Loader to receive data related to renewable energy availability for the mainland Greek transmission grid.

⁵ <https://www.admie.gr/en/market/market-statistics/key-data>

In addition, mobile app front-end elements for the existing EV Loader application were developed. These elements were added to the user dashboard to inform users of opportunities to charge at a lower cost, as illustrated in Figure 38.

Figure 38: Forecast of RES production in the Greek power grid (in percentage) embedded in the EV Charging Mobile app.

4.4.1.3 Input data description

The input data to the V2G-enabled flexibility management platform is the forecast for RES availability and the forecast of the total energy demand in the examined location. Table 17 shows all the parameters required to run the service. Note that, when examining mainland Greece, ISP3 IPTO RES FORECAST and ISP3 LOAD Forecast can be used via the API⁶. A small example of the RES and load forecast data is shown in Table 18.

Table 17: Input data of the V2G-enabled flexibility management platform.

Attribute	Description	Unit/Format
time_interval_counter	Integers from 1 to 48 indicating the 30 min interval starting from 00:00- 00:30 and ending at 23:30- 00:00	Integer
Re_mwh	Renewable energy capacity in MW during the specific 30 min interval	MW

<https://www.admie.gr/en/market/market-statistics/key-data>

De_mwh	Total energy demand during the specific 30 min interval in MW	MW
date	The date of the examined day	date

Table 18: Example of RES and load forecasting data, serving as input to the V2G-enabled flexibility management platform.

Date	Time	RES Forecast (IPTO)	Load Forecast (IPTO)
31/08/2024	1	780	5170
	2	790	5090
	3	820	4990
	4	840	4890
	5	860	4790
	6	880	4720
	7	890	4670
	8	910	4640
	9	940	4620
	10	950	4620

	35	2100	6110
	36	1630	6050
	37	1220	6010
	38	1020	6020
	39	920	6070
	40	950	6070
	41	1000	6020
	42	1050	5900
	43	1110	5720
	44	1170	5500
	45	1250	5250
	46	1320	5250
	47	1380	5400
	48	1440	5410

4.4.1.4 Output data description

One of the outputs of the platform is the determination of the RES share in the system and the respective hourly index of incentive for activation of flexible loads, i.e., the EV charging stations. Table 19 provides the outputs of the platform, namely the hourly percentage of RES in the system and the respective incentive index for activation of the flexibility resources.

Table 19: Outputs of the V2G-enabled flexibility management platform (percentage of RES and incentive index).

Date	Time	RES Forecast (IPTO)	Load Forecast (IPTO)	RES (%)	Incentive (Index)
31/08/2024	1	780	5170	15%	1
	2	790	5090	16%	1
	3	820	4990	16%	1
	4	840	4890	17%	1
	5	860	4790	18%	1
	6	880	4720	19%	1
	7	890	4670	19%	1
	8	910	4640	20%	1
	9	940	4620	20%	2

	35	2100	6110	34%	2
	36	1630	6050	27%	2
	37	1220	6010	20%	2
	38	1020	6020	17%	1
	39	920	6070	15%	1
	40	950	6070	16%	1
	41	1000	6020	17%	1
	42	1050	5900	18%	1
	43	1110	5720	19%	1
	44	1170	5500	21%	2
	45	1250	5250	24%	2
	46	1320	5250	25%	2
	47	1380	5400	26%	2
	48	1440	5410	27%	2

For each 30-minute interval on the day, the expected percentage of RES in the energy production mix is presented. Based on that percentage an index (1 to 4) is generated for that specific time interval. This index indicates:

- **Category 1:** Very low RES percentage. Flexible loads activated only on an immediate need basis, discharging incentives when possible, increase costs for EV charging;
- **Category 2:** Low RES percentage. Flexible loads activated only on a need basis;
- **Category 3:** High RES percentage. Flexible loads can be freely activated at full capacity;
- **Category 4:** Very high RES percentage. Flexible loads should be heavily incentivized.

EV Loader receives the percentage values and category for each specific time interval. Then based on the category of each time interval, charging station owners receive the following actionable guidance.

For time intervals in Category 1: Charging Station owners and drivers see messages on the mobile app front end informing them that during the examined interval RES percentage is low and that charging sessions should be avoided if possible. When a V2G compatible vehicle and EV charging station are present, discharging may also be advised.

For time intervals in Category 2 and 3, charging station owners and drivers do not see any special messages on the front end. There is no guidance to charge or avoid charging.

For time intervals in Category 4: Charging station owners and drivers view messages on the mobile app front-end informing them that there is higher RES availability and encouraging them to charge.

4.4.2 Illustrative Example

4.4.2.1 Case characterization

The objective of the V2G-enabled flexibility management platform pilot is to enhance the utilization of locally generated solar energy on Chalki Island and minimize energy imports from the neighbouring island of Rodos by encouraging optimal scheduling of electric vehicle charging in stations installed on the island.

Key Inputs for the V2G-enabled flexibility management platform:

- **Solar energy production data:** Real-time data streams from photovoltaic (PV) installations distributed across Chalki Island, capturing solar energy generation on a 30-minute basis;
- **Total demand forecast:** Day ahead forecast at 30 min for the island's electricity demand, factoring in variables such as seasonal patterns, diurnal load variations, and meteorological conditions;
- **Historical consumption data:** Aggregated data from past electricity usage and production on Chalki Island to inform and refine forecasting algorithms.

Operation of the V2G-enabled flexibility management platform:

- **Data integration:** The V2G-enabled flexibility management platform will continuously aggregate and process real-time solar production data and demand forecasts;
- **Optimal charging intervals:** The platform will use predictive analytics to identify periods when solar generation is projected to exceed local demand. During these intervals, the platform will issue recommendations for EV charging, prioritizing midday hours when solar irradiance peaks. The forecasts generated will be validated by monitoring actual observations;
- **Charging avoidance recommendations:** Conversely, during periods of low solar output or high demand – typically during early morning or evening hours – the platform will advise users to defer EV charging. To ensure actual incentives for users are in place, the cost per kWh in public charging stations can be modified according to the flexibility platform forecasts. Integration with EV Loader software used to process payments in charging stations installed on the island is required.

4.4.2.2 Results

Parity Platform has established an OCPP connection to EV Charging Stations installed in Chalki and has been collecting real-time and historical data from charging stations (as presented in Figure 39) and compiling graphs to visualize baseline and peak demand from flexible assets. Data connection for total RES production from solar projects and total load on the island is being implemented to enable the generation of an optimal scheduling plan. Resulting from these, a set of notifications, prompts and guidance to the users are made available, as exemplified in Figure 40.

Figure 39: Daily consumption in kWh / charging station as observed in Chalki Island.

Figure 40: Mock-ups of prompts and guidance to end users.

4.4.3 Further developments

The next steps in the development of the tool involve:

- Adding features within the platform to support V2G Charging. Currently, the platform supports incentivizing charging through lower prices or increasing prices to discourage charging and displaying relevant messages to the drivers;
- Adding data connections to support Chalki Pilot use case including data for total electricity demand on the island and total production from local solar assets.

4.5 OSTEC – Optimised scheduling tool for energy communities

4.5.1 General Characterization

OSTEC tool is responsible for simulating the operation of Energy Communities (ECn). It optimises energy utilisation through intra-community energy sharing, thereby diminishing dependence on energy retailers and delivering financial savings to participants. The allocation of energy resources and resultant cost efficiencies among members is contingent upon the chosen business model where the stakeholders can capitalize on the community operation.

Central to this service is a computational tool engineered to oversee the operational dynamics of ECn. Driven by Mixed-Integer Linear Problem (MILP) computations, this tool computes the optimal energy management strategies of the ECn flexible assets, profiting from the collective self-consumption of the local surplus energy. It is computed under the programming language Python, using the modelling framework PuLP [34]. Figure 41 depicts an overview of the OSTEC tool.

Figure 41: OSTEC tool general overview.

4.5.1.1 Initial status (before project start)

OSTEC can run under two different modes. In both cases, in the current version, the objective is the collective cost minimization, although other objectives could also be defined. Figure 42 shows both modes.

In Individual Cost (IC) mode, two stages corresponding to the two first stages described in [35] are run. The first stage is the individual cost minimisation of all members of the ECn which is used for a constraint in the second stage, where a collective cost minimisation is performed considering local energy transactions but guaranteeing that all members of the ECn keep or reduce their individual energy cost. To set up this constraint a local transaction price is needed before the optimisation, being the pricing mechanism one of the inputs of OSTEC that can be selected from those defined in the section 4.5.1.1.2.

In Shadow Price (SP) mode, a collective cost optimization is directly performed assuming that a fair compensation mechanism will be defined later for the final settlement. In this mode, both bilateral exchanges or pool type exchanges can be selected. In the bilateral mode, a constraint guarantees that for each pair of members, the energy sold by one is the energy bought by the other one. In the pool like mode, the constraint sets that the sum of all sales equals the sum of all purchases. Although for settlement purposes energy and prices should be computed after delivery, considering that OSTEC is to compute the pre-delivery optimal batteries schedules, OSTEC provides price information as the shadow prices of the constraints that equal sales with purchases, either bilateral for each transaction or uniform price for the pool like optimisation.

OSTEC can also be adapted to a post-delivery functionality where no assets are to be scheduled since all consumptions and generations are already known and measured, but where the outputs can be the final transactions. For example, to determine the local transactions that minimise the ECn energy cost, which must be communicated to the DSO when post-delivery energy allocation mechanisms are allowed by the regulatory framework, for example by sending the so-called dynamic allocation coefficients as in the Portuguese case, see [36].

Figure 42: OSTE running modes.

4.5.1.1.1 Mathematical Formulation

4.5.1.1.1.1 Stage 1

This stage focuses on optimising the energy management of each prosumer individually, based on their specific energy exchanges. Each prosumer is equipped with a behind-the-meter battery and a photovoltaic (PV) installation, with the option to participate in an external generation facility shared with other members. The battery scheduling is optimized to minimize the energy bill by considering the prosumer’s consumption, local generation, and supply, along with the relevant selling/buying and feed-in tariffs. Any energy imbalance is addressed by the retailer, who can either provide additional energy to cover deficits or purchase excess energy from the prosumer. At this stage, the individual cost is calculated for each prosumer based solely on their installed technologies and consumption, excluding participation in the energy community and interactions with other members. The decision variables include battery charging and discharging, energy exchanges with the retailer, and the net balance for each meter. Figure 43 depicts the main interactions between the prosumer resources and the supplier.

Figure 43: Stage 1 overview of prosumer and supplier interactions.

Table 2, Table 21, Table 22 and Table 23 provide the indices, sets, parameters, variables, the objective function and the constraints of the first stage, respectively.

Table 20: Indices and sets from Stage 1.

Indices and sets		
$t \in T$	Set of time intervals/slots over the operation period.	-
$n \in N$	Set of meters.	-
$s \in S$	Set of storage assets within each meter.	-

Table 21: Parameters from Stage 1.

Parameters		
Δt	Optimisation step.	h
$\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy}$	Supply energy tariff of n at t .	€/kWh
$\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell}$	Feed-in energy tariff of n at t .	€/kWh
$\hat{\lambda}_t^{market\,buy}$	OMIE-indexed buying tariff at t .	€/kWh
$\hat{\lambda}_t^{market\,sell}$	OMIE-indexed selling tariff at t .	€/kWh
$\hat{E}_{n,t}^C$	Meter n load profile at t .	kWh
$\hat{E}_{n,t}^G$	Meter n behind-the-meter generation at t .	kWh
$\hat{P}_n^{CPE,max}$	Maximum allowed power flow through the meter of n .	kW
$\hat{E}_{n,s}^{B,N}$	Nominal capacity of battery s of n .	kWh
$\widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,min}$	Minimum state of charge of battery s of n .	%
$\widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,max}$	Maximum state of charge of battery s of n .	%
$\hat{P}_{n,s}^{B,max}$	Maximum input and output power of battery s of n .	kW
$\hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,C}$	Charging efficiency of battery s of n .	%

$\hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,D}$	Discharging efficiency of battery s of n .	%
\hat{M}	A very big number (e.g., 1E6).	kWh
$\hat{\lambda}^{EXTRA}$	(Fictitious) very high cost of violating $\hat{P}_n^{CPE,max}$, independent of n or t .	€/kW
$\hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg}$	Estimated degradation cost of battery s of n , applicable to all <u>discharged</u> energy.	€/kWh

Table 22: Variables Stage 1.

Variables		
$E_{n,s,t}^B$	Energy stored by battery s of n , at t .	kWh
$SOC_{n,s,t}^B$	State of Charge (SOC) of battery s of n , at t .	%
$E_{n,s,t}^{B,C}$	Energy charged by battery s of n , at t .	kWh
$E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}$	Energy discharged by battery s of n , at t .	kWh
$\delta_{n,s,t}^{B,C}$	Auxiliary binary variable to impede s of n from simultaneously charging and discharging at t .	-
$E_{n,t}^{SUP_{retail}}$	Energy supplied to n from its retailer, at t .	kWh
$E_{n,t}^{SUR_{retail}}$	Energy surplus sold by n to its retailer, at t .	kWh
$E_{n,t}^{SUP_{market}}$	Energy bought by n at an OMIE-indexed price, at t .	kWh
$E_{n,t}^{SUR_{market}}$	Energy surplus sold by n at an OMIE-indexed price, at t .	kWh
$\delta_{n,t}^{SUP}$	Auxiliary binary variable to impede n from simultaneously buying and selling to the retailer at t .	-
$E_{n,t}^{CMET}$	Net consumption at meter n , at t .	kWh
$P_{n,t}^{EXTRA}$	Extra power flow at the meter of n , beyond $\hat{P}_n^{CPE,max}$, at t .	kW

Table 23: Objective function and constraints from Stage 1.

Objective function and constraints		
$\min \sum_{t \in T} \left(E_{n,t}^{SUP_{retail}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{retail}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell} + E_{n,t}^{SUP_{market}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{market_{buy}} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{market}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{market_{sell}} \right. \\ \left. + P_{n,t}^{EXTRA} \cdot \hat{\lambda}^{EXTRA} + \sum_{s \in S} E_{n,s,t}^{B,D} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg} \right)$		(1)
s. t.		
$E_{n,t}^{CMET} = E_{n,t}^{SUP_{retail}} + E_{n,t}^{SUP_{market}} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{retail}} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{market}}$	$\forall t \in T$	(2)
$E_{n,t}^{CMET} = \hat{E}_{n,t}^C - \hat{E}_{n,t}^G + \sum_{s \in S} (E_{n,s,t}^{B,C} - E_{n,s,t}^{B,D})$	$\forall t \in T$	(3)
$-P_{n,t}^{EXTRA} - \hat{P}_n^{CPE,max} \leq \frac{E_{n,t}^{CMET}}{\Delta t} \leq \hat{P}_n^{CPE,max} + P_{n,t}^{EXTRA}$	$\forall t \in T$	(4)
$E_{n,t}^{SUP_{retail}} + E_{n,t}^{SUP_{market}} \leq \hat{M} \cdot (\delta_{n,t}^{SUP})$ $E_{n,t}^{SUR_{retail}} + E_{n,t}^{SUR_{market}} \leq \hat{M} \cdot (1 - \delta_{n,t}^{SUP})$	$\forall t \in T$	(5)

$E_{n,s,t}^B = E_{n,s,t-1}^B + \left(E_{n,s,t}^{B,C} \cdot \hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,C} - \frac{E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}}{\hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,D}} \right)$	$\forall t \in T, s \in S$	(6)
$\widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,min} \leq SOC_{n,s,t}^B = \frac{E_{n,s,t}^B}{\widehat{E}_{n,s}^{B,N}} \cdot 100\% \leq \widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,max}$	$\forall t \in T, s \in S$	(7)
$\frac{E_{n,s,t}^{B,C}}{\Delta t} \leq \widehat{P}_{n,s}^{B,max} \cdot (\delta_{n,s,t}^{B,C})$ $\frac{E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}}{\Delta t} \leq \widehat{P}_{n,s}^{B,max} \cdot (1 - \delta_{n,s,t}^{B,C})$	$\forall t \in T, s \in S$	(8)
$E_{n,s,t}^{B,C}, E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}, E_{n,s,t}^B, SOC_{n,s,t}^B, E_{n,t}^{SUP_{retail}}, E_{n,t}^{SUP_{market}}, E_{n,t}^{SUR_{market}}, E_{n,t}^{SUR_{retail}}, P_{n,t}^{EXTRA} \geq 0$	$\forall t \in T, s \in S, ev \in EV$	(9)

Table 24 provides the description of the constraints.

Table 24: Constraints descriptions.

Constraints	Descriptions
(1)	Arbitrage objective function
(2)	Equilibrium constraint
(3)	Net consumption constraint
(4)	Defines the extra power flow at the Meter (strongly penalized in the O.F.)
(5)	Impede simultaneous buying and sell from the retailer
(6)	BESS energy content update
(7)	BESS SoC limits constraints
(8)	BESS power limit constraints
(9)	Positive variables' constraints

Having the values from the decision variables, the individual costs, \hat{C}_n^{ind} , can be calculated as:

$$\hat{C}_n^{ind} = \sum_{t \in T} \left(E_{n,t}^{SUP_{retail}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{retail}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell} + E_{n,t}^{SUP_{market}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{market_{buy}} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{market}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{market_{sell}} + P_{n,t}^{EXTRA} \cdot \hat{\lambda}^{EXTRA} + \sum_{s \in S} E_{n,s,t}^{B,D} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg} \right)$$

4.5.1.1.1.2 Stage 2

Nomenclature

This stage is a minimisation of the collective ECn bill using the existing flexibility, but also guaranteeing that the new individual energy bills of all peers are always equal to or less than their value obtained in the individual optimization of stage one (in this case between two members). Apart from the same energy exchanges of each prosumer with its retailer and with the facilities it partially owns, internal energy exchanges take place to share the local energy surplus among the community members, before injecting it back into the grid, so that a member can sell its

surplus to another member, or locally buy an additional supply. This stage enables community members to locally share their energy surplus, allowing them to gain additional benefits from participating in the ECn while retaining their individual benefits. Figure 44 represents the individual and collective energy exchanges in a simplified way. The indices, sets, parameters, variables, objective function and constraints are all indicated in Table 25, Table 26, Table 27 and Table 28, respectively.

Figure 44: Stage 2 overview of prosumers and supplier interactions.

Table 25: Indices and sets from Stage 2.

Indices and sets		
$t \in T$	Set of time intervals/slots over the operation period.	
$s \in S$	Set of storage assets within each meter's meter.	-
$n \in N$	Set of meters.	-

Table 26: Parameters from Stage 2.

Parameters		
Δt	Optimisation step.	h
$\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy}$	Supply energy tariff of n at t .	€/kWh
$\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell}$	Feed-in energy tariff of n at t .	€/kWh
$\hat{\lambda}_t^{market\,buy}$	OMIE-indexed buying tariff at t .	€/kWh
$\hat{\lambda}_t^{market\,sell}$	OMIE-indexed selling tariff at t .	€/kWh
$\hat{E}_{n,t}^C$	Meter n load profile at t .	kWh
$\hat{E}_{n,t}^G$	Meter n behind-the-meter generation at t .	kWh
$\hat{P}_n^{CPE,max}$	Maximum allowed power flow through the meter of n .	kW
$\hat{E}_{n,s}^{B,N}$	Nominal capacity of battery s of n .	kWh

$\widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,min}$	Minimum state of charge of battery s of n .	%
$\widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,max}$	Maximum state of charge of battery s of n .	%
$\widehat{P}_{n,s}^{B,max}$	Maximum input and output power of battery s of n .	kW
$\widehat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,C}$	Charging efficiency of battery s of n .	%
$\widehat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,D}$	Discharging efficiency of battery s of n .	%
\widehat{C}_n^{ind}	Energy bill of n from stage 1.	€
$\widehat{\lambda}_t^{grid}$	Global access tariff for self-consumption, at t .	€/kWh
$\widehat{\lambda}_t^{p2p}$	(Fictitious) local energy price, at t .	€/kWh
\widehat{M}	A very big number (e.g., 1E6).	kWh
$\widehat{\lambda}^{EXTRA}$	(Fictitious) very high cost of violating $\widehat{P}_n^{CPE,max}$, independent of n or t .	€/kW
$\widehat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg}$	Estimated degradation cost of battery s of n , applicable to all <u>discharged</u> energy.	€/kWh

Table 27: Variables from Stage 2.

Variables		
$E_{n,s,t}^B$	Energy stored by battery s of n , at t .	kWh
$SOC_{n,s,t}^B$	SOC of battery s of n , at t .	%
$E_{n,s,t}^{B,C}$	Energy charged by battery s of n , at t .	kWh
$E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}$	Energy discharged by battery s of n , at t .	kWh
$\delta_{n,s,t}^{B,C}$	Auxiliary binary variable to impede s of n from simultaneously charging and discharging at t .	-
$E_{n,t}^{SUP_{retail}}$	Energy supplied to n from its retailer, at t .	kWh
$E_{n,t}^{SUR_{retail}}$	Energy surplus sold by n to its retailer, at t .	kWh
$E_{n,t}^{SUP_{market}}$	Energy bought by n at an OMIE-indexed price, at t .	kWh
$E_{n,t}^{SUR_{market}}$	Energy surplus sold by n at an OMIE-indexed price, at t .	kWh
$\delta_{n,t}^{SUP}$	Auxiliary binary variable to impede n from simultaneously buying and selling to the retailer at t .	-
$E_{n,t}^{PUR}$	Energy bought locally by n , at t .	kWh
$E_{n,t}^{SALE}$	Energy sold locally by n , at t .	kWh
$E_{n,t}^{CMET}$	Net consumption at meter n , at t .	kWh
$E_{n,t}^{SLC}$	Energy self-consumed by n , at t (in theory, g.t.e. that value).	kWh
$E_{n,t}^{CMET,+}$	Consumption at meter n , at t (in theory, g.t.e. that value).	kWh
$E_{n,t}^{ALC+}$	Consumed energy bought locally by n , at t (in theory, g.t.e. that value).	kWh
$\delta_{n,t}^{SLC}$	Auxiliary binary variable for defining self-consumed energy by n .	-

$\delta_t^{rec_balance}$	Auxiliary binary variable that is 1 if the ECn has surplus energy and 0 if it has deficit	-
$\delta_{n,t}^{meter_balance}$	Auxiliary binary variable that is 1 if meter n has surplus energy and 0 if it has deficit	-
$\delta_{n,t}^{coeff}$	Auxiliary binary variable for imposing positive allocation coefficients.	-
$P_{n,t}^{EXTRA}$	Extra power flow at the meter of n , beyond $\hat{P}_n^{CPE,max}$, at t .	kW
$\delta_{n,t}^{cmet}$	Auxiliary binary variable for defining $E_{n,t}^{CMET,+}$ when $\hat{\lambda}_t^{grid} < 0$.	-
$\delta_{n,t}^{alc}$	Auxiliary binary variable for defining $E_{n,t}^{ALC,+}$ when $\hat{\lambda}_t^{grid} < 0$.	-

Table 28: Objective function and constraints from Stage 2.

Objective Function		
$\min \sum_{t \in T} \left(\sum_{n \in N} \left(E_{n,t}^{SUP_{retail}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{retail}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell} + E_{n,t}^{SUP_{market}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{marketbuy} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{market}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{marketsell} + E_{n,t}^{SLC} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{grid} + P_{n,t}^{EXTRA} \cdot \hat{\lambda}^{EXTRA} + \sum_{s \in S} E_{n,s,t}^{B,D} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg} \right) \right)$	(10)	
s. t.		
$\sum_n (E_{n,t}^{PUR}) - \sum_n (E_{n,t}^{SALE}) = 0$	$\forall t \in T$	(11)
(general case)		
$E_{n,t}^{CMET} = E_{n,t}^{SUP_{retail}} + E_{n,t}^{SUP_{market}} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{retail}} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{market}} + E_{n,t}^{PUR} - E_{n,t}^{SALE}$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(12)
(Portuguese regulation)		
$E_{n,t}^{CMET} = E_{n,t}^{SUP_{retail}} + E_{n,t}^{SUP_{market}} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{retail}} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{market}} + E_{n,t}^{SLC} - E_{n,t}^{SALE}$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(12.b)
$E_{n,t}^{CMET} = \hat{E}_{n,t}^C - \hat{E}_{n,t}^G + \sum_{s \in S} (E_{n,s,t}^{B,C} - E_{n,s,t}^{B,D})$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(13)
$-P_{n,t}^{EXTRA} - \hat{P}_n^{CPE,max} \leq \frac{E_{n,t}^{CMET}}{\Delta t} \leq \hat{P}_n^{CPE,max} + P_{n,t}^{EXTRA}$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(14)
$E_{n,t}^{SUP_{retail}} + E_{n,t}^{SUP_{market}} \leq \hat{M} \cdot (\delta_{n,t}^{SUP})$ $E_{n,t}^{SUR_{retail}} + E_{n,t}^{SUR_{market}} \leq \hat{M} \cdot (1 - \delta_{n,t}^{SUP})$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(15)
$E_{n,s,t}^B = E_{n,s,t-1}^B + \left(E_{n,s,t}^{B,C} \cdot \hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,C} - \frac{E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}}{\hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,D}} \right)$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N, s \in S$	(16)
$\widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,min} \leq SOC_{n,s,t}^B = \frac{E_{n,s,t}^B}{\hat{E}_{n,s}^{B,N}} \cdot 100\% \leq \widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,max}$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N, s \in S$	(17)
$\frac{E_{n,s,t}^{B,C}}{\Delta t} \leq \hat{P}_{n,s}^{B,max} \cdot (\delta_{n,s,t}^{B,C})$ $\frac{E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}}{\Delta t} \leq \hat{P}_{n,s}^{B,max} \cdot (1 - \delta_{n,s,t}^{B,C})$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N, s \in S$	(18)

$\sum_{t \in T} \left(E_{n,t}^{SUP_{retail}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{retail}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell} + E_{n,t}^{SUP_{market}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{market_{buy}} - E_{n,t}^{SUR_{market}} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{market_{sell}} + E_{n,t}^{SLC} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{grid} + (E_{n,t}^{PUR} - E_{n,t}^{SALE}) \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{p2p} + P_{n,t}^{EXTRA} \cdot \hat{\lambda}^{EXTRA} + \sum_{s \in S} E_{n,s,t}^{B,D} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg} \right) \leq \hat{C}_n^{ind}$	$\forall n \in N$	(19)
$E_{n,t}^{CMET+} \geq E_{n,t}^{CMET}$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(20)
$E_{n,t}^{ALC+} \geq E_{n,t}^{PUR} - E_{n,t}^{SALE}$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(21)
$E_{n,t}^{SLC} \geq E_{n,t}^{CMET+} - \hat{M} \cdot (1 - \delta_{n,t}^{SLC})$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(22)
$E_{n,t}^{SLC} \geq E_{n,t}^{ALC+} - \hat{M} \cdot \delta_{n,t}^{SLC}$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(23)
$E_{n,t}^{SALE} - E_{n,t}^{PUR} \leq -E_{n,t}^{CMET} + \hat{M} \cdot \delta_{n,t}^{coeff}$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(24)
$E_{n,t}^{SALE} - E_{n,t}^{PUR} \leq \hat{M} \cdot (1 - \delta_{n,t}^{coeff})$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(25)
$\sum_n E_{n,t}^{CMET} \geq -\hat{M} \cdot \delta_t^{rec_balance}$	$\forall t \in T$	(26)
$\sum_n E_{n,t}^{CMET} \leq \hat{M} \cdot (1 - \delta_t^{rec_balance})$	$\forall t \in T$	(27)
$E_{n,t}^{CMET} \geq -\hat{M} \cdot \delta_{n,t}^{meter_balance}$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(28)
$E_{n,t}^{CMET} \leq \hat{M} \cdot (1 - \delta_{n,t}^{meter_balance})$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(29)
$E_{n,t}^{SALE} \geq -E_{n,t}^{CMET} - \hat{M} \cdot (1 - \delta_{n,t}^{meter_balance} + \delta_t^{rec_balance})$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(30)
$E_{n,t}^{SALE} \leq -E_{n,t}^{CMET} + \hat{M} \cdot (1 - \delta_{n,t}^{meter_balance} + \delta_t^{rec_balance})$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(31)
$E_{n,t}^{PUR} \geq E_{n,t}^{CMET} - \hat{M} \cdot (1 - \delta_t^{rec_balance} + \delta_{n,t}^{meter_balance})$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(32)
$E_{n,t}^{PUR} \leq E_{n,t}^{CMET} + \hat{M} \cdot (1 - \delta_t^{rec_balance} + \delta_{n,t}^{meter_balance})$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N$	(33)
$E_{n,s,t}^{B,C}, E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}, E_{n,s,t}^B, SOCB_{n,s,t}, E_{n,t}^{SUP_{retail}}, E_{n,t}^{SUP_{market}}, E_{n,t}^{SUR_{market}}, E_{n,t}^{SUR_{retail}}, E_{n,t}^{CMET,+}, E_{n,t}^{SLC}, E_{n,t}^{PUR}, E_{n,t}^{SALE}, E_{n,t}^{ALC+}, P_{n,t}^{EXTRA} \geq 0$	$\forall t \in T, n \in N, s \in S$	(34)

Note that some of the constraints below are the linear optimisation implementation (using the approach based on binary variables and large and small numbers) of the following conceptual constraints:

$$E_{n,t}^{CMET,+} = \max(E_{n,t}^{CMET}, 0)$$

$$E_{n,t}^{ALC+} = \max(E_{n,t}^{PUR} - E_{n,t}^{SALE}, 0)$$

$$E_{n,t}^{SLC} = \min(\max(E_{n,t}^{CMET}, 0), \max(E_{n,t}^{PUR} - E_{n,t}^{SALE}, 0))$$

Table 29 indicates the descriptions of the Stage 2 constraints.

Table 29: Constraints description.

Constraints	Descriptions
(10)	Arbitrage objective function
(11)	Overall sold positions equal overall bought positions per time step constraint
(12)	Equilibrium constraint
(13)	Net consumption constraint
(14)	Defines the extra power flow at the Meter (strongly penalised in the O.F.)

(15)	Impede simultaneous buying and sell from the retailer
(16)	BESS energy content update
(17)	BESS SoC limits constraints
(18)	BESS power limit constraints
(19)	Equal to or better than O.F. value from stage 1 constraint
(20)	Positive net consumption constraint (for determining self-consumption)
(21)	Positive allocated energy constraint (when bottom-limited by positive net consumption)
(22)	Self-consumption definition constraint (when bottom-limited by positive net consumption)
(23)	Self-consumption definition constraint (when bottom-limited by positive allocated energy)
(24)	Constraint for imposing positive allocation coefficients (maximum = $-E_{n,t}^{CMET}$)
(25)	Constraint for imposing positive allocation coefficients (minimum = 0)
(26)	Constraint for signalling when the ECn has a surplus
(27)	Constraint for signalling when the ECn has a deficit
(28)	Constraint for signalling when the meter has a surplus
(29)	Constraint for signalling when the meter has a deficit
(30)	Constraint for imposing that all injected energy must be allocated to other meters when the ECn has a deficit, and the meter has a surplus (lower limit)
(31)	Constraint for imposing that all injected energy must be allocated to other meters when the ECn has a deficit and the meter has a surplus (upper limit)
(32)	Constraint for imposing that all consumed energy must be allocated from other meters when the ECn has surplus, and the meter has deficit (lower limit)
(33)	Constraint for imposing that all consumed energy must be allocated from other meters when the ECn has surplus and the meter has deficit (upper limit)
(34)	Positive variables' constraints

4.5.1.1.2 Pricing mechanisms

As said before, the tool running in mode IC needs an internal price that can be computed according to several implemented pricing mechanisms such as:

- **Mid-market rate (MMR)**
 - A mechanism that considers the maximum selling ($\max_n(\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell})$) and minimum buying prices ($\min_n(\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy})$) for each instant t among all participating members n to compute the internal transactions' price λ_t :

$$\lambda_t = \frac{\max_n(\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell}) + \min_n(\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy})}{2}$$

When computed pre-delivery, it is not possible to select only those selling prices corresponding to the members that will be finally selling, and those buying prices corresponding to those members will be finally buying, for each time t . Only an estimation before dispatching the batteries is available and can be computed by selecting PARTIAL_MMR.

- **Supply and demand ratio (SDR)**

- A mechanism that considers a ratio between total supply $\sum_n(E_{n,t}^G)$ and total demand $\sum_n(E_{n,t}^L)$ within the ECn, to which the following logic is applied:

if $0 < \frac{\sum_n(E_{n,t}^G)}{\sum_n(E_{n,t}^L)} < 1$ then:

$$\lambda_t = \frac{\min_n(\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy}) \cdot (\max_n(\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell}) + \hat{\lambda}^{comp})}{(\min_n(\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy}) - \max_n(\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell})) \cdot \frac{\sum_n(E_{n,t}^G)}{\sum_n(E_{n,t}^L)} + \max_n(\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell})}$$

if $\frac{\sum_n(E_{n,t}^G)}{\sum_n(E_{n,t}^L)} \geq 1$ then:

$$\lambda_t = \max_n(\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell})$$

The possibility of considering a compensation factor, $0 \leq \hat{\lambda}^{comp} \leq \min_n(\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy}) - \max_n(\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell})$ is also possible by selecting a variant called **compensated SDR** or **SDRC**.

As for the MMR, when computed pre-delivery, it is not possible to select only those selling prices corresponding to the members that will be finally selling, and those buying prices corresponding to those members will be finally buying, for each time t .

Further information on pricing mechanisms in the context of ECn can be found in [37].

4.5.1.1.3 Flexibility bidding curves for ECn

Flexibility from distributed resources via local flexibility markets will play an important role in integrating renewable generation. An ECn can participate in these markets through an aggregator, bidding to profit from flexibility provision and support grid management.

To provide flexibility to a Distribution System Operator (DSO) that publishes its flexibility needs for a selected period in some flexibility market platform, an aggregator should build the appropriate bidding curves to manage market price uncertainty. To achieve this, aggregators can optimise the operation of their asset portfolio considering different flexibility expected prices and the sign and delivery periods of the flexibility requested.

In the BeFlexible project, a methodology for an ECn to build these flexibility curves was developed and described in [38]. This methodology will be fully integrated into OSTEC in the next ENPOWER

project phases. The methodology is based on modifying the original MILP to consider the incomes from providing flexibility given the price the flexibility is paid. The baseline from which flexibility provided is computed is the optimal behaviour without flexibility provision. Then, for each flexibility price, the new schedule of the flexible assets and the flexibility provided is computed, considering a tolerance to relax the compliance with the baseline for those hours where no flexibility is needed, to increase this way the flexibility provided for the requested hours. Then a set of discrete flexibility prices is used to build the flexibility curve.

Figure 45 from [38] provides a flowchart with the main steps used to build the ECn flexibility bidding curves.

Figure 45: Steps to build flexibility bidding curves (reproduced with authorization from [38]).

4.5.1.2 Current status (until M13)

During this first phase of ENPOWER project, two main developments have been performed to improve OSTEC functionalities. First, the flexibility of EVs has been considered in the ECn by developing the linear model and integrating it into the OSTEC MILP. Second, a similar approach has been followed with the EWH to integrate the linear model of the DT already described into OSTEC. With these improvements, OSTEC is now able to profit from the cross-sector flexibility (these types of loads provide flexibility that can be used in the scheduling) by computing the optimal schedule of the flexible assets and further reducing the ECn energy cost. The following section provides a comprehensive overview of these implementations.

4.5.1.2.1 Electric Vehicles

EVs are expected to become essential players in modern energy systems, particularly within ECns. By integrating advanced technologies and innovative strategies, the EV role can be further

optimised in energy management and contribute to the overall optimal behaviour of collective self-consumption structures.

Beyond bidirectional charging, V2G systems enable EVs to not only draw power from the grid but also feed energy back into it. This two-way interaction allows EVs to serve as flexible energy storage units, balancing supply and demand fluctuations in real-time, although with the need to comply with the user requirements in terms of time and expected EV charge level for its use. A smart charging algorithm can optimize EV charging schedules based on factors such as energy prices, grid demand and renewable energy sources availability. This can ensure EVs charge when electricity prices are favourable and maximise cost savings and environmental benefits. Excess energy stored in an EV battery can be directly traded with other agents in the same ECn. By embracing these cutting-edge technologies and strategies, the full potential of EVs can be unlocked as dynamic assets in the energy ecosystem, driving us closer to a sustainable and decentralised energy future.

The inclusion of EV into OSTEC is based on the following assumptions:

- We refer to DSO meters those used for metering and billing the energy behaviour of the members ;
- No operational grid constraints are considered, only contracted powers at the DSO meters;
- Each member can own an EV charger behind-the-meter;
- EVs can provide flexibility and change the net consumption profile measured at the members' DSO meters;
- EVs charging and discharging power are limited by EVs batteries, the charging infrastructure and the contracted power at the connected DSO meter ;
- Consumption profiles of all consumers are available, as well as the EV driving patterns, and the characteristics of the technology of the assets (e.g., efficiency, minimum and maximum battery capacity, etc.);
- EVs' chargers are bidirectional (electricity flows from the electric grid into the EV and vice-versa);
- EVs' chargers are available when they need to be used;
- EVs' batteries can assist members in trading with the community when prices are favourable, as decided by the optimization algorithm;
- The energy of each EV battery is properly tracked, considering, when not connected, the energy consumed for travelling jointly with the energy remaining from the previous period and the charge/discharge in that period when connected;
- A minimum SoC is established for each period.

4.5.1.2.1.1 Mathematical Formulation

To include the EVs modelling into OSTEC, the variables and constraints shown in Table 30 must be added to the mathematical formulation of sections 4.5.1.1.1.1 and 4.5.1.1.1.2.

Table 30: Indices and sets, parameters, variables and constraints from the EVs integration into OSTEC.

Indices and sets

$ev \in EV$	Set of EVs within each meter.	-
Parameters		
$\hat{E}_{n,ev,t}^{Trip}$	Vehicle ev at meter n energy consumption in period t .	kWh
$\hat{E}_{n,ev}^{EV,MinCharge}$	Minimum stored energy to be guaranteed for vehicle ev at meter n .	kWh
$\hat{E}_{n,ev}^{EV,BatCapacity}$	The battery energy capacity of vehicle ev at meter n .	kWh
$\hat{\eta}_{n,ev}^{EV,C}$	Charging efficiency of vehicle ev at meter n .	%
$\hat{\eta}_{n,ev}^{EV,D}$	Discharging efficiency of vehicle ev at meter n .	%
$\hat{P}_{n,ev}^{EV,ChargeLimit}$	Maximum power charge of vehicle ev at meter n .	kW
$\hat{P}_{n,ev}^{EV,DischargeLimit}$	Maximum power discharge of vehicle ev at meter n .	kW
$\hat{X}_{n,ev,t}^{EV}$	Whether a vehicle ev at meter n is plugged-in or not (if plugged-in = 1 else = 0)	-
Variables		
$E_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Stored}$	Energy stored in vehicle ev at meter n at the end of period t	kWh
$P_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Charge}$	Power charge of vehicle ev at meter n in period t .	kW
$P_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Discharge}$	Power discharge of vehicle ev at meter n in period t .	kW
s.t.		
$E_{n,t}^{CMET} = \hat{E}_{n,t}^C - \hat{E}_{n,t}^G + \sum_{s \in S} (E_{n,s,t}^{B,C} - E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}) + \sum_{ev \in EV} (P_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Charge} - P_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Discharge})$		$\forall t \in T$ (3)
$E_{n,s,t}^{B,C}, E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}, E_{n,s,t}^B, SOC_{n,s,t}^B, E_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Stored}, P_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Charge}, P_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Discharge}, E_{n,t}^{SUP,reta} \geq 0$		$\forall t \in T, s \in S, ev \in EV$ (9)
$E_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Stored} = E_{n,ev,t-1}^{EV,Stored} + \hat{\eta}_{n,ev}^{EV,C} \cdot P_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Charge} - \frac{1}{\hat{\eta}_{n,ev}^{EV,D}} P_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Discharge} - \hat{E}_{n,ev,t}^{Trip}$		$\forall t \in T \setminus t = 1; \forall ev \in EV;$ (10)
$\frac{1}{\hat{\eta}_{n,ev}^{EV,D}} P_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Discharge} \leq \hat{P}_{n,ev}^{EV,DischargeLimit} \cdot \hat{X}_{n,ev,t}^{EV} \cdot \Delta t$		$\forall t \in T; \forall ev \in EV; \hat{X}_{n,t}^{EV} \in \{0,1\}$ (11)
$\hat{\eta}_{n,ev}^{EV,C} \cdot P_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Charge} \leq \hat{P}_{n,ev}^{EV,ChargeLimit} \cdot \hat{X}_{n,ev,t}^{EV} \cdot \Delta t$		$\forall t \in T; \forall ev \in EV; \hat{X}_{n,t}^{EV} \in \{0,1\}$ (12)
$E_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Stored} \leq \hat{E}_{n,ev}^{EV,BatCapacity}$		$\forall t \in T; \forall ev \in EV;$ (13)
$E_{n,ev,t}^{EV,Stored} \geq \hat{E}_{n,ev}^{EV,MinCharge}$		$\forall t \in T; \forall ev \in EV;$ (14)
Constraints	Descriptions	
(10)	Battery balance for each EV. The energy consumption for travelling must be considered jointly with the energy remaining from the previous period and the charge/discharge period	
(11)	Discharge limit for each EV considering the battery discharge rate	

(12)	Charge limit for each EV considering the battery charge rate
(13)	Battery capacity limit for each EV
(14)	Minimum stored energy to be guaranteed at the end of each period

4.5.1.2.2 Electric Water Heater

Similarly to EVs, EWHs have also been integrated into OSTEC. Through a very reduced dataset, it is possible to carry out processes of optimisation of EWH’s functioning calendar. The objective is to estimate periods where it is possible to provide flexibility, by optimising the operation of the EWH, using only the appliance consumption data as input. For this purpose, only with EWH electrical consumption data, it is possible to determine the periods in which the EWH should start operating, guaranteeing (with some constraints), comfort levels defined by the consumer, while minimising the cost of operation or just the total consumption. The formulation for the EWH can be found in the section 3.2.1.1 and in D3.1 [39] of the ENPOWER project.

4.5.1.3 Input data description

This section outlines the input data necessary for running a simulation with OSTEC with the integration of EVs and EWH. Each potential participant's characteristics must be clearly defined, including consumption profiles, photovoltaic production, batteries, and other flexible systems. Additionally, retailer and grid access tariffs need to be specified. The characteristics and costs of shared assets and technologies must also be provided. Table 31 provides all the required inputs.

Table 31: OSTEC inputs.

Input	Description	Type	Unit
delta_t	Optimisation time step to be considered	Float	hours
e_c	Forecasted total energy consumption	Array	kWh
e_g	Forecasted total energy generation	Array	kWh
horizon	Time horizon of the optimisation (typically 24h)	Float	hours
id	An id that unequivocally identifies the Meter or member	String	-
l_buy	Opportunity costs for buying energy from the retailer	Array	€/kWh
l_extra	Fictitious value penalizing overstepping "max_p"	Float	€/kWh
l_market_buy	Market-indexed buying tariffs	Array	€/kWh
l_market_sell	Market-indexed selling tariffs	Array	€/kWh

l_sell	Opportunity costs for selling energy to the retailer	Array	€/kWh
max_p	Maximum admissible power at the connection with the grid (e.g., can be the contracted power)	Float	kW
degradation_cost	A fictitious cost in €/kWh that penalizes the storage usage	Integer	€/kWh
e_bn	The storage current or initial nominal capacity	Float	kWh
eff_bc	A fixed value, between 0 and 1, that expresses the charging efficiency of the BESS	Float	-
eff_bf	A fixed value, between 0 and 1, that expresses the discharging efficiency of the BESS	Float	-
init_e	The initial energy content of the storage unit	Float	kWh
p_max	The maximum charge/discharge power that can be set	Float	kW
soc_max	Maximum limit to the energy content	Float	%
soc_min	Minimum limit to the energy content	Float	%
trip_ev	EV energy consumption	Array	kWh
min_energy_storage_ev	Minimum stored energy to be guaranteed for vehicle	Float	kWh
battery_capacity_ev	The battery energy capacity of the EV	Float	kWh
eff_bc_ev	Charging efficiency of the EV, between 0 and 1	Float	-
eff_bd_ev	Discharging efficiency of the EV, between 0 and 1	Float	-
init_e_ev	the initial energy content of the EV	Float	kWh
pmax_c_ev	Maximum power charge of the EV	Float	kWh
pmax_d_ev	Maximum power discharge of the EV	Float	kWh
bin_ev	Whether an EV is plugged-in or not (if plugged-in = 1 else = 0)	Bool	-
c_ind	Float with the individual cost with energy for the optimisation horizon; positive values are costs, and negative values are profits. Note: this input is just for Stage 2	Float	€

4.5.1.4 Output data description

Here, the outputs of a simulation are presented. The operation of each asset in the ECn is defined, including the charging and discharging profiles for flexible resources like batteries and EVs.

Additionally, the tool provides information on the energy shared between members (or within the community) and the members' bills. Table 32 provides the main outputs for both stages.

Table 32: OSTEC outputs.

Output	Description	Type	Unit
c_ind	Individual cost with energy for the optimisation horizon; positive values are costs, negative values are profits	Float	€
c_ind_without_deg	same as "c_ind" without the degradation cost	Float	€
c_ind_without_deg_and_p_extra	same as "c_ind" without the degradation cost and power limit violation cost	Float	€
c_ind_without_p_extra	same as "c_ind" without the power limit violation cost	Float	€
meter_id	string with the identification of the Meter or member	String	-
deg_cost	batteries' total degradation cost	Float	€
delta_bc	auxiliary binary values	Array	-
delta_sup	auxiliary binary values	Array	-
e_bat	energy content of each storage asset	Dictionary of Arrays	kWh
e_bc	charging energy setpoints for each storage asset	Dictionary of Arrays	kWh
e_bd	discharging energy setpoints for each storage asset	Dictionary of Arrays	kWh
e_cmet	net load consumption forecasted after using all resources	Array	kWh
e_sup_market	energy bought at market-indexed buying tariff	Array	kWh
e_sup_retail	energy bought at the retailer opportunity costs	Array	kWh
e_sur_market	energy sold at market-indexed selling tariff	Array	kWh
e_sur_retail	energy sold at the retailer opportunity costs	Array	kWh

milp_status	status of the optimisation problem; only non-error value is "Optimal"	String	-
obj_value	value obtained for the objective function under an optimal solution of the MILP	Float	€
p_extra	extra power consumed (positive) or injected (negative) beyond the maximum admissible power limit at the connection point with the grid	Array	kW
p_extra_cost	total power limit violation cost	Float	€
soc_bat	State-of-Charge of each storage asset	Dictionary of Arrays	%
ev_stored	EV energy content	Dictionary of Arrays	kWh
p_ev_charge	EV charged power	Dictionary of Arrays	kW
p_ev_discharge	EV discharged power	Dictionary of Arrays	kW

In addition to the outputs present in Table 32, if the second stage is run, some extra output, described in Table 33, are also provided. Note that the term ‘pool’ can be replaced by the term ‘bilateral’ depending on the type of simulation used when using the SP OSTEC mode.

Table 33: OSTEC Stage 2 outputs.

Output	Description	Type	Unit
e_pur_pool	The scheduled total energies bought on the LEM	Dictionary of Arrays	kWh
e_sale_pool	The scheduled total energies sold on the LEM	Dictionary of Arrays	kWh
e_slc_pool	The self-consumed energies from the ECn	Dictionary of Arrays	kWh
e_consumed	The forecasted energy consumption from the retailer	Dictionary of Arrays	kWh
dual_prices	The market equilibrium shadow prices to be used as LEM prices	Array	€/kWh

4.5.2 Illustrative Example

4.5.2.1 Case characterization

This illustrative example features a simple ECn with two members to facilitate the understanding of the community dynamics and how minor adjustments in resources or set points can impact individual members and the overall community welfare.

Each member can own a behind-the-meter battery and a bidirectional EV charger. The EV battery can assist members in trading with the community when prices are favourable.

Simulations were conducted over 24 hours and will be expanded in future deliverables. This duration means the initial state of the battery and EV battery significantly influences the results. Various simulations were performed, including scenarios with and without EVs and batteries, to analyse different outcomes related to the objective function, individual costs and asset operating setpoints.

The .json file with all the input data, based on input data from the section 4.5.1.3, can be found [here](#).

For the optimisation, two meters, and two types of electrical assets (batteries and EVs) were predefined. In this illustrative example, the PV production is dummy data, and the patterns are complementary to better assess the interactions between the two meters. Figure 46 illustrates the scenarios built for these simulations.

Figure 46: OSTEC use case examples.

Based on this, four use cases were defined to demonstrate the results, as shown in Table 34:

Table 34: Use cases built to assess the OSTEC.

Use Case	Stage 1				Stage 2			
	Meter#1		Meter#2		Meter#1		Meter#2	
	Battery	EV	Battery	EV	Battery	EV	Battery	EV
1	x		x					

2	X	X	X	X				
3					X		X	
4					X	X	X	X

4.5.2.2 Results

This section will explore the primary results for each use case, focusing on energy trading with the retailer and the setpoints for batteries and EVs.

4.5.2.2.1 Use Case 1 - Stage 1 with batteries and without EVs

In the first scenario, each meter is just equipped with a battery. Figure 47 depicts the main OSTEC results of stage 1 when running in IC mode.

Without batteries, the results would be less compelling, as members would need to rely solely on the retailer for buying and selling energy. Both meters exhibit similar behaviour. When PV power is not available, they turn to the retailer to meet their energy demands. Conversely, when PV power is available, members use it to meet the demand, charge the batteries, and sell any surplus to the retailer (green line). Once PV power is unavailable again, the batteries discharge to supply the load, and the retailer resumes providing most of the required energy.

Figure 47: Stage 1 results with batteries and without EVs [(a) Meter#1 and (b) Meter#2].

4.5.2.2.2 Use Case 2 – Stage 1 with batteries and EVs

The analysis of the scenario with both batteries and EVs in Stage 1 reveals some notable differences. As can be seen in Figure 48, initially, the EV battery is 58% charged. Both meters use EV batteries before PV production becomes available. However, Meter#1 (a) first resorts to the retailer to secure the energy needed for trips. Interestingly, both meters fully discharge their batteries just before PV availability, allowing them to fully recharge once PV production starts. In the final periods of the day, Meter#2 (d) can use the EV battery again, thanks to its capacity to recharge during PV hours due to its higher PV production (b).

Figure 48: OSTEC stage 1 results with batteries and EVs [(a) Meter#1, (b) Meter#2, (c) EV Meter#1 and (d) EV Meter#2].

4.5.2.2.3 Use Case 3 - Stage 2 with batteries and without EVs

Examining the results from Stage 2 (see Figure 49) where P2P transactions (red line) are allowed, slightly different behaviours are revealed. For example, the batteries in Meter#2 (b) are charged only during the last period of PV production, as most of the surplus is sold to Meter#1. Some residual energy is sold to the supplier during peak PV production hours. In this illustrative example, the PV production patterns are complementary, with Meter#1 and Meter#2 alternating roles; when Meter#1 (a) has higher PV production, Meter#2 (b) purchases energy from Meter#1. Interestingly, Meter#1's battery discharges during periods of PV production to participate in P2P activities, contrasting with the previous scenario. In the final periods of the day, both meters primarily rely on the retailer to meet their energy needs.

Figure 49: OSTEC stage 2 results with batteries and without EVs [(a) Meter#1 and (b) Meter#2].

4.5.2.2.4 Use Case 4 -Stage 2 with batteries and EVs

In this final use case, the results from Stage 2 with batteries and EVs are depicted in Figure 50. Compared to the previous scenarios, there is a higher level of engagement in P2P activities due to the flexibility provided by the EVs. For instance, in the first period, both the EV and battery from Meter#1 ((a), (c)) are already discharging to supply their load and sell 1 kW to Meter#2.

Additionally, there are periods when it is more advantageous to buy from the other meter rather than from the retailer. As expected, like Section 4.5.2.2.2, the EV batteries are completely depleted since there are no minimum limits to be kept.

Figure 50: OSTEC stage 2 results with batteries and EVs [(a) Meter#1, (b) Meter#2, (c) EV Meter#1 and (d) EV Meter#2].

4.5.3 Further developments

Future work will include the following:

- New business models with shared assets. The goal is to review the existing different shared assets models in the literature and integrate the model that makes the most sense to be deployed in energy communities;
- Integration of storage systems degradation models. The goal is to review degradation models for energy storage systems and integrate simple models that do not create a significant increase in the complexity of the optimization model;
- New thermal resources, such as HVAC and heat pumps will be studied for integration;
- API development to access the service.

4.6 AI-powered virtual energy manager – WIS4Households platform

4.6.1 General Characterization

The WIS4Households platform is an AI-powered virtual energy manager developed by Watt-IS that translates energy-related data into insightful information and added-value services that foster energy efficiency and a better understanding of energy flows. Using smart meter electricity data collected by DSO, a load disaggregation service is triggered that quantifies the consumption of the main appliances at home and, consequently, generates automated and targeted energy efficiency measures that include appliance replacement, time-of-use habits, and optimisation of contracted tariff, contracted power, solar PV sizing, among others.

This tool delivers the relevant outputs in a web-based platform with a backend infrastructure that is connected to the smart meter data of the end users, thus only relying on DSO collected data supporting 15-min up to 60-min smart meter electricity data, depending on the specific country regulation. The solution adopts a white-label approach and ensures a fully responsive front-end making it suitable to be accessed in the screen resolution of the most common devices (smartphones, tablets, PCs, notebooks, etc.).

Figure 51: WIS4Households solution front-end in different screen resolutions (in Portuguese).

Figure 52 depicts the main building blocks that constitute the WIS4Households solution and that will be updated to incorporate Renewable Energy Community (REC) information to be made available in the Portuguese and Spanish pilots.

Figure 52: WIS4Households data flow.

The foreseen integration of the WIS4Households solution in the Spanish pilot must be aligned with CUERVA so that the data exchange mechanism for the DSO collected smart metering data can be established among the two parties.

4.6.1.1 Initial status

At the beginning of the ENPOWER Project, the WIS4Households tool was already in a commercial stage where the main features were developed and tested.

Below we present a more detailed description of the available AI-powered data analytics modules that enrich the information made available through the WIS4Households platform:

- Load curve and benchmark analysis:** We enable the platform users to analyse their consumption data for a given period and compare how much was consumed when compared to similar households. Figure 53 provides an example of the load curve and benchmark analysis.

Figure 53: Example of load curve and benchmark analysis within WIS4Household Platform (in Portuguese).

- **Non-intrusive load monitoring (NILM):** Our NILM module can quantify the main electrical loads at a given house only with the analysis of smart meter data (without requiring any additional CAPEX investments in smart plugs or higher resolution smart meters) and location-related information, such as zip code or geo coordinates. An example of the NILM analysis is depicted in Figure 54. The main loads that are identified and quantified for 15-minute resolution smart metering data are:
 - Standby;
 - Fridge/freezer;
 - Lighting;
 - Multimedia;
 - Dishwasher;
 - Washing machine;
 - Cooking;
 - Heating;
 - Cooling;
 - Water heater;
 - Water pump;
 - Electrical vehicle.

Figure 54: Example of NILM analysis within WIS4Household Platform (in Portuguese).

Additionally, on an optional basis, if the end-user provides metadata of the main electrical appliances they have in their house (as illustrated in Figure 55), the accuracy of the model improves. For example, knowing that the client does not have an electrical water heater, we will not quantify consumption for a water heater, thus 100% assuring the non-existence of a false positive.

Figure 55: Example of equipment metadata collection within WIS4Household Platform (in Portuguese).

It is also possible for the platform users to input information regarding their own house through a specific page, as illustrated in Figure 56. This information can also improve the accuracy of the data analytics algorithms and sometimes are required for the execution of on-demand optimisations (such as tariff, contracted power and solar PV optimisations).

Figure 56: Example of house metadata collection within WIS4Household Platform (in Portuguese).

- Energy efficiency measures:** Knowing the energy consumption of each appliance from the NILM module, as well as possibly having metadata related to the appliances, tailored energy efficiency measures are automatically generated ranging from appliance replacement (with quantified investment, savings and return period) to general energy efficiency measures. These are a significant way of engaging with the end users, as they can effectively benefit from the tool. Figure 57 provides an example of an energy efficiency measure.

Figure 57: Example of an energy efficiency measure within WIS4Household Platform (in Portuguese).

- Tariff optimisation:** This module is integrated with the targeted energy efficiency measures and provided as an “on-demand” tool that the end user can use at any time if it has enough historical data (at least 3 months with 80% data quality). The module goes through the prices of all available tariffs in Portugal (that are frequently updated in our database) and cross-check them with the consumption profile of the end user, then suggests the tariff with the lower associated cost, as exemplified in Figure 58.

Figure 58: Example of tariff optimization analysis within WIS4Household Platform (in Portuguese).

- Contracted power optimisation:** In Portugal, each electricity client has a contracted power with their utility above which they cannot exceed their used power from the grid. The higher the contracted power level, the higher the monthly cost. This module is integrated with the targeted energy efficiency measures and provided as an “on-demand” tool in which the end-user can check whether their contracted power is well dimensioned or not. Should the contracted power be significantly above the highest used power over a past period, then one can suggest a decrease in that contracted power, quantifying financial savings. An example of such analysis is presented in Figure 59.

Figure 59: Example of contracted power optimization analysis within WIS4Household Platform (in Portuguese).

- Solar PV optimisation:** Finally, this “on-demand” module allows the user to know the optimal PV solution for their consumption profile, quantifying the investment, savings

and return period. An example of the results of the analysis for PV introduction is presented in Figure 60.

Figure 60: Example of solar PV optimization analysis within WIS4Household Platform (in Portuguese).

Within the development of the project, it is expected that the WIS4Households will also be integrated with the Spanish pilot. Our load disaggregation algorithm has already undergone an adaptation to the Spanish energy consumption data, but the WIS4Household platform will require some fine-tuning. Primarily, a data integration process needs to be agreed upon with CUERVA as well as a translation of the platform and the existing Energy Efficiency measures to English or Spanish, as well as an update of the costs and characteristics of the main appliances in the Spanish market.

4.6.1.2 Current status (until M13)

The WIS4Households developments that have taken place are related to the data integration with the pilots, namely with CEVE clients. In fact, working jointly with CEVE (a regional DSO with around 10.000 clients), Watt-IS has already developed a data integration process with their data infrastructure where Watt-IS can in a secure way access CEVE's user data that is related to customer data and consumption data. Now we are persisting this data into our infrastructure and then we will be able to deploy the WIS4Households platform using this data infrastructure.

The integration with the data from Coopérnico's clients will be straightforward since their clients are supplied by the Portuguese main DSO, E-Redes. This data integration process is already done from Watt-IS side, requiring only an automated file transference process to be established so that Watt-IS starts to receive the energy consumption data from Coopérnico clients, as provided by the national DSO.

4.6.1.3 Input data description

The WIS4households platform requires a set of input data to run the algorithms. Table 35 establishes the parameters for the user metadata and DSO smart meter data. Table 36 provides an example of the user metadata in json. Table 37 and Table 38 provides examples of the consumption data required to run the services.

Table 35: WIS4Households user metadata and DSO smart meter data.

Type of data	Data description	Data format
User metadata	Description of the end user household, including energy contract, existing appliances, location, type of house, etc.	Json
DSO smart meter data	Time series with timestamp and electricity consumption value with the corresponding unit.	Json
DSO smart meter data	Time series with timestamp and electricity consumption value with the corresponding unit	SGL

Table 36: WIS4Households user metadata example.

User metadata .json example	
<pre>{ "equipments": [{ "equipment_id": 1582, "type": "fridge", "characterization": { "type": "combined", "efficiency_class": "E", "age_class": "less-than-5", "capacity_class": "301-400L" } }, { "equipment_id": 1583, "type": "dishwasher", "characterization": {</pre>	<pre>(...) "household": { "energy_contract": { "phase_system": "single-phase", "tariff_type": "bi", "tariff_cycle": "weekly", "contracted_power": "6.9", "vazio_price": 0.1498, "fora_vazio_price": 0.2251 }, "house": { "house_typology": "t4+", "house_type": "apartment", "construction_area": "125 - 150", "construction_period": "before-1960", "house_floor_type": "ground",</pre>

<pre> "efficiency_class": "D", "age_class": "5-to-10", "cutlery_capacity_class": "14" } }, { "equipment_id": 1586, "type": "washer", "characterization": { "type": "normal", "efficiency_class": "A++", "age_class": "less-than-5", "capacity_class": "9-kg" } }], (...) </pre>	<pre> "house_roof_slope": "horizontal", "house_energy_certificate": "E" }, "inhabitants": { "num_persons_btwn_16_25yrs": 2, "num_persons_btwn_35_65yrs": 2 } } } </pre>
--	---

Table 37: WIS4Households .json consumption data example.

Consumption data .json example
<pre> { "readings": { "A+": { "source": "load-profile", "unit": "kW", "type": "active-power-import", "readings": [["2024-04-02T23:00:00Z", 0.524], ["2024-04-02T23:15:00Z", 0.456],] } } } </pre>

```
[
  "2024-04-02T23:30:00Z",
  0.428
],
[
  "2024-04-02T23:45:00Z",
  2.104
]
]
}
```

Table 38: WIS4Households .jgl consumption data example.

Consumption data .sgl example												
0	CEVE	0081/6	12	11	1	20240401	20240501	2	253895	2	0	20240715
1	D	S	6	POTENCIA	K	15M	0	0	T			
4	A+											
20	20240401	0015	0.1	0								
20	20240401	0030	0.2	0								
20	20240401	0045	0.1	0								
20	20240401	0100	1	0								
20	20240401	0115	0.5	0								
20	20240401	0130	0.8	0								
20	20240401	0145	0.3	0								
20	20240401	0200	0.2	0								
20	20240401	0215	0.2	0								
20	20240401	0230	0.6	0								
20	20240401	0245	0.9	0								
20	20240401	0300	2	0								
20	20240401	0315	1.5	0								
20	20240401	0330	1.1	0								
20	20240401	0345	1.9	0								
20	20240401	0400	0.7	0								
20	20240401	0715	0.3	0								

4.6.1.4 Output data description

The WIS4Households platform has a set of outputs that have been already addressed. Thus, Table 39 summarizes the main outputs from the WIS4Households platform. The outputs for the NILM, energy efficiency measures, contracted power optimisation and tariff optimisation services are provided in Table 40, Table 41, Table 42 and Table 43, respectively.

Table 39: WIS4Households outputs.

Type of data	Data description	Data format
NILM	The load disaggregation values for each identified appliance for a given period	Json
Energy efficiency measures	Tailored energy efficiency measures that can be quantified	Json
Tariff optimisation	The result of the best tariff for the client	Json
Contracted power optimisation	The result of the best contracted power for the client	Json
PV optimisation	The result of the best PV system for the client	Json

Table 40: WIS4Households NILM outputs example.

NILM
<pre>{ "reading_time": "2024-06-28T23:00:00+00:00", "nilm": { "consumption_Wh": { "total": 223000, "rop": 28799, "t_avg": 0, "fridge": 54783, "cook": 41383, "white_appl": 6266, "cooling": 0, "heating": 0, "wheater": 0, "standby": 22359, "ev": 0, </pre>

```

    "lighting": 18029,
    "multimedia": 45112,
    "dishwasher": 2620,
    "washer": 3644,
    "water_pump": 0
  }
}
}

```

Table 41: WIS4Households output example related to energy efficiency measures.

Energy efficiency measures

```

{
  "ok": true,
  "result": [
    {
      "eem_type_id": 10001,
      "type": "targeted",
      "equipment": "fridge",
      "title": "Substitua o seu frigorífico combinado por um mais eficiente",
      "text": "Se substituir o seu frigorífico combinado por um mais eficiente de classe energética A++, poderá atingir poupanças de cerca de 113 €. Assumindo um custo de 410 €, poderá ter o retorno do seu investimento em 3.6 ano(s)",
      "action": "replace",
      "estimated_investment_euros": "410",
      "estimated_payback_time": "3.6",
      "estimated_annual_financial_savings": "113",
      "estimated_annual_energy_savings_kwh": "614",
      "seasonable": false,
      "retention_days": 7,
      "points": 30,
      "rank": 30,
      "adoptable": true
    }
  ]
}

```

Table 42: WIS4Households output example related to the contracted power optimisation.

Contracted power optimisation
<pre>{ "ok": true, "data": { "max_W": 4252.0, "current_kVA": 10.35, "new_kVA": 5.75, "annual_savings": 55.0 } }</pre>

Table 43: WIS4Households output example for tariff optimisation.

Tariff optimisation
<pre>{ "ok": true, "data": { "name": "Casa & Estrada Eletricidade Verde & Combustível (com DD) - Novos clientes", "type": "Bi-horária", "provider": "GALP ENERGIA", "quality": 68, "annual_price": 63.17, "annual_savings": 37.04 } }</pre>

4.6.2 Further developments

The next steps for WIS4households concern the data integration Exchange mechanism with Coopérnico’s clients, which should not be a significant challenge since Watt-IS has already implemented a complete integration process with the national DSO (that supports all Coopernico clients) and the data to be exchanged will follow the same data formats and processes.

The required back-end and front-end infrastructure will be set up by Watt-IS to support both CEVE and Coopérnico’s clients where WIS4Households will be made accessible throughout the pilot period.

Furthermore, the WIS4Households will be upgraded to incorporate and show its users data related to the participation in RECs such as energy received from the community or shared with the community, among others. For that, Watt-IS will also integrate it with our proprietary REC

management platform (WIS4Communities), which aims to support the activities of entities that manage several RECs and allow for different roles in the REC. It will allow entities to manage their energy and financial flows and will help to optimise the sharing coefficients for general optimisation of the community and allow for the creation or simulation of local energy markets.

Finally, a demand response layer will be integrated that will make it possible to control the user's specific energy loads (water heaters, water pumps, electrical heaters, etc.) and will provide the capacity to aggregate these flexible loads within a REC environment to respond to specific DSO requests such as foreseen grid constraints.

4.7 Nudging Apps for near real time closed loop consumers activation

4.7.1 General Characterization

The Power Seller Nudging Application offers a solution for optimizing energy production and encourages behavioural changes in communities. By providing personalized tips and tracking user responses, it enhances user involvement and community energy efficiency. This innovative tool acts as a key source of information, offering valuable insights into energy production and consumption. Its main advantage is delivering personalized energy production recommendations, helping users make informed choices based on past and predicted data. Additionally, the app promotes better community energy management by encouraging individual actions in response to changing energy situations. By analysing user interactions and increasing community engagement, the Power Seller Nudging Application not only enhances efficiency but also fosters a more responsive and sustainable energy system.

Figure 61 shows an architectural diagram of the Nudging App. The Power Seller Nudging Application backend will serve as the centre for data processing and management. It is integrated with different data sources and interfaces such as the EDA portal, which allows for the collection of smart meter data from users. Also, the backend receives forecasts from energy and weather forecasting services. Nudging recommendations will be displayed via the Power Seller Nudging Application frontend, which also acts as a feedback channel for gathering user responses to the nudging interventions.

Figure 61: Architectural diagram of the Power Seller Nudging Application with connected services.

4.7.1.1 Initial status

At the initial stage, the power seller nudging application operates as a basic prototype with limited features. It is capable of displaying individual consumption and production data and forecasting individual energy usage and generation. Additionally, weather forecasts are integrated into the energy forecasts. However, at this stage of development, the energy community, which participants are part of, is simulated. The nudging recommendations presented are calculated based on the virtual energy community. This prototype does not yet incorporate nudging signals from real energy communities, the OurPower P2P platform, or cascading energy communities within the platform.

4.7.1.2 Current status (until M13)

At the current state of this project, new frontend designs were started. Additionally, innovative methods to increase user engagement and responsiveness to nudging mechanisms are conceptualized and visualized now. Future iterations of the nudging application should incorporate non-financial incentives, such as reward points and achievement badges for specific interaction milestones, to further promote user participation.

In addition, materials and methods to support Power Sellers in their active engagement are constantly being developed and tested in a co-creation process. These materials and methods are intended to support low-threshold activation.

4.7.1.3 *Input data description*

Input data includes:

- **Energy production data:** Information about the historic and forecasted energy generation from PV systems;
- **Energy consumption data:** Data on historic and forecasted energy consumption by the community and individual users;
- **User preferences and historical responses:** Information on user behaviour, preferences, and previous responses to nudging to tailor advice more effectively;
- **Community event information:** Details about upcoming community dialogs and online events to be communicated to users.

4.7.1.4 *Output data description*

Output data includes:

- **Personalized energy production advice:** Specific recommendations for users to adjust their energy production based on historic and forecasted data.
- **Improved energy management:** Contribution to overall community energy optimisation by encouraging and facilitating individual actions in response to dynamic energy situations.
- **User interaction data:** Records of how users respond to the advice and interact with the app, which can be used to further refine the nudging strategy and improve the app.
- **Enhanced community engagement:** Increased user participation in community through direct communication and feedback opportunities within the app.

4.7.2 **Illustrative Example**

Figure 62 shows as an illustrative example of the initial status of the Nudging App including visual representations based on past and predicted data.

Figure 62: Illustrative example of Nudging Application (initial status).

4.7.3 Further developments

The next steps in the development of the Power Seller Nudging Application are:

- Finalize the new frontend designs (mock-up) and implement them;
- Setup the Power Seller Nudging Application backend;
- Implement new community interaction features;

- Integrate relevant services and systems.

4.8 Summary

This section outlines the tools developed to optimise the self-consumption of consumers (considering RES) and enhance the operation of energy communities across various configurations. The tools are categorized into two main groups: those designed for individual use and those focused on community-level optimisation, including collective self-consumption and energy-sharing models. Each tool is tailored to address the specific needs of the pilots involved.

The self-consumption optimisation tool forecasts and optimises both self-consumption and asset operation, which may involve load shedding or shifting based on individual consumption patterns. Using heuristic optimisation, this tool aims to minimise reliance on external energy sources and maximise self-consumption. The tool outputs a GUI that provides production forecasts, optimal energy consumption times, and load scheduling recommendations. It will also be integrated with the tool closed-loop optimal load control and intelligent monitoring of electric appliances for residential users. This allows users to specify typical usage hours for their devices, enabling the tool to suggest strategies for shifting or shedding loads, particularly for cooling, to improve energy efficiency and reduce costs.

The V2G-enabled flexibility management platform optimizes EV charging based on real-time electricity demand data from smart meters, weather forecasts, historical consumption patterns, and solar energy production data. The tool is developed to provide users with hourly guidance on when to charge their EVs. In addition, the platform can shift flexible EV charging during time intervals where RES production exceeds total demand. Thus, the service can advise users when to charge or discharge (if V2G is possible), aiming to maximize the user's benefit. For V2G mode, a credit system is available, which can be used by the users to charge their vehicle in public charging stations for free or redeemed for reductions in their electricity bill.

At the community level, the OSTEC tool was developed to simulate ECn operations, optimising energy use and facilitating P2P energy exchange among members. It incorporates flexible resources such as EVs, batteries, and EWHs. The tool operates in two stages: first, calculating individual costs for each member, and second, considering local transactions while ensuring that no member incurs a worse cost. Additionally, it includes pricing mechanisms to determine internal prices for the community.

On the WATT-IS side, an AI-powered virtual energy manager was developed to translate energy data into actionable insights, promoting energy efficiency. By analysing data from the DSO's smart meters, the tool offers users various recommendations, such as optimal contracted power levels, solar PV installation, tariff selection, and device replacement. These insights are delivered through a web-based platform.

Lastly, a nudging app was created to enable near real-time, closed-loop consumer activation. This tool optimises energy production and user behaviour by providing actionable insights based on past and predicted data, encouraging users to adjust their consumption patterns in response to energy signals. The app also leverages smart meter data, and users can provide feedback to enhance the tool's future responses.

5 Hybrid community-based flexibility aggregation mechanisms for consumer and communities integration into the electricity markets

5.1 Overview

This task focuses on developing a hybrid top-down/bottom-up virtual power plant (VPP) module for flexibility optimisation. The task is split into two subtasks according to the level of application:

- Subtask 5.4.1: Intra-community flexibility scheduling and trading;
- Subtask 5.4.2: Inter-community flexibility mechanisms and aggregation.

The subtask 5.4.1 aims to design new blockchain-based local markets with seamless automation and simplicity based on a post-delivery approach to avoid low liquidity situations. The market design integrates citizen's requirements, consumer preferences (financial and non-financial) and the local DSO as a potential buyer of DR products. The marketplace will be compliant with Energy Data Space in terms of data interoperability, privacy, and sovereignty. The main technological enablers supporting the development of the marketplaces in the task are TE-15 Blockchain-based hybrid coalition-based flexibility aggregation tool, TE-16 P2P digital tools and platforms for consumer activation and social engagement and TE-17 P2P energy markets designs and algorithms.

The subtask 5.4.2 aims to provide mechanisms to aggregate the flexibility from independent energy communities as a VPP for the participation in energy and ancillary services markets. Each community should be able to participate in the national energy markets by incorporating stream revenues from these markets while competing with local flexibility services. The resulting mechanisms will enable the offering of aggregated local flexibility to the energy markets. An automated cross-sector scheduling will be built on top of the resulting tools and the aggregation of local RES surplus will be implemented to enable exposing it to the wholesale electricity market.

5.2 Blockchain-based hybrid coalition-based flexibility aggregation tool

5.2.1 General Characterization

This technology enabler consists of two separate contributions from past projects such as H2020 PHOENIX [40] and after the change in the beneficiary structure, the other part of technology enabler is provided by current and past development of a new project partner DST.

The technology enabler consists of two parts. First part is a collection of blockchain tools for community flexibility aggregation and Virtual Power Plant (VPP) operations. The second part is a blockchain-based solution for traceable privacy and confidentiality protection. This solution manages rules, policies and control interfaces for automated demand response operation.

5.2.1.1 Initial status

In the project H2020 PHOENIX [40] a block of components called Privacy Protection Enforcement (PPE) was developed. The PPE components have the following objectives:

- To ensure the preservation of privacy for any personal data involved in the project, provide a set of features for personal data management (compliant with GDPR);
- Provide mechanisms and related security protocols for cross-border information exchange without privacy violation, providing reputation-based mechanisms, notification functionalities and enforcing integrity and traceability by exploiting blockchain immutability features.

The tools allow personal data management in compliance with the current EU Regulatory Framework through smart contracts, notification and compliance rules and governance policies. PPE consists of two main components:

- Privacy, Reputation and Mutual Auditability (PRIMULA);
- Compliant Regulatory Data Exchange (CoreDEX).

The two components cooperate during the entire data lifecycle to enforce privacy protection. They provide complimentary features. PRIMULA is responsible for the data registration process and for the creation of signed consent between the data subject (DS) and data controller (DC). CoReDEX monitors data exchange and agrees or disagrees on data exchange based on the consent by granting or rejecting the permission to data exchange. CoReDEX components also track the data exchange process. CoReDEX also notifies involved parties regarding data access events and other privacy and data-related events.

When a new data is generated, a data is being registered in PRIMULA. A data registration object is being created and recorded on a blockchain. To allow access to the new data object, a consent object has to be created that contains an explicit consent given to the data controller (DC) or data processor (DP) by the data subject (DS). Upon a first request to access data by DC or DP, an explicit request for signing consent is sent to the DS. After the DS response, a consent object is created according to the outcome (consent given or consent rejected) and recorded to the blockchain.

CoReDEX listens for data access/exchange requests and in case of a new request checks the status of the consent for the selected data and DS-DC/DP pair. If consent is given to DC/DP, a permission object is created and recorded on the blockchain, and data access/exchange request is approved. For each data access, a log object is created and recorded on the blockchain. A class diagram of PPE objects is presented in Figure 63.

Figure 63: PPE class diagram.

The PPE component is built on top of the Secure and Persistent Communication Layer (SPC). The SPC layer is built based on GoQuorum blockchain technology and exposes the blockchain API to the PPE components over the PPE Quorum API interface. CoReDEX and PRIMULA components interact with the SPC by using a set of Smart Contracts (SCs) written in Solidity language. SCs are exposed to the PPE components over the PPE Quorum API interface so they can be invoked from outside of the blockchain.

PPE functionality is exposed to the project components over the central message broker which also acts as a transport layer between PPE components and the SPC layer. Message broker is implemented using RabbitMQ technology which provides secure transport with fine-grained routing between the components. CoReDEX and PRIMULA components expose their APIs to other project components over the message broker component. The PPE component and SPC layer are presented in Figure 64.

Figure 64: Workflow of the PPE component with SPC layer.

5.2.1.2 Current status (until M13)

In the first stage of the ENPOWER project, an initial conceptual design for the blockchain-based flexibility marketplace was proposed. The conceptual design includes both the main actors in the energy community and the functionality groups that cover the main groups of interactions inside the energy community related to flexibility aggregation and flexibility management.

There are four possible roles of actors that can be involved in the local flexibility market:

- **REC member:** REC member is a person owning or living in a household with or without flexible assets that is a member of the REC;
- **REC manager:** The person who organises and coordinates the activities inside the energy community is the REC manager. REC manager recruits new REC members, adds or removes REC members to/from the energy community and can also be a REC member.
- **Service provider:** The service provider is typically an energy retail company that provides the electrical energy to the REC members but can also be a DSO buying an aggregated flexibility from the energy community.
- **3rd party entity (external actor):** The last actor role in the proposed flexibility market is a 3rd party entity which is an external actor that can request specific data from the energy community. The data is being shared with 3rd party entities only by giving explicit consent by REC member or REC manager.

The functionality groups in the flexibility market are defined to cover contextually similar activities inside the flexibility market. The functionality groups are later transformed into smart contracts providing specific interfaces to the blockchain. The first group of functionalities is the REC management functionality group, which provides the basic functionality to create an energy community, manage REC memberships and register metering and flexible assets on the REC. Flexibility management functionality group provides means to share flexibility, to activate flexibility and to report activation results. The energy profiles management functionality group acts as a manager of individual REC members and aggregated REC energy profiles and settlements and the billing functionality group provides functionalities for requesting and

providing billing and settlements based on energy profiles and flexibility activation reports. There is also a disputes management functionality group providing interfaces to create and resolve disputes between the actors on the flexibility market. The last group of functionalities is data sharing management group which provides interfaces to external 3rd party entities to request and receive flexibility market data. The complete interaction diagram is presented in Figure 65.

Figure 65: Flexibility marketplace interactions.

Figure 66 presents the intended digital records, smart contracts and actors involved in the local flexibility marketplace. REC management functionality group is transformed into a smart contract that provides functionalities to create or update REC, add or change REC manager, add or remove REC members (join or leave REC) and add or remove smart meter to the REC member. Functionalities are connected to the digital records such as REC Manager, REC, REC Member and Smart Meter. Digital records are written to the blockchain, and the REC Management functionality group can be used by the REC members and REC manager.

The Energy Profiles Management functionality group is transformed into the Energy Profiles Management smart contract which provides functionalities to create an energy profile, update the energy profile, share the energy profile and read the energy profile. The digital records managed by the Energy Profiles Management smart contract are REC Member Energy Profile and Aggregated REC Energy Profile. The actors that can interact with the Energy Profiles Management smart contract are REC members, REC managers and service providers.

The flexibility Management functionality group is transformed into a Flexibility Management smart contract which provides functionalities to create and remove flexibility bids, request

flexibility activation, report flexibility activation and read flexibility activation status. The digital assets interfaced by the Flexibility Management smart contract are Flexibility Bid, Aggregated Flexibility Bid and Flexibility Activation Request. The actors that can interact with the Flexibility Management smart contract are REC Members, REC Managers and Service Providers.

Disputes are managed by the Dispute Management smart contract that provides functionalities to create disputes, resolve disputes and read a dispute. The actors that can interact with the Dispute Management smart contract are REC Members, REC Managers and Service Providers.

The last smart contract in the local flexibility marketplace is the Data Sharing Management smart contract which provides functionalities to create data sharing requests, accept/allow data sharing requests, reject data sharing requests, update data sharing requests and read data sharing requests. The actors on the local flexibility marketplace that can interact with the Data Sharing Management smart contract are REC Managers, Service Providers and 3rd Party Entities.

Figure 66: Digital records, smart contracts and actors involved in flexibility market.

5.2.2 Further developments

The first stage of development included the proposal and outline of the local flexibility marketplace design. In the following stages, the flexibility marketplace design will be further refined, implemented and integrated into the blockchain solution developed in T4.4. The next steps in the development process will follow as noted:

- Finalisation of marketplace definitions;
- Applying P2P energy market designs and algorithms (TE-17) in the marketplace definitions;
- Implementing marketplace on blockchain technology developed in T4.4.

5.3 P2P digital tools and platforms for consumer activation and social engagement

5.3.1 General Characterization

The OurPower P2P Marketplace is a service that matches electricity generated from renewable energy sources by its members with customers. The platform provides a comprehensive suite of services, including accounting, settlements, and contracting, in adherence to applicable legislation. This infrastructure supports nationwide P2P electricity trading utilizing standard market procedures, allowing for economic valuation and statistical load profiling without the necessity for real-time smart meter data access. The platform enables small and medium-scale producers to choose individual prices for their electricity and consumers have the opportunity to select their power suppliers and form communities for long-term price stability.

5.3.1.1 Initial status

The OurPower marketplace allows energy producers to share their energy with energy consumers within the OurPower community. Producers state how much electricity they offer on the marketplace and set the price for their produced energy on a range from 2 to 12 ct/kWh. After completing the online onboarding process the producers have various options to invite friends, family, neighbours or others to buy their electricity through the OurPower marketplace. Producers have access to a personal dashboard. Through this dashboard, they can monitor their sellings, change their prices and invite contacts. In the future, OurPower plans on extending this dashboard.

OurPower remunerates producers for all the electricity they produce, regardless of whether it is sold directly within the community or not. For the energy, which is sold directly within the community, producers receive their set price. For the energy which cannot be sold directly within the community, producers receive a variable monthly price that is based on wholesale prices.

Customers simply visit ourpower.coop and type in their postcode plus their estimated annual electricity consumption. After filling in this information, the marketplace generates an individual offer with 2 to 5 power plants located in geographical proximity to the inserted postcode. The offer usually includes electricity from solar, wind and hydropower plants to always be able to offer consumers 100% supply security. Consumers can also customise the displayed offer according to their liking. Power plants can be switched or the distribution across the different types of

generation can be adapted. Consumers do have access to a personal dashboard as well. There they can view their current energy suppliers, their prices, and personal data.

Consumers pay the price per kilowatt hour to the producers following the electricity mix they have set. OurPower does the billing and is responsible for the balancing of kWh, but not in terms of grid stability. In Austria, the balancing of energy production and consumption is done by balancing groups (not the DSO). OurPower cooperates with an energy supplier and therefore is part of their balancing group, but OurPower does not carry out the balancing itself. OurPower just provides enough energy in the marketplace. So, there is no forecast done on the P2P platform. In cooperation with the energy supplier, OurPower then takes care of the entire energy management process, such as changing the metering point from the previous electricity supplier to OurPower and so on.

In addition to the regular marketplace, OurPower also has a platform for energy communities which is currently in development. At the start of the ENPOWER project, the major function of this platform was the billing process of energy communities and the management of energy community participants. The platform could only be used by OurPower; external users could not gain access.

In this initial state of the marketplace were no other options for engagement between consumers and producers than the visualisation via the electricity relationship.

5.3.1.2 *Current status (until M13)*

For engagement between consumers and producers following features were implemented:

- **Power Plant Overview:** The Power Plant Overview provides comprehensive information on all power plants available on the OurPower platform. This section is designed to offer users detailed insights into the various power generation facilities, including their types, capacities, and power sellers. By presenting this information in a structured format, users can easily assess the available energy resources and make informed decisions regarding their energy consumption and engagement with the platform and the corresponding power sellers;
- **Power Plant Map:** The Power Plant Map visually represents on a map all the power plants available on the OurPower platform. This interactive map allows users to get a geographical overview of the power plants in their region. By zooming in on specific areas, users can identify nearby power generation facilities and power sellers, which can foster a personalized connection with the power sellers and energy sources in their proximity. This feature is aimed at enhancing user engagement by providing a tangible sense of the energy landscape and enabling more informed choices;
- **Family&Friends:** The Family & Friends feature empowers power sellers to set custom tariffs for selected individuals, particularly family members and friends. This functionality offers them a unique way to engage with their immediate social circle, providing special rates and incentives to their chosen recipients. By enabling personalized tariff settings, power sellers can strengthen relationships with their customers and encourage greater participation in the platform. This targeted approach not only helps in customer activation but also promotes a community-centric model of energy sharing and consumption.

Currently, a simulation tool for energy communities is in development, which is a powerful tool for exploring various scenarios regarding the composition and dynamics of energy communities. For individuals or entities interested in joining or founding an energy community, this tool offers valuable insights into the potential benefits they could gain. Users can simulate different configurations and assess how their participation would impact their energy savings, sustainability goals, and overall community benefits. Existing energy communities can leverage this tool to evaluate the effects of new members joining the community. By simulating the integration of additional members, they can analyse the potential changes in energy production, consumption patterns, and economic benefits. This enables energy communities to make informed decisions about growth and membership, optimising their strategies for enhanced performance and sustainability. Overall, the simulation tool empowers both prospective and current members of energy communities with the information needed to make strategic decisions, fostering the development of more efficient and resilient energy systems.

5.3.1.3 *Input data description*

OurPower marketplace:

- Energy consumption and production measurement data from grid operator;
- Producer and consumer data;
- Cost/price information.

OurPower energy community platform:

- Energy consumption and production measurement data from grid operator / EDA platform;
- Energy community settings, e.g., energy allocation (static vs. dynamic);
- Energy community member data;
- Cost/price information;

Simulation tool for energy communities:

- Energy consumption and production profiles of (possible) members
- Asset information, e.g., energy source type, peak power, storage capacity
- Energy community setting, e.g., energy allocation (static vs. dynamic)
- Cost/price information

5.3.1.4 *Output data description*

OurPower marketplace:

- Energy production and consumption billing;
- Optimal energy mix and offer based on individual settings, e.g., location and consumption.

OurPower energy community platform:

- Energy community billing;
- Visualization of energy flows inside the energy community.

Simulation tool for energy communities:

- Energy consumption and production distribution;
- Impact on individual and community energy costs and economic benefits;
- Sustainability and environmental impact;
- Recommendations for optimizing energy community composition.

5.3.2 Illustrative Example

This section contains some screenshots from the OurPower P2P marketplace and its functions. Figure 67 shows the dashboard for consumers to access information from the producers. At this mock-up, producers provide their offers and their specific information and motivation for participating in this platform. Figure 68 presents the geographical mapping of all producers available in the P2P platform in Austria. Figure 69 presents the mock-up of the Family & Friends function. Figure 70 shows the mock-up of a list of producers with specific filters selected by the user.

Figure 67: Page for offer generation for customers on the OurPower P2P marketplace (in German).

Figure 68: Map with all producers on the OurPower Marketplace.

Figure 69: Screenshot from new Family&Friends function (in German).

Figure 70: Overview of energy producers with filter options (in German).

5.3.3 Further developments

The next steps in the development include:

- Design and implementation of a simulation tool for the energy community;
- Integration of power seller nudging application with energy community platform;
- Add more functionalities to the platform, including engagement components for power sellers and more incentives to increase social participation and awareness

5.4 P2P energy markets designs and algorithms

This section relates to TE-17, P2P energy markets designs and algorithms of subtask 5.4.1. This subtask covers competitive DR products and P2P energy trading (TE-15, TE-16, TE-17) for ECns and aims to design new blockchain-based local markets, on top of the DLT/Blockchain/Smart

contracts tool developed by DST and ComSensus in WP4, with seamless automation and simplicity (e.g., post-delivery approach) to avoid low liquidity situations. The market design will integrate citizens' requirements from WP2/T5.1, consumer preferences and smart contracts with P2P information forecasting and sharing, and the local DSO as a potential buyer of DR products. These market designs will also incorporate sophisticated and non-financial consumer preferences, and they will be compliant with WP4 Energy Data Space in terms of data interoperability, privacy, and sovereignty.

5.4.1 General Characterization

INESC TEC has been developing algorithms exploring local energy and flexibility market designs with the corresponding clearing and settlement mechanisms according to different regulatory alternatives for self-consumption (demonstrated in operational environments in National Project Digital CER [41], and in international projects H2020 POCITYF [42] and InterConnect [43]).

In ENPOWER, it is expected to solidify the developed market designs and algorithms by integrating, adapting, and tuning the algorithms to the specificities of realistic environments, with a special focus on flexibility provision, agents' relationships, and balancing responsibilities.

TE-17 for Local Flexibility Markets (LFM) integration builds upon the post-delivery local energy market (PD-LEM) design and pricing tools of OSTEC, already described in the section 4.5.1.1.2. To integrate LFMs into the PD-LEM design, adaptations of the LEM no-delivery commitment algorithm are necessary to consider the commitment to the accepted flexibility peers' bids with the non-committed PD LEM bids, as it will be explained.

Figure 71: Functionalities needed for LEM and LFM integration.

Figure 71 shows some of the original INESC TEC functionalities developed, that will need to be adapted, and those that will need to be developed as new, as explained below:

- **Virtual BRP compensations tool:** new functionality based on the energy and flexibility markets integration proposal in [44], where LEM virtual peers are used to represent retailers and aggregators in the LEM, so that the imbalances created to the retailers by the local flexibility activation from the aggregator, can be compensated by automatic local energy trades. These transactions are bilateral transactions between the BRP virtual peers, and do not impact the LEM post-delivery pool clearing. They do, however, impact the computation of the Collective Self-Consumption (CSC) Allocation Coefficients (AC) so that energy is in fact allocated to the virtual peers in the REC. As far as we know, this is not currently allowed in the existing regulatory framework but responds to a claim from retailers and is compatible with USEF contractual model proposal. However, as also highlighted by USEF, other solutions are possible without a direct contractual relationship between aggregators and retailers in [45];
- **LFM bidding:** building upon two recently developed and published innovative proposals, the LFM bidding new functionality [38], a new functionality to build flexibility bids from aggregating the community resources. The community manager sends a bidding curve to the LFM relating quantities of available flexibility to price and, if activated, each individual resource will be remunerated for the service provided. In addition, it has to consider the possible CSC allocation rules [46], which may imply important adaptations of the OSTEC optimization algorithm. Indeed, the LFM bidding model must provide bidding curves that are compatible with the selected ECn CSC allocation rules;
- **LEM bidding functionality:** adapting the LEM PD-LEM bidding algorithm to also consider energy bids from resources that are committed to providing flexibility;
- **PD-LEM clearing functionality:** the PD clearing functionality must be adapted to consider not only the current post-delivery price-only bids, but also the quantity-committed bids from the activated peers in the LFM;
- **Settlement functionality:** this functionality has already been developed conceptually in [47] and must be upgraded to integrate the LFM transactions and the new LEM types of transactions [44], [47].

5.4.1.1 Initial status

Regarding the initial status, TE-17 departs from the following already developed algorithms and designs:

- The PD-LEM algorithm and design, which computes the transactions after delivery [48], as allowed by the self-consumption regulation with dynamic coefficients [35], [36];
- The settlement framework algorithm may be used to simulate and operate REC under CSC schemes and compute the compensations for the local energy sharing tariffs and local energy market transactions;
- The design proposal is to integrate local flexibility and local energy markets to resolve the imbalances and problems that the flexibility provision causes to the activated peers' retailers.

The PD-LEM has already been tested in some environments, and computes the transactions after delivery, as allowed by the self-consumption regulation with dynamic coefficients.

As Figure 71 shows, at each Interval Settlement Period (ISP), clearing is performed by building the aggregated supply and demand curves with the metered energies already consumed and

produced. For each meter, the price bids are based on its opportunity costs which are the buying tariffs from their retailer, and the selling prices to their aggregators, as shown on the left side of Figure 72. After delivery, when the meter measurements are available, it is possible to compute the aggregated buying and selling bidding curves, as the right side of Figure 72 shows, and clear the market.

Figure 72: Post-delivery LEM bidding design.

Regarding the settlement algorithm, a complete settlement framework [47] has also been proposed for settling REC transactions, fees and allocation of energy under different configurations, business models, and regulatory options.

Figure 73: Settlement framework structure.

The settlement framework, as shown in Figure 73, considers the allocation rules allowed by the CSC regulation, which is often operated by DSOs. These allocations define how much energy is supplied and consumed in each DSO meter after the community energy sharing.

The settlement framework is compatible with the general CSC regulation scheme in Figure 74, which is similar to some EU member states national rules, like Portugal, France and Spain, and according to the EU directives [49] and [50].

Figure 74: general CSC regulation scheme.

In CSC schemes, consumers may self-consume energy self-generated locally by other members. Every member must have a contracted BRP for energy consumed from the grid (retailer) or injected into the grid (aggregator). When self-consuming through the public grid, tariffs must be paid by the REC manager, who must sign grid usage contracts with the DSO or TSO. In Portugal, as in Figure 74, the manager is the one who is responsible for contracting an aggregator to sell REC aggregated surplus to.

The settlement framework was developed as a module of the INESC TEC RECreation platform for the management of ECn to compute the financial compensations corresponding to the REC LEM transactions, CSC tariffs, imbalances and other parameters. As in Figure 75, the Settlement Module may be called in different instances for different purposes, including for pre-delivery simulations and post-delivery compensations.

INPUTS	3 Post Fixed	6 Pre Fixed	4 Post Proportional	7 Pre Proportional	5 Post Dynamic	8 Pre Dynamic
alloc_method	External	External	External	Proportional	Dynamic	Dynamic
alloc_type	Either	Either	Either	-	-	-
resource_t	Local	Local	Local	Local	Local	Local
cpe_t	DSO validated	Local	DSO validated	Local	DSO validated	Local
resource_transactions	Required	Required	Required	Required	Required	Required
external_allocation	Required (from DSO)	Required (pre-defined)	Required (from DSO)	-	-	-

INPUTS	1 Post Adjust resource_t	2 Pre Adjust resource_t
resource_t	Local	Local
cpe_t	DSO validated	Local

Figure 75: Inputs and calling methods of the Settlement Module in RECreation.

Finally, TE-17 builds upon the already published design proposal to integrate local flexibility and energy markets to solve the imbalances that the flexibility provision causes to the activated peers' retailers. This proposal however only tries to solve a specific issue tackled in [51], which is the passive energy transfer problem between the Aggregator who activates a peer flexibility and the peer Retailer, who could not predict the flexibility activation.

Figure 76: Integrating LEM and LFM with virtual prosumers and CSC regulation.

In this proposal, virtual peers are used to represent Retailers and aggregators in the LEM so that imbalances created by local flexibility activation can be compensated by an automatic local energy transaction. These transactions are bilateral, between the BRP virtual peers, and do not impact the LEM post-delivery pool clearing. They do, however, impact the CSC AC computations so that energy is in fact allocated to the virtual peers in the REC. This proposal was only done

conceptually and its usage to solve not only the transfer problem, but to integrate LFM activations is part of TE-17 development.

5.4.1.2 Current status (until M13)

Two tools currently developed are to be considered in the TE-17 design:

- The LFM bidding tool [38], that computes the optimal REC flexibility for each flexibility price, sending the LFM operator a bidding curve relating flexibility delivery with price;
- REC optimisation tool [46], which optimizes the REC program considering the CSC allocation rules.

Both tools can be potentially combined in an LFM that is compatible with the REC CSC allocation rules. Both developed models are explained following.

LFM bidding curve model:

In this model, an aggregator runs a REC and uses the community’s assets to offer flexibility to the DSO through an LFM. As in Figure 77, the DSO has flexibility needs, sent to the LFM, which requires a bidding curve with how much flexibility can be provided at each price from the REC. A market clearing is done considering the DSO and REC inputs, and later the DSO requires the cleared flexibility.

Figure 77: Sequence diagram of the LFM bidding-curve and market clearing.

To find the bidding curve, the REC runs a two stages model as shown in Figure 78.

Figure 78: Overview of the process for computing the bidding curve.

In stage 1, the REC computes the optimal operation considering its assets, consumption and generation forecasts, and price signals, but without providing flexibility. This stage is necessary for two reasons. First, it defines the initial REC baseline, i.e., its aggregated optimal energy behaviour when no flexibility is requested. It also computes the member's energy cost to guarantee that in stage 2 the provision of flexibility at least reduces their individual cost.

Stage 2 computes the optimal operation of the REC with flexibility delivery, considering: a) the flexibility required by the DSO and the periods where it is needed, and the baseline tolerance for the periods when it is not needed, b) the set-points of the flexible assets from Stage 1, and c) a range of flexibility prices λ^{flex} to build the flexibility curve. For each λ^{flex} , an optimization problem computes the optimal flexibility to be provided, either upward (UpFlex) or downward (DwFlex). Note that, since this model uses the member's metered consumption as a reference, DwFlex refers to decreasing net consumption and UpFlex refers to increasing net consumption.

Regarding the stage 1, the objective function (1) minimizes EC's costs.

$$\min \sum_{t \in T} \left(\sum_{n \in N} \left(E_{n,t}^{SUP} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy} - E_{n,t}^{SUR} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell} + E_{n,t}^{SLC} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{grid} + \sum_{s \in S} E_{n,s,t}^{B,D} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

where, for each member $n \in N$, $E_{n,t}^{SUP}$ is the energy supplied by its retailer at the price $\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy}$, $E_{n,t}^{SUR}$ is the surplus sold to its retailer at a feed-in price $\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell}$, $E_{n,t}^{SLC}$ is the self-consumed energy which pays a grid access tariff $\hat{\lambda}_t^{grid}$, and for each BESS $s \in S$, a degradation cost $\hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg}$ is applied to each discharge $E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}$ to minimize unprofitable BESS cycles. Energy is traded internally in a pool-like market, as in (2).

$$\sum_n (E_{n,t}^{PUR}) - \sum_n (E_{n,t}^{SALE}) = 0, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (2)$$

where $E_{n,t}^{PUR}$ is the energy bought locally and $E_{n,t}^{SALE}$ is the energy sold locally. Equation (3) is the energy trade equilibrium constraint:

$$E_{n,t}^{CMET} = E_{n,t}^{SUP} - E_{n,t}^{SUR} + E_{n,t}^{PUR} - E_{n,t}^{SALE}, \quad \forall t \in T, n \in N \quad (3)$$

where $E_{n,t}^{CMET}$ is the metered net consumption of member n, where negative values mean injections to the grid. Equation (4) is the energy equilibrium constraint:

$$E_{n,t}^{CMET} = \hat{E}_{n,t}^C - \hat{E}_{n,t}^G + \sum_{s \in S} (E_{n,s,t}^{B,C} - E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}), \quad \forall t \in T \quad (4)$$

where both the load profile $\hat{E}_{n,t}^C$ and the generation profile $\hat{E}_{n,t}^G$ are fixed input parameters, $E_{n,s,t}^{B,C}$ is the energy charged by the s BESS of member n. Equation (5) limits the member's exchanges to their contracted power:

$$-\hat{P}_n^{CPE,max} \leq \frac{E_{n,t}^{CMET}}{\Delta t} \leq \hat{P}_n^{CPE,max}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{P}_n^{CPE,max}$ is the contracted power of member n. The energy of each BESS is tracked with (6):

$$E_{n,s,t}^B = E_{n,s,t-1}^B + \left(E_{n,s,t}^{B,C} \cdot \hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,C} - \frac{E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}}{\hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,D}} \right), \quad \forall t \in T, s \in S \quad (6)$$

where $E_{n,s,t}^B$ is the energy stored by the BESS, and $\hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,C}$ and $\hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,D}$ are the charging and discharging efficiencies. Their state of charge (SOC) is given by (7) and limited by (8), while (9) ensures the SOC is at 50% at the end of the last period.

$$SOC_{n,s,t}^B = \frac{E_{n,s,t}^B}{\hat{E}_{n,s}^{B,N}} \cdot 100, \quad \forall t \in T, s \in S \quad (7)$$

$$\widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,min} \leq SOC_{n,s,t}^B \leq \widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,max}, \quad \forall t \in T, s \in S \quad (8)$$

$$SOC_{n,s,t}^B \geq 50, \quad t = T_{last} \quad (9)$$

where $SOC_{n,s,t}^B$ is the SOC of the BESS, $\hat{E}_{n,s}^{B,N}$ is its nominal capacity, $\widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,min}$ and $\widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,max}$ the minimum and maximum SOC, and T_{last} is the last period of the optimization horizon set to one day. Charging and discharging rates are limited by (10) and (11), which also ensure the BESS cannot charge and discharge simultaneously (for example if efficiencies are neglected):

$$\frac{E_{n,s,t}^{B,C}}{\Delta t} \leq \hat{P}_{n,s}^{B,max} \cdot (\delta_{n,s,t}^{B,C}), \quad \forall t \in T, s \in S \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}}{\Delta t} \leq \hat{P}_{n,s}^{B,max} \cdot (1 - \delta_{n,s,t}^{B,C}), \quad \forall t \in T, s \in S \quad (11)$$

where $\hat{P}_{n,s}^{B,max}$ is the maximum input and output power of the BESS and $\delta_{n,s,t}^{B,C}$ is binary and equal to 1 when charging. Finally, (12) calculates the individual member's energy costs $C_n^{ind,1}$:

$$C_n^{ind,1} = \sum_{t \in T} (E_{n,t}^{SUP} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy} - E_{n,t}^{SUR} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell} + E_{n,t}^{SLC} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{grid} + (E_{n,t}^{PUR} - E_{n,t}^{SALE}) \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{p2p} + \sum_{s \in S} E_{n,s,t}^{B,D} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg}) \quad (12)$$

In stage 2, the objective function (13) minimizes the total cost of the REC including the incomes from providing flexibility:

$$\min \sum_{t \in T} \left(\sum_{n \in N} \left(E_{n,t}^{SUP} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy} - E_{n,t}^{SUR} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell} - E_{n,t}^{FLEX} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{flex} + E_{n,t}^{SLC} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{grid} + \sum_{s \in S} E_{n,s,t}^{B,D} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg} \right) \right) \quad (13)$$

where $E_{n,t}^{FLEX}$ is the flexibility to be offered, output of this stage, given an input flexibility price $\hat{\lambda}_t^{flex}$. All the other stage 1 constrains apply, except (4) which is replaced by (14):

$$E_{n,t}^{CMET-2} = \hat{E}_{n,t}^C - E_{n,t}^G + \sum_{s \in S} (E_{n,s,t}^{B,C} - E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}), \quad \forall t \in T, n \in N \quad (14)$$

where $E_{n,t}^G$ is the behind-the meter generation given by (15):

$$E_{n,t}^G = \hat{E}_{n,t}^G - E_{n,t}^{CURT}, \quad \forall t \in T, n \in N \quad (15)$$

where $E_{n,t}^{CURT}$ is the generation of member n curtailed to provide flexibility. Equation (16) computes flexibility provided by each member for the periods $t \in T_{wf}$ where it is requested:

$$E_{n,t}^{FLEX} = E_{n,t}^{CMET-2} - \hat{E}_{n,t}^{CMET-1}, \quad \forall t \in T_{wf} \quad (16)$$

where $\hat{E}_{n,t}^{CMET-1}$ is the metered consumption in stage 1. In the periods $t \in T_{nf}$ where no flexibility is requested, (17) and (18) apply a tolerance ρ_t so that the members can deviate from their baseline from stage 1, $E_{n,t}^{CMET-1}$, to increase its flexibility potential of stage 2 resulting from $E_{n,t}^{CMET-2}$:

$$\sum_N E_{n,t}^{CMET-2} \leq \sum_N \hat{E}_{n,t}^{CMET-1} + \rho_t, \quad \forall t \in T_{nf} \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_N E_{n,t}^{CMET-2} \geq \sum_N \hat{E}_{n,t}^{CMET-1} - \rho_t, \quad \forall t \in T_{nf} \quad (18)$$

Finally, (19) calculates the new individual costs C_n^{ind-2} of stage 2, and (20) guarantees they are lower than in stage 1:

$$C_n^{ind-2} = \sum_{t \in T} (E_{n,t}^{SUP} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy} - E_{n,t}^{SUR} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell} - E_{n,t}^{FLEX} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{flex} + E_{n,t}^{SLC} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{grid} + (E_{n,t}^{PUR} - E_{n,t}^{SALE}) \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{p2p} + \sum_{s \in S} E_{n,s,t}^{B,D} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg}) \quad (19)$$

$$C_n^{ind-2} \leq \hat{C}_n^{ind-1}, \quad \forall n \in N \quad (20)$$

Note that constraint (20) enforces that stage 2 does not increase the member's cost of stage 1, guaranteeing that all members benefit from the flexibility provision. Since the LEM price is defined from an *ad-hoc* mechanism, local trades do not necessarily reflect the true opportunity costs of the energy in the second stage, and this may limit the member's ability to share their flexibility through local trades, impacting the REC available flexibility and the bidding curve. This effect is illustrated in the case study.

Regarding the results, an example of the bidding curves is provided in Figure 79. Two scenarios are considered, one where flexibility is required during noon (11h to 13h) and another where DSO needs flexibility in the evening (19h to 21h).

Figure 79: Two scenario bidding curves results.

Positive flexibility values refer to increasing net consumption (UpFlex), for which the peers require a positive payment. Negative flexibility, on the other side, refers to decreasing net consumption (DwFlex), where, in practice, peers are paid to increase generation. As explained in the model equations, above, the flexibility provision comes from BESS operation and solar generation curtailment. The main differences between the two scenarios above are:

- During noon, electricity is in full generation in the solar PVs, so it can be curtailed to provide UpFlex at a lower price than the opportunity costs of consumption.
- At noon, also the BESS have more time to make use of the tolerance limits allowed by to DSO.

Considering these two main factors, the noon bidding curve is more flexible than the evening one, so more flexibility can be provided. To understand their impact on BESS operation, Figure 80 shows how the tolerance limits are used to provide flexibility.

Figure 80: REC operation within tolerance limits.

The black line refers to the stage one REC operation optimization. Within the tolerance limit of 1 kWh, i.e., the community can only deviate 1 kWh from the stage one operation, NF1_0.2 scenario (blue line) is the REC operation when subject to a positive flexibility price of 0.2 €/kWh during noon, and NF1_-0.2 is subject to negative flexibility price of 0.2 €/kWh. To provide UpFlex during noon, the REC must reduce consumption in the other periods, and to provide DwFlex it must increase consumption in none flexibility delivery periods.

This means that tolerance limits can significantly impact the REC bidding curve, as in Figure 80.

Figure 81: Impact of tolerance limits on REC operation.

CSC allocation rules in REC operation model:

In this model, a REC subject to different CSC allocation rules is simulated. Since these rules impact how energy can be shared among the community members, assets operation including BESS and the LEM transaction are impacted.

AC types are simulated by running a 2-stage optimization. In stage 1, each member optimizes its own operation, as if they were individual self-consumers, which is used as a reference for comparison in stage 2 to guarantee that no member becomes worse off. Stage 2 minimizes the CSC's costs. While the first stage is the same in all cases, the second stage is adapted to each AC type.

Regarding stage 1, the objective function (1) minimizes the individual costs.

$$\min \sum_{t \in T} \left(E_{n,t}^{SUP} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy} - E_{n,t}^{SUR} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell} + \sum_{s \in S} E_{n,s,t}^{B,D} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg} \right), n \in N \quad (1)$$

where, for each CSC member $n \in N$, $E_{n,t}^{SUP}$ is the energy supplied by its retailer at price $\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy}$, $E_{n,t}^{SUR}$ is the surplus sold to its retailer at a feed-in price $\hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell}$, and for each BESS $s \in S$, a degradation cost $\hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg}$ is applied to each discharge $E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}$ to minimize unprofitable BESS cycles. Equation (2) is the energy balance with the grid:

$$E_{n,t}^{CMET} = E_{n,t}^{SUP} - E_{n,t}^{SUR}, \forall t \in T, n \in N \quad (2)$$

where $E_{n,t}^{CMET}$ is the metered net consumption of n , where negative values mean injections into the grid. Equation (3) is the energy equilibrium constraint:

$$E_{n,t}^{CMET} = \hat{E}_{n,t}^C - \hat{E}_{n,t}^G + \sum_{s \in S} (E_{n,s,t}^{B,C} - E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}), \forall t \in T \quad (3)$$

where the load $\hat{E}_{n,t}^C$ and the generation $\hat{E}_{n,t}^G$ profiles are input parameters, and $E_{n,s,t}^{B,C}$ is the energy charged by the BESS. Equation (4) limits the grid exchanges to the contracted power:

$$-\hat{P}_n^{CPE,max} \leq \frac{E_{n,t}^{CMET}}{\Delta t} \leq \hat{P}_n^{CPE,max}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{P}_n^{CPE,max}$ is the contracted power of n . The energy of each BESS is tracked with (5):

$$E_{n,s,t}^B = E_{n,s,t-1}^B + \left(E_{n,s,t}^{B,C} \cdot \hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,C} - \frac{E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}}{\hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,D}} \right), \quad \forall t \in T, s \in S \quad (5)$$

where $E_{n,s,t}^B$ is the energy stored by the BESS, and $\hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,C}$ and $\hat{\eta}_{n,s}^{B,D}$ are its charging and discharging efficiencies. The state of charge (SOC) is given by (6) and limited by (7), while (8) ensures the SOC is at 50% at the end of the last period.

$$SOC_{n,s,t}^B = \frac{E_{n,s,t}^B}{\hat{E}_{n,s}^{B,N}} \cdot 100, \quad \forall t \in T, s \in S \quad (6)$$

$$\widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,min} \leq SOC_{n,s,t}^B \leq \widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,max}, \quad \forall t \in T, s \in S \quad (7)$$

$$SOC_{n,s,t}^B \geq 50, \quad t = T_{last} \quad (8)$$

where $SOC_{n,s,t}^B$ is the SOC of the BESS, $\hat{E}_{n,s}^{B,N}$ is its nominal capacity, $\widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,min}$ and $\widehat{SOC}_{n,s}^{B,max}$ the minimum and maximum SOC, and T_{last} is the last period of the optimization horizon (set to one day). SOC in $t = 0$ is set to 50%. Charging and discharging rates are limited by (9) and (10), which also ensure that the BESS cannot charge and discharge simultaneously.

$$\frac{E_{n,s,t}^{B,C}}{\Delta t} \leq \hat{P}_{n,s}^{B,max} \cdot (\delta_{n,s,t}^{B,C}), \quad \forall t \in T, s \in S \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{E_{n,s,t}^{B,D}}{\Delta t} \leq \hat{P}_{n,s}^{B,max} \cdot (1 - \delta_{n,s,t}^{B,C}), \quad \forall t \in T, s \in S \quad (10)$$

where $\hat{P}_{n,s}^{B,max}$ is the maximum input and output power of the BESS and $\delta_{n,s,t}^{B,C}$ is binary and equal to 1 when charging. Finally, (11) calculates the individual costs C_n^{ind-1} :

$$C_n^{ind-1} = \sum_{t \in T} \left(E_{n,t}^{SUP} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy} - E_{n,t}^{SUR} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell} + \sum_{s \in S} E_{n,s,t}^{B,D} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg} \right) \quad (11)$$

In stage 2, the CSC optimization in objective function (12) that minimizes the aggregated CSC's costs is runs for different allocation rules.

$$\min \sum_{t \in T} \left(\sum_{n \in N} \left(E_{n,t}^{SUP} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy} - E_{n,t}^{SUR} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell} + E_{n,t}^{SLC} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{grid} + \sum_{s \in S} E_{n,s,t}^{B,D} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg} \right) \right) \quad (12)$$

where $E_{n,t}^{SLC}$ is the self-consumed energy which pays a grid access tariff $\hat{\lambda}_t^{grid}$. Equation (2) is replaced by (13) to include LEM trades.

$$E_{n,t}^{CMET} = E_{n,t}^{SUP} - E_{n,t}^{SUR} + E_{n,t}^{PUR} - E_{n,t}^{SALE}, \quad \forall t \in T, n \in N \quad (13)$$

where $E_{n,t}^{PUR}$ and $E_{n,t}^{SALE}$ are the local purchases and sales respectively. The constraints (3)-(10) of stage 1 also apply to stage 2. In CSC, the self-consumption of a member is usually computed as in (14).

$$E_{n,t}^{SLC} = \min(E_{n,t}^{CMET}, E_{n,t}^{ALC}), \quad \forall t \in T \quad (14)$$

where $E_{n,t}^{ALC}$ is the total energy allocated to one member from all CSC injecting members $m \in N$, as in (15).

$$E_{n,t}^{ALC} = \sum_{m \in N} E_{n,m,t}^{ALC}, \quad \forall n \in N \quad (15)$$

where $E_{n,m,t}^{ALC}$ is the energy allocated from m to n , computed by applying the corresponding AC ($\alpha_{n,m,t}$) to the energy injected into the grid by m , as in (16).

$$E_{n,m,t}^{ALC} = \alpha_{n,m,t} \times \max(0, -E_{m,t}^{CMET}), \quad \forall t \in T \quad (16)$$

In this model, using fixed or dynamic ACs implies computing $E_{n,m,t}^{ALC}$ in different ways, which also has an impact on the LEM transactions, as explained above.

Fixed AC with self-allocation

The fixed AC $\hat{\alpha}_{n,m,t}$ are defined by the CSC prior to the energy delivery, typically at the CSC licensing time, and change only when members join or quit the CSC. In this work it is assumed that the CSC defined a simple AC pool-like rule $\hat{\alpha}_{n,t}^{init}$, where the proportion allocated to each member is equal, regardless of who is injecting, as in (17).

$$\hat{\alpha}_{n,m,t} = \hat{\alpha}_{n,t}^{init}, \forall n, m \in N, t \in T \quad (17)$$

The bilateral allocations $E_{n,m,t}^{ALC}$ are computed applying $\hat{\alpha}_{n,m,t}$ to (16). This implies that all members have energy allocated to them if members are injecting, regardless of whether they inject into the grid or not. Although some regulations avoid allocating energy to members injecting into the grid, as in Portugal, this work wants to assess if this could be reasonable or not, especially with BESS. Regulators can also set limits to the AC values to force the CSC to only allocate energy physically injected into the grid, which can be modelled with (18).

$$0 \leq \alpha_{n,m,t} \leq 1 \ \& \ \sum_m \alpha_{n,m,t} \leq 1, \forall t \in T \quad (18)$$

Finally, the bilateral LEM transactions $E_{m,n,t}^{SALE}$ and $E_{n,m,t}^{PUR}$ correspond to the bilateral allocations:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{m,n,t}^{SALE} &= E_{n,m,t}^{ALC} = \hat{\alpha}_{n,m,t} \times \max(0, -E_{m,t}^{CMET}), \forall t \in T \\ E_{n,m,t}^{PUR} &= E_{n,m,t}^{ALC}, \forall t \in T \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Note that, although the energy values of the LEM trades derive from the allocations, the pool-like price was set to the dual variable of (23). Each member's final cost is computed including LEM trades in (20) for all AC types.

$$C_n^{ind-2} = \sum_{t \in T} \left(E_{n,t}^{SUP} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{buy} - E_{n,t}^{SUR} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,t}^{sell} + (E_{n,t}^{PUR} - E_{n,t}^{SALE}) \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{p2p} + E_{n,t}^{SLC} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_t^{grid} + \sum_{s \in S} E_{n,s,t}^{B,D} \cdot \hat{\lambda}_{n,s}^{deg} \right) \quad (20)$$

Fixed AC without self-allocation

To avoid self-allocation of the energy injected into the grid for a member n , $\hat{\alpha}_{n,m,t}$ is adjusted with (21) while also defining that allocation from one member to itself $\hat{\alpha}_{n,n,t}$ is 0.

$$\hat{\alpha}_{n,m,t} = \frac{\hat{\alpha}_{n,t}^{init}}{1 - \hat{\alpha}_{n,n,t}^{init}}, \forall n, m \in N \quad (21)$$

Note that this still allows an injecting member to be allocated energy from others. Since implementing the constraints to guarantee that only consumers have energy allocated to them (as regulated in some MS), would require significant changes in the initial model, this was left for future research.

Strict Dynamic AC

The dynamic AC can be computed following any rule the CSC agrees, so that the local transactions determine the bilateral allocations $E_{n,m,t}^{ALC}$.

$$E_{n,m,t}^{ALC} = E_{n,m,t}^{PUR} - E_{n,m,t}^{SALE}, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (22)$$

where $E_{n,m,t}^{PUR}$ and $E_{n,m,t}^{SALE}$ are decision variables, representing the energy bought and sold bilaterally in the LEM, respectively. The pool market is enforced in all AC types using constraint (23) whose dual value is used as the LEM trade price.

$$\sum_{m \in N} (E_{n,m,t}^{PUR}) = \sum_{m \in N} (E_{n,m,t}^{SALE}), \quad \forall t \in T \quad (23)$$

To find $E_{n,t}^{ALC}$, needed to compute $E_{n,t}^{SLC}$ in (14), the members injection into the grid $\max(-E_{n,t}^{CMET}, 0)$ is added to the sum of all bilateral transactions with the other members in (24). This is necessary

to establish the members' ownership over the energy they inject into the grid, which can, then, be allocated to others through LEM sales.

$$E_{n,t}^{ALC} = \max(-E_{n,t}^{CMET}, 0) - \sum_{m \in N} E_{n,m,t}^{SALE} - E_{n,m,t}^{PUR}, \forall n \in N \quad (24)$$

The bilateral dynamic AC values $\alpha_{n,m,t}$ are found by using (22) in (25), and the pool-like AC $\alpha_{n,t}$ are computed by using (24) in (26).

$$\alpha_{n,m,t} = \frac{\min(0, E_{n,m,t}^{ALC})}{\min(0, -E_{m,t}^{CMET})}, \forall t \in T \quad (25)$$

$$\alpha_{n,t} = \frac{\min(0, E_{n,t}^{ALC})}{\sum_{m \in N} \max(-E_{m,t}^{CMET}, 0)}, \forall t \in T \quad (26)$$

To enforce the limits imposed by regulators in (18) the dynamic AC we call strict is used, and (27)–(29) are added.

$$E_{n,t}^{SALE} - E_{n,t}^{PUR} \leq -E_{n,t}^{CMET}, \forall t \in T \quad (27)$$

$$E_{n,t}^{SALE} \leq -E_{n,t}^{CMET}, \forall t \in T \quad (28)$$

$$E_{n,t}^{PUR} \leq E_{n,t}^{CMET}, \forall t \in T \quad (29)$$

Flexible Dynamic AC:

The goal of flexible dynamic AC is to allow CSC members to use their SUP to locally share the energy they do not inject into the grid. This can be done by allowing negative ACs by removing constraints (27)–(29), members are no longer forced to sell internally at most what they inject into the grid, and ACs can take negative values or be bigger than 1. Although allocation is no longer attached to physical injection, this does not imply that the CSC members are sharing inexistent energy, since constraint (13) holds. Any excess $E_{n,t}^{PUR}$ or $E_{n,t}^{SALE}$ values not met by the member's injections, given by negative $E_{n,t}^{CMET}$, are covered by trading with their SUP for $E_{n,t}^{SUP}$, or AGG for $E_{n,t}^{SUR}$. To avoid unlimited trading with the grid, a limit equal to each member's contracted power is imposed to $E_{n,t}^{SUP}$ and $E_{n,t}^{SUR}$.

The individual costs for each member and the total costs for the whole CSC, in each scenario, are provided in Figure 82.

Figure 82: Individual and total daily costs in each scenario.

Stage 1 leads to the highest total daily cost, 5.8€, as there is no collective energy sharing, and individual surpluses are sold to the grid. In Fixed-WSA, costs drop marginally to 5.7€, mostly because the CSC members inject into the grid and self-allocate part of their energy, reducing the benefits of using BEES, i.e., to reduce $E_{n,t}^{SUP}$. Since there is no self-allocation in the Fixed-NSA, P2P

trading from the BESS is more effective at reducing $E_{n,t}^{SUP}$ and total costs fall to 4.8€ (17% lower than in Stage1). With dynamic AC, LEM trades are not tied to predefined ACs values, and members have the freedom to operate the BESS and trade locally. The benefits are therefore more substantial, with even certain members having profits (negative costs). In the Dyn-strict case, the total daily cost drops to 3.1€ (47% lower than in Stage1), and it drops even further in the Dyn-flex case, reaching 2.9€ (50% lower than in Stage1).

BESS have a significant role in the CSC, since they can physically increase the consumption from or the injection into the grid, in many cases leading to bilateral allocations and LEM trades. To further analyse the behaviour of the CSC members in these scenarios, Figure 83 and Figure 84 display the evolution of the SOC of M4's BESS.

M4's $\hat{\alpha}_{n,t}^{init}$ is very high (0.4), meaning that 40% of the energy it injects into the grid is self-allocated back into the Fixed WSA, becoming $E_{n,t}^{SUR}$ and sold back to the grid at a lower price. The only time it sells locally to other members is at 9h, to increase M2's surplus revenue. Note that M2 is already injecting into the grid due to its own PV generation and the CSC is allocating even more energy to it. Curiously, at 10h and 11h M4's SOC increase since M3, with 0.3 $\hat{\alpha}_{n,t}^{init}$, is injecting considerably into the grid to generate surplus for M2, however, 40% of this injection also goes to M4.

Figure 83: SOC of M4 BESS in Stage 1, Fixed WSA, and Fixed NSA.

Figure 84: SOC of M4 BESS in Stage 1, Dyn strict, and Dyn flex.

In the Fixed NSA scenario, the no self-allocation rule completely changes the BESS operation incentives. Now, M4's BESS generates a surplus to M2, since it allocates more energy to it than M3 when injecting energy back to the grid. That is why M3's SOC reduces from 8h to 11h. In addition, this rule is more efficient and reduces considerably other members $E_{n,t}^{SUP}$, as seen in

Table 44, and consequently their costs (Figure 82). There is also an up-and-down pattern that is very clear in the next Dynamic Strict scenario. Since M4 buys energy from the grid at a reduced price, it has an incentive to arbitrage, obtaining gains from selling to others who avoid consuming at a higher cost.

Table 44: EC Trades with each AC Type.

Scenarios	M	Esup [kWh]	Esur [kWh]	Epur [kWh]	Esale [kWh]
Stage1	M1	6.69	0	-----	-----
	M2	11.86	3.31	-----	-----
	M3	13.85	0	-----	-----
	M4	8.52	1.10	-----	-----
Fixed WSA	M1	6.02	0	0.67	0
	M2	11.86	1.34	0.67	2.65
	M3	11.84	0	2.00	0
	M4	9.56	1.45	1.33	2.02
Fixed NSA	M1	2.52	1.53	5.69	0
	M2	5.37	4.07	10.56	3.31
	M3	0	0	16.11	2.26
	M4	35.03	0.82	2.95	29.74
Dyn strict	M1	1.23	0.00	6.26	0.80
	M2	1.18	20.55	29.58	1.67
	M3	0.44	0	23.05	9.65
	M4	54.19	0	0	46.78
Dyn flex	M1	0	0	6.69	0
	M2	0	20.70	30.91	1.67
	M3	0	0	13.85	0
	M4	57.20	0	0	49.78

However, in the Fixed WSA, Fixed NSA, and Dyn strict cases, constraints (27)-(29) are active and the only way to arbitrage is by physically consuming and injecting through the BESS, as it is clearly visible in the Dyn strict SOC. Arbitrage takes place during the whole set T, and not only between 9h and 11h. This work supposes zero BESS losses to increase this effect, but intertemporal arbitrage is unavoidable if members have sufficiently different SUP prices in a CSC, even for fixed AC. Using BESS to physically arbitrage in a non-intertemporal problem leads to a waste of energy and asset degradation. In the Dyn flex, where constraints (27)-(29) are removed, M3 and M4's BESS are constant. Since members can trade without physical leverage, BESS only needs to make use of the total CSC surplus, saving it to reduce CSC consumption after the sun has set. Table 44 shows how arbitrage significantly increases from Fixed WSA to Fixed NSA and it is even more

present in the Dyn strict and the Dyn flex, i.e., M4 buys from its SUP ($E_{n,t}^{SUP}$) to sell to M2 so it can sell to the grid ($E_{n,t}^{SUR}$).

5.4.2 Further developments

Regarding further development, and considering all the aforementioned algorithms and designs from Figure 71, this TE-17 is considering implementing the following developments:

- **Design level integration of LFM and LEM:** product specification, integration time-line, how do LFM active resources participate in LEM and adapt their bids;
- **Design level PD-LEM adaptations:** How to combine bilateral transactions from LFM and PD-LEM pool like bids;
- **Settlement framework:** It can be improved to consider behind-the-meter resources since ECn often has more complex structures inside the DSOs meters, i.e., several resources with internal REC meters associated with different owner peers. This adds significant complexity to the REC settlement, especially regarding how to transpose the CSC allocation rules that apply to DSO meters into resource-to-resource meters transactions. Note that this is needed, since different resources can be connected to the same DSO meter but belong to different community members, who may or may not have different needs for the energy resources.

5.4.2.1 Case characterization

TE-17 proposes to develop P2P energy markets designs and algorithms that covers competitive DR products and P2P energy trading (TE-15, TE-16, TE-17) for ECns which integrate citizens' requirements from WP2/T5.1, consumer preferences and smart contracts with P2P information forecasting and sharing, and the local DSO as a potential buyer of DR products.

Several algorithms already developed and in development can be combined to provide this integrated environment, which can provide:

- PD-LEM clearing and bidding algorithms integrated with LFM bids and activation. More than the PD-LEM, the ECn local market algorithms must adapt the bids from peers who are committed to LFM activation, since, contrary to all other participants, they have a delivery commitment equal to the flexibility requirement;
- The settlement framework and billing guide system to compensate for both PD-LEM and LFM products. The billing guide resulting from the settlement must consider not only the LEM transactions, but also earnings from LFM assets participations. For these assets, compensations for deliveries different than requested must be also considered;
- The use of virtual peers to compensate BRP cross imbalances, when different BRPs are involved in an asset's operation, being one the one who requests the flexibility and the other the supplier;
- An ECn to DSO bidding system integrated with CSC regulation, requiring both LFM product definition from the DSO and ECn LEM and assets operation rules. This tool will optimize the ECn operation to provide flexibility as required by the DSO. Money flows from the DSO to the ECn asset owners through pre-defined LFM rules and ECn to peer contracts.

In fact, Figure 71, in section 5.4.1 presents the best overview of the design map to be developed and how all of the aforementioned works combine to provide the integrated service.

Since TE-17 is essentially a design tool, fulfilling this document framework for modelling data, inputs and outputs as well as model results is inadequate. We believe this case characterization is sufficient to provide the toll development guide.

5.5 Summary

This section focuses on the development of a VPP for optimising flexibility. It is divided into two main components: one dedicated to creating a blockchain-based local market with seamless automation using a post-delivery approach, and the other focused on aggregating flexibility from independent energy communities to participate in energy and ancillary services markets.

The blockchain-based hybrid coalition tool for flexibility aggregation comprises two key elements: a blockchain tool for aggregating flexibility and a suite of solutions for privacy-preserving and confidentiality protection.

The P2P digital tools and platforms are designed to enhance consumer activation and social engagement by matching energy generated from RES with consumers. This tool provides a range of services, including accounting, settlements, and contracting, all in compliance with current legislation. Additionally, it enables P2P electricity trading without the need for real-time smart meter data. From the consumer's perspective, a dashboard is available that allows them to view details about their energy purchases, including the source, pricing, and personal data. A unique feature enables users to sell energy at different prices to family and friends, fostering greater user engagement. The tool also tracks and reports on the sustainable and environmental impacts of energy transactions.

Finally, the design and algorithms for the P2P energy market delve into exploring local energy and flexibility markets, focusing on market clearing and settlement mechanisms that align with various legislative frameworks.

6 Automated, privacy-preserving and interoperable Demand Response

6.1 Overview

This task deals with preparing integrated products to enable the deployment of secure edge-level solutions for the aggregation and management of devices participating in DR schemes, flexibility coordination within the energy community and flexibility coordination between the energy community, power grid and market.

The solutions are based on concepts defined in previous projects by Universal Security Gateway (USG) and Open Distributed Energy Resources Management System (OpenDERMS) combined and extended by the solutions and tools developed inside the ENPOWER project. The ENPOWER tools that extend the provided functionality by the USG and OpenDERMS are the API Gateway (defined and partially implemented in T4.1) and integration of tokenised marketplace from task T4.4 with community-based flexibility aggregation mechanisms from task T5.4.

API Gateway provides privacy protection and security mechanisms to the end user to give him/her control over the data access management which gives the user an insight into individual queries of his/her data and fine-grained data access control. A blockchain-based marketplace integration with mechanisms for community-based flexibility aggregation connects energy community members and provides tools to aggregate and expose flexibility to energy markets.

6.2 Universal Security Gateway

6.2.1 General Characterization

Universal Security Gateway (USG) is an edge software platform for secure and privacy-preserving energy consumption management and energy community management. The platform is designed to give energy community managers tools for creating an energy community, aggregate consumption and flexibility, remotely manage flexible assets and expose the energy community to the potential energy and flexibility markets.

The core of the USG platform mainly operates as a data storage unit. It contains at least one database system with relational database system functionality and additionally supports a time series database functionality for efficient storage of time series data related to assets and users. The core also contains other key components, such as message streaming and buffering service (Apache Kafka), message queueing system (MQTT), data pre-processing service, and API service exposing the data collected in the USG core system. Message queueing system together with buffering service acts as a main data interface between the USG core system and flexible and non-flexible assets. The data model of the data storage is designed to support energy communities with DR applications.

Components of the system that are crucial for flexible asset virtualisation and management are the asset interface services. Asset interface services are services developed as individual processes interfacing with flexible and non-flexible assets for data collection and asset control. Each type of energy asset needs its own asset interface service that acts as a main asset data collection and control interface. The asset interface service separates the actual data interface

from the data collection and control plane to simplify and standardise the interfaces between the USG platform and assets.

The next important part of the USG platform is a data API service that exposes all data collected in the USG core to internal and external services. The services that interact with the USG core system contain web applications for personal energy management, energy community management and various local optimisation services.

The most important part of the USG platform is the API Gateway with identity and access management (IAM). API Gateway and IAM are the components that are being defined in task T4.1 as a part of the privacy, security and legal compliance framework for energy consumer's data sharing and AI. IAM provides mechanisms to manage the energy community participants and gives tools to users to manage access to their data inside and outside the community.

Management tools and visualization of energy consumption are provided by the web application running on USG. It provides a clear presentation of the consumption parameters of the user or the whole energy community (depending on the role of the user) and provides the configuration panels to the user or community manager to manage the flexibility.

Part of the USG platform is the integration of a blockchain-based marketplace interface developed in tasks T4.4 and T5.4. This provides the integration with marketplace, where flexibility and energy can be exchanged and traded to provide flexibility service to the grid and enable users to increase the self-consumption of RES surpluses on a level of their energy community.

The final part of USG integration is an integration of interoperability tools and the potential integration of the IDS connector into the USG architecture. The architecture of USG is presented in Figure 85.

Figure 85: USG architecture.

6.2.1.1 Initial status

Originally, USG was a hardware and software platform for secure edge asset virtualisation developed in projects such as H2020 PHOENIX [40] and H2020 BRIGHT [52]. It was predominantly designed to provide an interoperable and secured gateway functionality to integrate various energy assets into cloud-based DR platforms. The hardware platform was based on a low-power ARM application CPU running Debian GNU/Linux with a limited amount of memory and limited computational capabilities, thus limiting the complexity of the DR application that can be deployed on USG devices.

Due to the limitations in computational power, the USG platform was changed from a software and hardware platform to a software-only platform for energy community management providing greater flexibility for deployment but with increased computational requirements for

the hardware platform used for deployment (typically mini-PC in case of local deployment or any form of GNU/Linux-compatible machine in case of edge or cloud deployment).

The initial development of the USG software platform was done as a part of participation in open call activities in the Interconnect project [43]. A platform supported deployment in an edge/cloud configuration and enabled the integration of smart meters into a data collection system. The pre-ENPOWER version of the USG platform did not contain the integrated IAM functionality but provided only a limited integration of Keycloak into the web application to provide basic authentication of energy community users that were added manually into the application using Keycloak's generic user interface.

USG platform at the beginning of the ENPOWER project supported smart meter data collection, load forecasting, giving recommendations to adapt consumption profiles, aggregating consumption and production and provided mechanisms for exposing flexibility to the DSO. The core system was designed around a compact data model that supported all interactions and activities expected in the small energy community.

Many functionalities of the USG platform were supported by the information provided by external information systems such as the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform⁷ for access to electricity pricing and grid status (congestion), Electricity Maps⁸ for access to information on CO₂ emissions produced by the electricity consumption/production and OpenWeather⁹ platform to access the weather data.

6.2.1.2 *Current status (until M13)*

6.2.1.2.1 *Containerisation*

The USG platform was initially developed as a group of standalone tools and services which made it difficult to distribute, duplicate or re-deploy. The first step in making the USG platform an integrated product is to deploy a secure edge-level solution for the aggregation and management of the energy community in an as automated way as possible. The components must be packed in a form that provides easy deployment on as many computational platforms as possible and potentially supports cloud deployments.

A technology that enables packaging, deploying, and running applications with all parts that the application needs (libraries and other dependencies) and can be shipped as one package are containers with the most popular solution being Docker.

The first assignment and extension of the existing USG platform was packing components into individual Docker images using Docker files and orchestrating them into a deployable solution using Docker Compose files. That enables an easy and almost plug-and-play deployment experience without the complexity of, for example, Kubernetes for cloud-based deployments.

⁷ <https://transparency.entsoe.eu/>

⁸ <https://app.electricitymaps.com/map>

⁹ <https://openweathermap.org/>

6.2.1.2.2 IAM Integration

The work done in T4.1 contributed to the overall USG architecture to protect users and their personal and non-personal data. Energy community application is connected to the Keycloak as an IAM provider to give energy community managers the tool to add and remove users from the energy community. When the energy community manager adds a new user to the energy community, it creates a new user account in the Keycloak which creates a new digital identity with a temporary password. The user gets notified about the new user account and is requested to set a new password in the first step after he/she logs in. After successfully logging into the energy community management application, the user gets access to his/her account page and personal energy management application interface. The energy community manager can now start mapping the user’s assets to the user’s account and therefore adding assets to the energy community.

6.2.1.2.3 API Gateway Integration

API Gateway provides security, privacy protection and access management capabilities to the otherwise unsecured application API. This gives control to the user to set who can access his/her data and for what purposes. The permission to access data can be revoked at any time, for any user and for any reason.

Protected resources are exposed via an unprotected API, which is secured by an API gateway with a privacy enforcement point (PEP) proxy (Envoy) in the data plane and tools in the control plane. The control plane includes an IAM system (e.g., Keycloak), a control interface, and auditing mechanisms.

External actors (clients) accessing data act on behalf of users (data processors, data consumers). The IAM interface allows data owners to grant and revoke consent for specific uses (e.g., data collection and processing), providing fine-grained control over resources.

When an external actor requests access, the PEP proxy verifies with the IAM provider (Keycloak) if consent has been granted. If authorized, the PEP proxy grants access to the resource. A diagram illustrating the API Gateway and system actors is presented in Figure 86.

Figure 86: Architecture of API Gateway solution.

Currently, the API Gateway solution is not yet developed completely and lacks many sub-component implementations. The current status of development and integration is that the Envoy proxy is deployed to function as a PEP proxy and permissions for resource access are granted by manually entering access rules in the Keycloak.

6.2.1.3 *Input data description*

Input data in the first version of the USG platform contain the main smart meter data, PV data, electricity prices, CO₂ emissions for the current energy mix on the national level and the weather data supporting the forecasting capabilities at the selected site.

Smart meter data for the single household or other kind of single active user contains two useful data channels that are being used in the USG platform: imported energy and exported energy. Both data sources are consumed in 15-minute intervals and represent the amount of imported energy from the grid in 15-minute intervals and the amount of exported energy to the grid in 15-minute intervals.

The next data source needed to support the functionality of the USG pre-aggregation platform is PV production data which can be sourced from a dedicated production smart meter or as an aggregated data source from the installed PV inverters. Typically, households with installed PV production capabilities do not have dedicated production meters, which are mostly installed in bigger community and commercial buildings.

An important data source for the estimation of energy expenses and a source for self-consumption and flexibility optimisation algorithms are the day-ahead electricity prices. The supplier of electricity prices is the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform¹⁰, where all the data for electricity generation, transportation and consumption for the pan-European market is collected on a national and regional level. Electricity prices inform the USG platform about the costs of electricity during the specific periods of a day on an hourly basis, providing an indication, of when it is beneficial to do some specific energy-intensive tasks and when it is better to increase self-consumption to optimise the energy expenses and consumption on a household level or a level of energy community.

Information on CO₂ emissions is useful for the platform to provide information about CO₂ emission produced by the user's electrical energy consumption and to provide information on CO₂ emissions reduction due to the self-consumption of locally produced electrical energy by renewable energy sources. Initially, in the prototyping phase, the CO₂ emissions were supplied by the Electricity Maps¹¹ platform but the source is now redirected to the internally developed CO₂ emissions estimation service to avoid the violation of the Electricity Maps licence. The CO₂ emissions are calculated for each hour for the selected country or grid region and are calculated based on the energy mix (energy sources) in the selected country and their estimated carbon intensity factors.

The final data source for the USG pre-aggregation platform is the weather data provided by the Open-Meteo¹² platform. The main parameters used in weather data are the outdoor temperature and Solar irradiation. Both parameters are used by the forecasting algorithms which produce PV production forecast and consumption forecast. Historical weather data are used for model fitting

¹⁰ <https://transparency.entsoe.eu/>

¹¹ <https://app.electricitymaps.com/map>

¹² <https://open-meteo.com/>

where the current weather data and weather forecast are needed for energy consumption forecasting. All input data sources are presented in Table 45.

Table 45: USG pre-aggregation platform input data sources.

Data source	Time frame
Smart meter data: imported energy	Most recent value (last 15 minutes)
Smart meter data: exported energy	Most recent value (last 15 minutes)
PV production data: exported energy	Most recent value (last 15 minutes)
Day-ahead electricity prices	24 values for the next day
CO ₂ emissions	Most recent value (for the last hour)
Weather: outdoor temperature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 24 values for the last 24 hours • most recent value • 24 forecasted values for the next 24 hours
Weather: Solar irradiance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 24 values for the last 24 hours • most recent value • 24 forecasted values for the next 24 hours

6.2.1.4 Output data description

The USG platform in its current form calculates and prepares many prosumers related parameters that are served to the user or community manager. It generates three groups of output data that are presented visually in the USG user interface: daily statistics, daily self-consumption and self-sufficiency, and daily prosumption graph.

The daily prosumption statistics section of UI contains the following information:

- Imported energy [kWh]
- Exported energy [kWh]
- Net energy [kWh]
- Cost [€]
- Revenue [€]
- Net revenue [€]
- CO₂ emissions [g]

Descriptions and mathematical formulations of individual statistics are presented in Table 46.

Table 46: Daily statistics and their mathematical formulation.

Item	Description	Formula	Unit
Imported energy	Amount of energy imported from the grid during the current day.	$E_{import} = \sum e_{import}$ <p>E_{import} – total energy imported from the grid e_{import} – vector of 15-minute values of energy imported from the grid for the current day</p>	kWh
Exported energy	Amount of energy exported to the	$E_{export} = \sum e_{export}$	kWh

	grid during the current day.	E_{export} – total energy exported to the grid $\mathbf{e}_{\text{export}}$ – vector of 15-minute values of energy exported to the grid for the current day	
Net energy	Residue after subtracting imported energy from the exported energy. It provides the information on excess local energy production.	$E_{\text{net}} = E_{\text{export}} - E_{\text{import}}$ E_{net} – net energy export E_{import} – total energy imported from the grid E_{export} – total energy exported to the grid	kWh
Cost	Cost of the imported energy.	$C = \mathbf{e}_{\text{import}} \cdot \mathbf{price}_{\text{energy}}$ C – cost of imported energy (dot product) $\mathbf{e}_{\text{import}}$ – vector of 15-minute values of energy imported from the grid for the current day $\mathbf{price}_{\text{energy}}$ – vector of 15-minute prices of electrical energy	€
Revenue	Revenue generated by the exported energy if it is being compensated.	$R = \mathbf{e}_{\text{export}} \cdot \mathbf{price}_{\text{energy}}$ R – revenue generated by the exported energy (dot product) $\mathbf{e}_{\text{export}}$ – vector of 15-minute values of energy exported to the grid for the current day $\mathbf{price}_{\text{energy}}$ – vector of 15-minute prices of electrical energy	€
Net revenue	Residue after subtracting imported energy cost from the revenue generated by the exported energy.	$R_{\text{net}} = R - C$ R_{net} – net revenue C – cost of imported energy R – revenue generated by the exported energy	€
CO₂ emissions	Emissions generated by the imported electrical energy.	$EM_{\text{CO}_2} = \mathbf{e}_{\text{import}} \cdot \mathbf{em}_{\text{CO}_2}$ EM_{CO_2} – CO ₂ emissions generated by the imported energy (dot product) $\mathbf{e}_{\text{import}}$ – vector of 15-minute values of energy imported from the grid for the current day $\mathbf{em}_{\text{CO}_2}$ – vector of hourly CO ₂ emissions for the current national energy mix	g

The next two statistics represent the self-consumption and self-sufficiency parameters of household prosumption. Self-consumption parameter represents the portion of locally produced

energy that was consumed locally and not exported to the grid. The higher the percentage of the self-consumption, the lower the amount of locally produced energy interfering with the grid. The self-sufficiency parameter represents the ability of a household to supply its own energy needs by local electrical energy production capability. Both self-consumption and self-sufficiency parameters are calculated on 15-minute intervals instead of a net-metering approach to give the user a realistic estimation of the household energy management performance and the size of the space for further energy management optimisations. Definitions and mathematical formulations for self-sufficiency and self-consumption parameters are presented in Table 47.

Table 47: Definition and mathematical formulation of self-sufficiency and self-consumption statistics.

Item	Description	Formula	Unit
Self-consumption	Share of locally produced energy that was consumed locally.	$\text{Self-consumption} = \frac{\text{self-consumed energy}}{\text{total energy produced}}$	%
Self-sufficiency	Ability of a prosumer to provide his/her own energy.	$\text{Self-sufficiency} = \frac{\text{self-consumed energy}}{\text{total energy demanded}}$	%
Total energy demanded	Total amount of energy demanded locally – total household consumption.	$\text{total energy demanded} = \sum (e_{\text{production}} - e_{\text{export}} + e_{\text{import}})$ <p> $e_{\text{production}}$ – vector with 15-minute energy production values e_{export} – vector of 15-minute values of energy exported to the grid for the current day e_{import} – vector of 15-minute values of energy imported from the grid for the current day </p>	kWh
Total energy produced	The amount of energy produced by the PV plant for the current day.	$\text{total energy produced} = \sum e_{\text{PV}}$ <p> e_{PV} – vector with 15-minute values of PV energy production for the current day (production) </p>	kWh
Self-consumed energy	Locally consumed locally produced energy.	$\text{self-consumed energy} = \sum \min(e_{\text{PV}}, e_{\text{consumption}})$ <p> e_{PV} – vector with 15-minute values of PV energy production for the current day (production) $e_{\text{consumption}}$ – vector with 15-minute values of local energy consumption </p>	kWh
Consumption	Vector of total consumption values with 15-minute intervals.	$e_{\text{consumption}} = e_{\text{production}} - e_{\text{export}} + e_{\text{import}}$ <p> $e_{\text{consumption}}$ – vector with 15-minute values of local energy consumption </p>	kWh

		<p>$e_{\text{production}}$ – vector with 15-minute energy production values</p> <p>e_{export} – vector of 15-minute values of energy exported to the grid for the current day</p> <p>e_{import} – vector of 15-minute values of energy imported from the grid for the current day</p>	
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6.2.2 Illustrative Example

To demonstrate the functionalities of the USG platform, we selected a household with a PV plant and a smart meter installed. The example provides the integration of smart meter data and PV production data into the core system, generating the statistics and presenting them to the user. In the later stages of the project, the USG platform will further provide integration of mechanisms for flexibility aggregation, sharing and trading and will extend the support on existing API Gateway functionalities.

6.2.2.1 Case characterization

The use case for the USG platform is positioned in the bigger house equipped with a smart meter and a PV powerplant. Input data is collected at a 15-minute interval to comply with the current standards for billing. As specified in the previous sections, the input data include smart meter data, PV production data, outdoor temperature and solar irradiance from the weather service, electricity prices from the ENTSO-E platform and hourly CO₂ emissions for the energy mix in the national grid estimated based on the production and exchange data from ENTSO-E platform.

All input data is consumed by the USG core component where the data pre-processing components reshape the data into the common data format and store them in the local database. The forecasting component takes historical smart meter, PV production and weather data to prepare a day-ahead prosumption forecast which is important for flexibility and energy consumption optimisation. The statistics component prepares the daily consumption statistics that are later presented on UI to the user. Those statistics contain imported energy, exported energy, net energy, energy cost, revenue, net revenue, CO₂ emissions, self-sufficiency and self-consumption. All those statistics are calculated for the current day (from 0:00 local time until the last valid 15-minute data update). A scheme of USG platform data flow and components is presented in Figure 87.

Figure 87: Diagram of data flow in the demonstration use case.

Limited selection of data sources is exposed over external data API which is protected by the API Gateway component integrated into the USG platform. The data on external API can be accessed just by the external users and external components/services that pose the explicit consent for data access that was signed both by the data owner/subject and data processor (external user). Each consent signing process starts with the external user requesting data over the external API. The data owner receives the notification about the new data access consent request and can give the consent and permission for the data access to the external user/service or he/she can reject it. The data sources available in the current version of external data API are presented in the Table 48.

Table 48: External data API data sources.

Data source	Description
/api/v1/data/history/today/prosumption	Electricity prosumption profile for the current day.
/api/v1/data/history/today/production	Electricity production profile for the current day.
/api/v1/data/forecast/today/prosumption	Electricity prosumption profile forecast for the current day.
/api/v1/data/forecast/today/production	Electricity production profile forecast for the current day.
/api/v1/data/forecast/dayahead/prosumption	Electricity prosumption profile for the next day.
/api/v1/data/forecast/dayahead/production	Electricity production profile for the next day.

6.2.2.2 Results

Results of the USG platform are presented in the user interface which the user can access by using the web browser, currently in his/her local network where the USG platform is being installed. The user logs in to the UI using his own credentials and gets access to the presumption and flexibility information related to his/her household.

The first section of the home page on the UI presents the daily presumption statistics such as energy consumption and production concerning the grid, costs and revenues related to the imported and exported energy and estimation of CO₂ emissions produced by the imported electrical energy. The first two sections of the USG platform UI are presented in Figure 88.

Figure 88: A part of the information panel for the user site with information on consumption statistics, including self-sufficiency and self-consumption and the revenue generated by the produced electrical energy.

The second section of the UI presents the self-consumption and self-sufficiency parameters for the current day and the last section of the main page of the UI presents the presumption profile for the current day with the forecasted presumption profile. The graph with presumption profile for the current day and the forecasted presumption profile for the current day that is presented in the third section of the main page on the UI is presented in the Figure 89.

Prosumption

Figure 89: A part of the information panel for the user site, where the forecasted load profile is compared to the actual load profile.

6.2.3 Further developments

The current state of the USG platform provides basic functionality to the energy community member to view the statistics and forecasts of his own energy consumption, energy production and energy flows concerning the energy grid.

In the following months the functionality to integrate the flexible assets will be implemented where selected smart flexible devices such as battery chargers and EV charging stations can be integrated into the USG platform and controlled based on the pre-set target schedules defined during the energy consumption optimisation cycles of the USG platform. Local flexibility potential will be estimated and shared with the energy community manager that can be later converted into a flexibility offer which can be shared within the energy community or traded on the flexibility marketplace.

The API Gateway functionality will be more thoroughly integrated into the USG platform, where the energy community management interface will be extended to provide more fine-grained control over the identities inside the energy community, their assets and control over the data access. The identity and access management will be integrated into the USG UI, where individual users can see and manage all the requests to access data. In addition, all previous data access events can be reviewed. The user will be able to revoke the individual data access permissions to manage and have control over his/her own privacy.

In the next stages, a flexibility marketplace will be developed inside tasks T4.4 and T5.4 and will be integrated into the USG platform to provide interfaces and mechanisms to share the local and aggregated flexibility and expose it to the flexibility markets and providers.

6.3 Open Distributed Energy Resources Management System

6.3.1 General Characterization

OpenDERMS was developed by EPRI as part of EPRI’s *Simulation Platform for Integration of DER (SPIDER)* Testbed¹³. OpenDERMS is a Distributed Energy Resources (DER) management system with the capability to aggregate, monitor, translate, and actively manage devices at a group or individual level. This application provides the user functions to monitor device states, deploy user-defined control logics, and communicate with devices via standard communication protocols. OpenDERMS is a web application built with Django, a Python-based web framework.

6.3.1.1 Pre-requisites

OpenDERMS requires a minimum set of software to run the tool. Table 49 lists the software requirements for OpenDERMS.

Table 49: OpenDERMS software requirements.

Software Package	Module Name	Source
Python version	Python 3	https://docs.anaconda.com/anaconda/install/ https://www.anaconda.com/products/individual
Additional packages	<i>Django</i>	https://anaconda.org/anaconda/django
	<i>bootstrap4</i>	https://pypi.org/project/django-bootstrap4/
	<i>crispy_forms</i>	https://django-crispy-forms.readthedocs.io/en/latest/install.html
	<i>polymorphic</i>	https://django-polymorphic.readthedocs.io/en/stable/quickstart.html
	<i>svg</i>	https://pypi.org/project/django-inline-svg/
	<i>rstr</i>	https://pypi.org/project/rstr/
	<i>requests</i>	https://pypi.org/project/requests/
	<i>Eclipse Paho MQTT</i>	https://pypi.org/project/paho-mqtt/

6.3.1.2 Architecture

The communication architecture followed by OpenDERMS is presented in Figure 90. The web application is accessible through a web browser. It utilizes one or more protocol driver agents (PDAs) to communicate with DER devices. The PDA receives the command messages from OpenDERMS and translates them to device-specific protocol messages. The PDA has the DER communication protocol information and converts the generic JSON commands from OpenDERMS to DER-specific messages accordingly. OpenDERMS communicates with the PDAs using the DER API, which exchanges messages in JSON format. The JSON messages consist of DER

¹³ Simulation Platform for Integration of DER (SPIDER): Testbed Software Manual. EPRI, Palo Alto, CA. 2022. 3002021858

configuration commands issued from OpenDERMS as well as DER status reports. In the other direction, the PDA receives the DER status using the standard protocols, converts them to simple JSON messages, and forwards them to OpenDERMS. The application is also capable of communicating with a DER controller using MQTT, from which it receives schedules of DER control commands.

Figure 90: OpenDERMS architecture overview for communications with DER.

6.3.1.3 Protocol Driver Agent (PDA)

The PDA is launched as a separate executable that acts as the bridge between the OpenDERMS application and the device layer. A PDA has its communication endpoint – the IP address and port – where it keeps listening for messages coming from OpenDERMS. Using JSON format, OpenDERMS sends API requests to the PDA consisting of information about the devices and the commands with its parameters. The PDA is responsible for mapping the device ID (MRID), constructing a message according to the device protocol with all the JSON information, and relaying it to the devices. The PDA then receives a return message from the devices, which it sends back to OpenDERMS in a similar JSON format. This return message contains the device status and is processed by OpenDERMS to update the status of the devices. Multiple PDA instances can be created with different port numbers in OpenDERMS.

6.3.1.4 Functionalities

Devices:

Users can create and configure DER device instances in OpenDERMS.

Groups:

OpenDERMS can group DER according to such characteristics as device type, location, and DER size. The user can send a group command to the selected group, and OpenDERMS will disaggregate the group command to the respective devices.

Projects:

The OpenDERMS application allows the user to load different projects and run each project for a given test scenario. Each project can contain a distinct set of DER devices and groups. The results of each test scenario are saved in a database, and the user can access them for post-analysis.

MQTT Communication:

OpenDERMS is capable of connecting with the MQTT broker and communicating with other co-simulation components by subscribing to their topics and publishing messages.

6.3.1.5 Control Algorithm

OpenDERMS has an option of sending group commands to the DER based on logics scripted in Python. This sandbox feature enables users to send schedules or define control logic to manage DER and send control commands automatically. The script can receive a grid service request to be disaggregated to a fleet of DER based on the service request and the logic defined in the script to optimally manage all the DER. Multiple algorithms in the sandbox can be defined, and the user has the option to test the effectiveness of each algorithm. The control algorithm is an advanced feature of the OpenDERMS tool. This feature allows the user to send automatic commands to the device layer based on schedules. These schedules are received by the OpenDERMS from the control algorithm client via an MQTT subscription. To use this feature, OpenDERMS must be connected to the MQTT broker and subscribed to the topics from the control algorithm client of the testbed.

When using the control algorithm, OpenDERMS provides the parameters listed in Table 50 to the algorithm. This information is provided in JSON format.

Table 50: Monitored parameters of DER sent from OpenDERMS to the control algorithm.

Parameter		Description
Sim_time		Simulation timestamp for which the following parameters are monitored
Devices	<mrid>	Unique DER ID
	ACTIVE_POWER_WATT	Monitored active power in watts
	REACTIVE_POWER_VAR	Monitored reactive power in VAR
	VOLTAGE_A_VOLT	Monitored Phase A voltage power in volts
	FREQUENCY_HZ	Monitored frequency in hertz

In the other direction, the schedule that the control algorithm provides to OpenDERMS includes the parameters listed in Table 51. The schedule is transmitted in JSON format.

Table 51: Setpoint parameters of schedules provided by the control algorithm to OpenDERMS.

Parameter	Description
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Sim_time		Simulation timestamp for which the following parameters are scheduled
Devices	<mrid>	Unique DER ID
	AP_MAX_P	Active power limit setpoint in percentage of the nameplate maximum power
	CHARGE_DISCHARGE_SETPOINT	Charge-discharge setpoint for energy storage systems (ESSs)
	CONST_PF	Constant power factor setpoint
	<mrid>	Unique DER ID

Instead of using the Python script, the schedule can be uploaded by the user in JSON file format. The JSON file will contain similar information, as presented in Table 51, and represents a complete schedule that needs to be followed by OpenDERMS.

Commands:

The user can configure the devices by sending different smart inverter function commands.

Monitoring:

Users can monitor the current status of devices including standard monitoring parameters such as: output Active Power, Reactive Power, and SOC. The values update automatically according to the PDA settings. OpenDERMS receives this information from the PDA at a certain periodic interval and updates the values.

6.3.2 Further developments

The OpenDERMS tool will be utilized to implement the DER management algorithms developed as part of the Irish pilot in the ENPOWER project. Existing DER management algorithms will be updated and adapted to manage the operation and controllability of the various DER and demand response devices present in the Irish pilot case. These developments are planned to allow OpenDERMS to optimize the operation of the controllable devices within the Irish pilot to maximise self-consumption within the energy community. With the updated control algorithms, OpenDERMS can be used for testing and verification Irish pilot use cases.

Further developments include:

- Configuration of OpenDERMS to manage controllable devices within the Irish Pilot;
- Development of DER/demand response control algorithm;
- Testing and verification of DER management in the context of the Irish pilot to validate use cases.

6.4 Summary

This section focuses on deploying secure edge-level solutions to enable device aggregation for participation in DR and flexibility schemes across energy communities, the power grid, and the

market. These solutions are built upon two key frameworks: USG and OpenDERMS. The USG framework is designed to provide community managers with tools to establish and manage energy communities while ensuring security and privacy. Each type of energy asset is associated with a data collection mechanism and a control interface. The services interacting with the USG core system include web applications for personal energy management, energy community management, and various local optimisation services. These services leverage a blockchain-based platform to facilitate the exchange of energy and flexibility within the marketplace. On the other hand, OpenDERMS is a web application developed to aggregate and manage devices, enabling seamless communication via standard protocols. It includes a translation component, the PDA, which converts command messages from OpenDERMS into device-specific protocol messages.

The integration of USG and OpenDERMS provides a robust and secure infrastructure for managing energy assets and facilitating active participation in energy markets, thereby enhancing the flexibility and resilience of energy communities.

7 Conclusions

This report has explored the intersection of data-driven services and energy communities, highlighting the critical role of data sharing in fostering energy security and sustainability. By examining the challenges, opportunities, and best practices in this area, we have designed the groundwork for future research and practical applications aimed at optimising energy systems and empowering communities. The insights and tools discussed provide a comprehensive foundation for advancing energy transitions and enhancing the resilience of energy communities across diverse contexts.

A literature review was conducted to explore and define practices related to data-driven services for energy-secure communities. This work forms the foundation of a broader research initiative aimed at identifying best practices and research recommendations for energy community data sharing. The study focused on understanding energy data sharing from multiple perspectives, highlighting opportunities to promote energy transitions and behavioural change at the community level. Through a combination of literature review, workshops, and surveys, the aim is to inform and guide discussions on co-designing data-driven services for energy communities, aligning with the broader objectives of WP5 and supporting the implementation of these solutions across diverse European pilot sites.

At the heart of these advancements is the focus on flexibility optimisation. As renewable energy sources become more prevalent, their intermittent nature necessitates more sophisticated management tools. The development of digital twins for energy systems, predictive models for appliances, and clustering methods for household energy usage represents a concerted effort to harness data for better decision-making. These tools not only optimise individual energy consumption but also facilitate broader community-level initiatives, allowing for more effective collective self-consumption and energy-sharing models.

Moreover, the integration of these tools into community-level operations highlights the importance of collaboration between individual consumers, communities, and larger energy networks. By enabling peer-to-peer energy exchanges and offering real-time feedback mechanisms, these innovations create a more dynamic and responsive energy ecosystem. This approach helps to bridge gaps between different energy stakeholders, fostering a more interconnected and resilient energy system.

The secure edge-level solutions developed for device aggregation and participation in demand response and flexibility schemes further strengthen this interconnectedness. By ensuring secure data sharing and management across diverse energy assets, these frameworks enhance the capacity of energy communities to participate actively in the broader energy market. This integration of security and flexibility is crucial for maintaining the trust and participation of all stakeholders, from individual consumers to large industrial players.

Ultimately, the progress made in these areas points to a future where energy communities play a pivotal role in the energy transition. By aligning advanced technological tools with regulatory and social frameworks, we can create energy systems that are not only more efficient and sustainable but also more equitable and resilient. The collective efforts to address these challenges lay the ground for a more integrated and adaptive energy system, where the benefits of renewable energy and smart technologies are fully realized by all.

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